

Bari, 2-5 September 2024

ABSTRACT BOOK

a cura della Società Geologica Italiana

Geology for a sustainable management of our Planet

Politecnico di Bari

PRESIDENTS OF THE CONGRESS

Luisa Sabato (SGI), Emanuela Schingaro (SIMP).

VICEPRESIDENT OF THE CONGRESS

Marcello Tropeano (SGI).

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE COORDINATOR

Sandro Conticelli (Università di Firenze).

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Lucia Angiolini (Università di Milano), Giuseppina Balassone (Università di Napoli), Domenico Calcaterra (Università di Napoli), Angelo Camerlenghi (OGS), Serafina Carbone (Università di Catania), Chiara Cardaci (Protezione Civile), Domenico Chiarella (Royal Holloway, London), Angelo Cipriani (ISPRA), Paolo Conti (Università di Siena), Giovanni De Giudici (Università di Cagliari), Patrizia Fiannacca (Università di Catania), Diego Gatta (Università di Milano), Guido Giordano (Università di Roma Tre), Lara Maritan (Università di Padova), Annalisa Martucci (Università di Ferrara), Ilaria Mazzini (CNR-IGAG), Stefano Mazzoli (Università di Camerino), Barbara Nisi (CNR-IGG), Stefano Poli (Università di Milano), Giovanna Rizzo (Università della Basilicata), Laura Scognamiglio (INGV), Mauro Soldati (Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia), Mario Tribaudino (Università di Torino), Chiara Varone (CNR-IGAG).

ORGANISING COMMITTEE

Donato Belmonte (SIMP), Bernardo Carmina (Università di Pisa), Fabio Dioguardi (Università di Bari), Giacomo Eramo (Università di Bari), Lorenza Fascio (SIMP), Vincenzo Festa (Università di Bari), Marilena Filippucci (Università di Bari), Fulvio Franchi (Università di Bari), Salvatore Gallicchio (Università di Bari), Giulia Innamorati (SGI), Maria Lacalamita (Università di Bari), Isabella Serena Liso (Università di Bari), Stefania Lisco (Università di Bari), Piernicola Lollino (Università di Bari), Daniela Mele (Università di Bari), Patrizia Maiorano (Università di Bari), Nadia Malaspina (SIMP), Virginia Marchionni (SIMP), Giuseppe Mastronuzzi (Università di Bari), Ernesto Mesto (Università di Bari), Francesca Micheletti (Università di Bari), Mario Parise (Università di Bari), Fabio Massimo Petti (SGI), Angela Rizzo (Università di Bari), Giovanni Scardino (Università di Bari), Giovanni Scicchitano (Università di Bari), Luigi Spalluto (Università di Bari), Simona Tripaldi (Università di Bari), Alessandro Zuccari (SGI).

COMMUNICATION COMMITTEE

Giovanna Agrosì (Università di Bari), Giulia Innamorati (SGI), Christian Leo (Università di Bari), Fabio Massimo Petti (SGI), Virginia Marchionni (SIMP), Nicola Venisti (Museo di Scienze della Terra, Università di Bari), Martina Zucchi (Università di Bari).

ABSTRACT BOOK EDITORS

Bernardo Carmina, Lorenza Fascio, Giulia Innamorati, Virginia Marchionni & Fabio Massimo Petti.

COVER IMAGE

The Pontifical Basilica of Saint Nicholas (Bari).

*Papers, data, figures, maps and any other material published are covered by the copyright own by the **Società Geologica Italiana**.*

DISCLAIMER: The Società Geologica Italiana, the Editors are not responsible for the ideas, opinions, and contents of the papers published; the authors of each paper are responsible for the ideas opinions and contents published.

La Società Geologica Italiana, i curatori scientifici non sono responsabili delle opinioni espresse e delle affermazioni pubblicate negli articoli: l'autore/i è/sono il/i solo/i responsabile/i.

INDEX

OPENING CERIMONY

Jackson C.A-L. - Geoscience Communication During the Energy Transition	90
Adiyaman Lopes O. & Sabo R. - Geology and the Sustainable Development Goals	91
Bignami L. - Geology: as fascinating as difficult to describe	92
Casalini E. - The storytelling of natural beauty to learn how to recognize and share itaa.....	93

PLENARY SESSIONS

Antonucci M. - Digital classroom for petrology and mineralogy	95
Della Moretta D. - How Geoscientists can make the difference in industrial carbon storage projects	96
Erba E.* - The birth of the modern ocean and its first 180 million years of crises, speciations and extinctions	97
Foria F. & Pantaneschi S. - L'analisi qualitativa e quantitativa del rischio geomorfologico e la sua gestione tramite sistemi di allertamento lungo le infrastrutture ferroviarie	98
Hernández Molina F.J.* - Contourites and mixed depositional systems: a paradigm for deepwater sedimentary environments	99
Hudson-Edwards K.A.* - Sustainable mining of critical raw materials: opportunities and obstacles for geoscientists	100
Pellegrini M.* & Fischer M. - Carbon isotope analyses on dissolved inorganic carbon of seawater samples: sample preparation and analysis using the GasBench Plus system	101

S1. Geobiological and geochemical approaches in the study of bioconstructions and microbe-mineral interactions: new tools for modern and ancient environmental reconstructions and bio-remediation

Balzano S., Ghani J., Bettinelli A., Zhao Y., Guo L. & Funari V.* - Mine tailings characterization and potential pychoremediation	103
Borrelli M.*, Kairouani H., Micheletti F., Zaghoul M.N., Fornelli A. & Perri E. - Microbial signatures in the Early Jurassic phosphatic sandstones of the External Rif (Northern Morocco).....	104
Borrelli M.*, Perri E., Heimhofer U., Umbro B., Santagati P. & Le Pera E. - Role of microbes in the the Pliocene giant cold-seep system of the Croton Basin.....	105

ADALTA
Soluzioni software
per le Geoscienze

Cipriani M.*, Maruca G., Dominici R., Muzzupappa M., Bruno F., Lagudi A., Gallo A., Rosso A., Sanfilippo R., Bracchi V.A., Basso D. & Guido A. - ROV-based sampling as tools for geobiological determination of recent marine bioconstructions.....	106
Dela Pierre F.*, Natalicchio M., Birgel D., Giunti S., Guibourdenche L., Pellegrino L., Aloisi G. & Peckmann J. - Authigenic carbonate and native sulfur formation in Messinian (Upper Miocene) marine sediments: sedimentological, petrographical and geochemical constraints	107
Guerrieri S.*, Borrelli M., Medas D., De Giudici G. & Perri E. - Biomineralization of As-schwertmannite in acid mine drainage.....	108
Guerrieri S.*, Borrelli M., Medas D., De Giudici G., Sedda L., Musu E. & Perri E. - Heavy metal-minerals microbial mediated coprecipitation in mine tailings drainage	109
Guido A.*, Fuoco I., Vespasiano G., Cipriani M., Maruca G., Scalercio A., Talà A., Calcagnile M., Belmonte G., Alifano P., Tredici S.M., Sicoli G., Gargano D., Bloise A. & Apollaro C. - Microbial activity involved in aluminosilicate mineralization in an arsenopyrite mine.....	110
Maruca G., Cipriani M., Apollaro C., Vespasiano G., Dominici R., Bruno F., Lagudi A., Bracchi V.A., Basso D., Mauri F., Cellini E., Pirrera L., De Benedetto C., Piscitelli V.F. & Guido A.* - GIS-based protocol for benthic habitat mapping of Coralligenous build-ups (Isola Capo Rizzuto, Calabria, Italy).....	111
Natalicchio M.*, Pellegrino L., Carnevale G., Cavagna S., Dela Pierre F., Lozar F., Pastero L. & Varese C. - Minerals & microorganisms, a possible relationship: an awareness project of GEOMICROBIOlogy ...	112
Onnis P.*, Calandrelli T., Alisi C., Dore E., Fancello D., Frau F., Marras P.A., Medas D., Musu E., Pisano B., Podda F. & De Giudici G. - From bioleaching to biomining: learning from geomicrobial processes in mining areas.....	113
Santagati P.*, Borrelli M., Guerrieri S. & Perri E. - Microbial micritic cementation in a Late Pleistocene (MIS 5.5) mid-latitude shallow-water calcarenite (Gulf of Taranto, central Mediterranean).....	114
Santagati P.*, Guerrieri S., Borrelli M. & Perri E. - Capo Colonna (Crotone Basin - Southern Italy) MIS 5 calcareous bioconstructions: an association of algal, metazoan, and microbial framebuilders	115
Tenuta S.*, Evans K.A., Reddy S.R., Rickard W.D.A. & Saxey D.W. - Nanoscale biosignatures in native-Cu and sulphides from the Wadi Tayin ophiolite, Oman	116
Vespasiano G.*, Cipriani M., Maruca G., Apollaro C., Ponte M., Dominici R., Bruno F., Muzzupappa M., Rosso A., Sanfilippo R., Bracchi V.A., Basso D. & Guido A. - Integrated Geochemical/Geobiological approach for the identification of environmental proxies in Coralligenous bioconstructions.....	117
Youm C.I.*, Gueye A., Miyouna T., Ba F., Signaté A.S., Sow S.N., Sissokho M., Doumbouya M.F., Errami E. & Sow E. - Petrography of stromatolites from the summit of the Pelel Formation in the Walidiala valley (Madina Kouta Basin, Kédougou, Senegal)	118

Single crystal
& powder
diffractometry
since 1887

Gambetti
Vacuum Technology
and Related Solutions

gambetti.it

S2. The global challenge of plastic pollution: causes, impacts and solutions

Birarda G., Bonanni V., Buosi C.*, Caridi F., Casu M.A., Costanzi E., De Giudici G., Gianoncelli A., Longo E., Marras P.A., Medas D., Meneghini C., Onnis P., Pili S., Pivetta T., Sabbatini A., Tromba G., Vaccari L. & Zizic M. - Response of benthic foraminifera to plastic pollution	120
Buoninsegni J.*, Tessari U., Marrocchino E. & Vaccaro C. - Integration of microplastic gravimetric separation protocol considering sediment texture and composition	121
Canovi C.*, Siligardi C. & Cedillo-González E.I. - Investigation of the efficiency of several TiO ₂ microstructures for the photocatalytic degradation of nanoplastics	122
Croce A.*, Bertolotti M., Roveta A., Ugo F., Bertolina C., Farotto M., Bellis D., Quaglia M., Carratta L. & Maconi A. - Identification of microplastics in human tissues and fluids: a pilot study.....	123
Festa R.M.*, Lo Bue G., Musa M., Marchini A., Riccardi M.P. & Mancin N. - Extraction of microplastics from marine environmental matrices: density separation protocol validation	124
Fracchiolla T.*, Veneziano F., de Luca A., D'Abicco V., Trani R., Moretti M. & Lisco S. - Evaluation of microplastics in coastal and marine sediments of the Ionian Sea (Southern Italy)	125
Lo Bue G.*, Musa M., Kaestner A., Di Martino D., Busi M., Shakoorioskooie M., Riccardi M.P. & Mancin N. - Imaging of microplastics in bio-engineered marine substrates: a neutron tomography approach...	126
Lo Bue G.*, Musa M., Lisco S., Marchini A., Riccardi M.P. & Mancin N. - Microplastic dynamics in the littoral reefs created by Sabellariid Polychaetes in the Southern Adriatic Sea.....	127
Merlino S.*, Locritani M., Morigi C., Gerard N., Bianucci M., Muccini F., Lombardi C., Bronco S., Ricci L., De Monte C., Granata U. & Cucco A. - Plastic accumulation on a marine protected area: the case study of the Giannutri Island in Tuscan Archipelago	128
Monnanni A.*, Rimondi V., Morelli G., Nannoni A., Sforzi L., Martellini T., Cincinelli A., Chelazzi D., Laurati M., Lattanzi P. & Costagliola P. - Microplastics characterisation in shallow waters of the Arno River (Central Italy) and its discharge into the Mediterranean Sea: the main impacting role of the smallest size particles	129
Pellegrini C.*, Saliu F., Bosman A., Sammartino I., Raguso C., Mercorella A., Galvez D., Petrizzo A., Madricardo F., Lasagni M., Clemenza M., Trincardi F. & Rovere M. - Hotspots of microplastic accumulation at the land-sea transition and their spatial heterogeneity: the Po river prodelta (Adriatic Sea).....	130
Pierdomenico M.*, Casalbore D., Morgana S., Ridente D. & Chiocci F.L. - Source-to-sink propagation of marine plastic and accumulation in seafloor sediments: the role of sedimentary gravity flows	131

planetek
italia

SIMPLIFYING
THE COMPLEXITY
OF SPACE

WWW.PLANETEK.IT

EO DATA & SERVICES
| SPATIAL DATA INFRASTRUCTURES
| END-TO-END SATELLITE SOLUTIONS

Rizzo A.*, Barracane G., Bonifazi G., Capobianco G., Cucuzza P., Gorga E., Mele D., Scardino G., De Santis V., Lapietra I., La Salandra M., Lisco S., Liso S., Marsico A., Mastronuzzi G., Parise M., Serranti S., Scicchitano G. & Sozio A. - Litter distribution in marine and coastal environments: highlights from ongoing research projects 132

Sabbatini A., Birarda G., Buosi C., Caridi F.*, De Giudici G., Medas D. & Vaccari L. - Effect of plastics on marine ecosystem: preliminary findings of Phthalates (PAEs) on Gromiids 133

Sasso C.*, Lapietra I., Liso I.S., Marsico A. & Rizzo A. - Microplastics analysis from sediment samples collected at Capitolo Beach (Apulia, Italy) 134

Sozio A.*, Rizzo A., Aucelli P.P.C., Anfuso G., Barracane G., Dimuccio L., La Salandra M., Scarrica V.M., Staiano A., Tarantino M.P. & Scicchitano G. - Multidisciplinary approaches for the analysis of Beach Litter distribution in coastal environments 135

Valdrè G. *, Moro D., Moro L., Helal K.M. & Fragasso J. - Autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs including gliders) for the characterization and monitoring of environmental conditions in fresh and marine waters 136

S3. Antarctica and the Arctic: unveiling the geological past and future evolution of polar regions

Andò S.*, Perotti M., Zurli L., Torricella F., Colizza E., Ferrante G.M. & De Santis L. - High-resolution mineralogical and petrographic analysis of marine sediments in Antarctica: from silt to gravel 138

Balestrieri M.L.*, Olivetti V., Chew D., Zurli L., Zattin M., Drakou F., Cornamusini G. & Perotti M. - Multi-proxy single-grain provenance analysis to tackle growth and retreat of West Antarctic Ice Sheet: insights from apatite and zircon U-Pb dating coupled with fission-track age and geochemical analysis of apatite 139

Battaglia F., Torricella F., Belt S., Capotondi L.*, Colizza E., Colleoni F., Di Roberto A., Langone L., Giordano P., Mollenhauer G., Pochini E. & Tesi T. - GRETA (CoolinG overR the VicToria LAnd (GRETA)): resolving the Ross Sea response to continental climate change during the last two millenia 140

Bronzo L., Morigi C.*, Carbonara K., Caricchi C., Musco M.E., Douss N., Gois Smith F.S., Villa G., Cascella A. & Lucchi R.G. - Paleoclimatic reconstruction of the past 30.000 years through analysis on calcareous nanofossil assemblages on the west Spitsbergen margin 141

Caridi F.*, Sabbatini A., Howa H., Mouret A., Nardelli M.P. & Pusceddu A. - Soft- and hard-shelled foraminiferal assemblages to assess the vulnerability of Foraminifera to climate change in Kongsfjorden, Svalbard 142

Cornamusini G., Zurli L., Liberato G.P., Corti V.*, Gulbranson E.L., Perotti M. & Sandroni S. - A lithostratigraphic reappraisal of a Permian-Triassic fluvial succession at Allan Hills (Antarctica) and implications for the terrestrial end-Permian extinction event 143

Ter
Gracias
ευχαριστώ πάρα πολύ
THANK YOU
Облагодарил
ありがとうございました
Dziękuję
okashiku
Joy and Fun
Merci

Corti V.*, Spina A. & Cornamusini G. - Stratigraphic constraints on the Beacon Succession of the Transantarctic Mountains through palynological data 144

Crispini L.*, Civile D., Ferrante G.M., Locatelli M., Morelli D., Volpi V., Accettella D., Accaino F., Busetti M., Läufer A., Armadillo E., Colizza E., Salvini F. & Ruppel A. - Geodynamic processes at the Pacific margin of North Victoria Land (Antarctica): new evidence from offshore geophysical data on the crustal structure and seabed morphology (PNRA_BOOST Project)..... 145

Dumon Steenssens L.*, Lisco S., Micheletti F. & Mastronuzzi G. - Sedimentologic and petrographic characteristics of beach ridges in Terra Nova Bay (Antarctica)..... 146

Dumon Steenssens L.*, d’Elia M., Quarta G. & Mastronuzzi G. : ¹⁴C age determination of beaches ridges from Terra Nova Bay, Antarctica..... 147

Ferraccioli F.*, Ebbing J., Wiens D., Eagles G., Gohl K., Forsberg R., Armadillo E., Young D., Blankenship D.D., Aitken A.R.A., Jordan T.J., Mather B., Ford J., Verdoya M. & Jacobs J. - 4D heterogeneity in geological boundary conditions beneath the West and East Antarctic ice sheets: what have we learnt and what do we need to know?..... 148

Fioraso M.*, Olivetti V., Balsamo F., Rossetti F., Zattin M. & Cornamusini G. - Oligocene-Miocene structurally-controlled hydrothermal activity along the Transantarctic Mountains: evidence from apatite thermochronology 149

Galli G.*, Morigi C., Thuy B. & Gariboldi K. - The use of macrofaunal microfossils to unveil past Holocene changes: a case study from Edisto Inlet (Ross Sea, Antarctica)..... 150

Gamboa Sojo V.M., Morigi C.*, Langone L. & Lucchi R.G. - Paleoceanographic changes suggested by planktic and benthic foraminifera in the Western Svalbard Slope (Bellsund Drift) during the last century..... 151

Langone L.*, Bensi M., Aulicino G., Battaglia F., Caridi F., Carotenuto A., Cerino F., Diociaiuti T., Gallerani A., Giglio F., Kovacevic V., Kralj M., Mangoni O., Mansutti P., Monti M., Morigi C., Patrolecco L., Rauseo J., Relitti F., Retelletti Brogi S., Sabbatini A., Serino E., Tesi T., Ursella L., Greggio N. & Giordano P. - Mechanisms driving formation and preservation of the laminated sediments of Edisto Inlet, western Ross Sea (Antarctica): the sub-seasonal variability of particle composition and fluxes .. 152

Lucchi R.G.*, St. John K., Ronge T. & IODP Exp-403 Science Party - IODP Expedition 403 Eastern Fram Strait Paleo-Archive: preliminary results from the last expedition of the International Ocean Discovery Program 153

Olivetti O.*, Cattò S. & Zattin M. - The topography of the high latitude mountain chain and the enigma of high-standing plateau..... 154

infrastructure
is a social value

etsingegneria.it

Pastore G.*, Marschalek J., van de Flierdt T., Andò S., Vermeesch P. & Carter A. - Contrasting provenance signals during Pleistocene interglacial periods influenced by West Antarctic Ice Sheet climatic response recorded at IODP Site U1524 exp. 37	155
Perotti M., Zurli L.*, Marschalek J., Mallery C., van de Flierdt T., Licht K., De Santis L., McKay R., Kulhanek D. & Expedition 374 Scientists - Clast petrography from IODP 374 cores in the central Ross Sea (Antarctica): implications for sediment provenance and source terranes.....	156
Sabbatini A. *, Morigi C., Bartolini A.C., Bardin J., Caridi F. & Monti M. - Assessing planktonic foraminiferal species from Antarctic sea-ice as a paleoceanographic proxy: preliminary insights	157
Sciarra A.*, Ruggiero L., Mazzini A., Florindo F., Wilson G., Mazzoli C., Anderson J.T.H., Olivetti V., Romano V., Sassi R., Bigi S. & Ciotoli G. - A multidisciplinary investigation into the source and impact of greenhouse gases in the Dry Valleys, Antarctica.....	158
Simonetti M.*, Montomoli C., Capponi G., Salvatore M.C., Casale S., Musumeci G., Cox S., Lyttle B.S., Pertusati P.C. & Läufer A. - Geological map of the Convoy Range and Franklin Island quadrangles (Victoria Land, Antarctica)	159
Tomassini A. *, Rocchi I., Masotta M., Petrelli M., Ágreda-López M., Ubide T. & Rocchi S. - Ice load modulation of plumbing system dynamics: Insights from intracrystalline texture and chemistry at The Pleiades Volcanic Field, Antarctica	160
 S4. Chemostratigraphy through time and space: Reconstruction of palaeoenvironment and palaeoclimate by using geochemical proxies and isotopes	
Akaki M.*, Sato H., Onoue T., Maron M., Ishikawa A. & Rigo M. - Geochemical studies across the Norian/Rhaetian boundary in the Pignola-Abriola section of the Lagonegro Basin, southern Italy	162
Aversa L., Cornacchia I.*, Aldega L., Catanzariti R., Gori F., Marianelli D. & Brandano M. - Clay minerals, trace elements and stable isotope geochemistry reveal increased biogeochemical weathering during the Middle Eocene Climatic Optimum: the Ligurian Alps record (northern Italy).....	163
Baldassarri L. *, Fanti F., Dinelli E. & Bais G. - Geochemical analysis and palaeoenvironmental reconstruction of the laminated limestones from the Villaggio del Pescatore fossil site (Trieste, Italy)	164
Brocker K.*, Border E., Montagna P., Rigo M., Áki Ragnarsson S., Valdimarsson H., Hilma Ólafsdóttir S., Therre S., Fohlmeister J., Trotter J., McCulloch M., Schröder-Ritzrau A., Lausecker M., Blaser P., Reverdin G., Colin C. & Norbert F. - Seawater temperatures, pH and water mass provenance reconstructions over the last century from cold-water coral geochemistry in the North Atlantic Ocean.....	165

A RELIABLE GEOLOGY
FOR YOUR PROJECTS

Caruso A.*, Maiorano P., Addante M., Cosentino C., Fasone S., Girone A., Guccione P., Maccotta A., Marino M., Militello G., Pernice M. & Scopelliti G. - The PRIN “REMEPP” project: response of Mediterranean calcareous plankton to CO ₂ variability during some intervals of the Plio/Pleistocene	166
Catania G.*, Barbagallo V., Brandano M., Borzi L., Cornacchia I., Distefano S., Pellegrino A., Mancini A., Marianelli D., Maniscalco R., Salerno A. & Di Stefano A. - Middle Miocene paleoclimatic phases: a Central Mediterranean perspective from the SE Sicily sedimentary succession.....	167
Columbu A.*, Asanidze L., Zanchetta G., Burns S., Lezhava Z., Tsikarishvili K., Avkopashvili I., Natali S., Luppichini M., Isola I., McGee D. & Fleitmann D. - Quantitative reconstruction of temperature changes during the last ~13500 years in Georgia through stable isotopes ($\delta^2\text{H}$ - $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) from speleothems fluid inclusions and calcite	168
Khatami M., Vahdati B., Gasparrini M.*, Lasseur E., Spina A., Montano D., Dapiaggi M., Compostella C., Berra F., Decarlis A. & Ceriani A. - Chemostratigraphy study of the Toarcian marine deposits from the Paris Basin southern margin	169
Mancini A.*, Cornacchia I., Lamal J., Capezzuoli E., Swennen R. & Brandano M. - Deciphering climate changes from stable Isotopes in continental carbonate deposits: the <i>Lapis Tiburtinus</i> travertine succession (Acque Albule Basin, Tivoli, Central Italy).....	170
Mancini A.M.*, Marino G., Dela Pierre F. & Negri A. - ECORD and IODP-Italy Project: the mediterranean deoxygenation dynamics during the Pliocene in the Mediterranean.....	171
Marianelli D.*, Yang J., Medici G., Cornacchia I., Aversa L. & Brandano M. - Diagenesis of karsified deposits to reconstruct the sea level drop at the Eocene-Oligocene Transition in the Apulian Platform, Southeastern Italy	172
Maron M.*, Onoue T., Satolli S., Soda K., Sato H., Muttoni G. & Rigo M. - Weathering trends in the Norian through geochemical and rock magnetic analyses from the Pignola-Abriola Section (Lagonegro Basin, Italy).....	173
Omori S.*, Sato H., Onoue T. & Rigo M. - High-resolution radiolarian biostratigraphy across the impact ejecta layer in the upper Norian hemipelagic sediments in the Sasso di Castalda section, southern Italy	174
Onoue T.*, Hori S., Tomimatsu Y. & Rigo M. - A dilute sodium hydroxide technique for extracting radiolarians and conodonts from chert	175
Preto N.*, Borsato A., Carampin R., Della Porta G., Frisia S., Gattolin G., Klügel A., Himmler T., Westphal H. & Zorzi F. - On the potential and pitfalls of REE+Y analyses on fossil microbial carbonates: two case studies from the Triassic of the Dolomites compared	176
Rigo M.*, Bertinelli A., Onoue T., Sato H., Tomimatsu Y., Maron M., Zaffani M., Satolli S., Roghi G. & Nicora A. - The Pignola-Abriola section (southern Apennines, Italy): a GSSP candidate for the base of the Rhaetian Stage	177
Rigo M.*, Di Stefano P. & Todaro S. - Organic carbon isotope ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$) curve and extinction trends across the Triassic/Jurassic boundary at Mt Sparagio (Italy): a tool for global correlations between peritidal and pelagic successions	178
Sato H.*, Ishikawa A., Lowery C.M., Arenillas I., Arz J.A., Gilibert V., Claeys P., Goderis S., Gulick S.P.S. & Morgan J.V. - Post-impact marine environment within the Chicxulub impact basin inferred from Re-Os isotopes.....	179
Tomimatsu Y., Onoue T.*, Sato H. & Rigo M. - Oceanic anoxia during the Carnian Pluvial Episode (Late Triassic) in the Panthalassa Ocean	180

S5. Geosciences for Cultural Heritages

Annese C., Bellopede R.*, Intini P.C., Intini P., Lamanna L.M., Marini P., Merico A., Quartulli A. & Sivilli S. - Itria Valley limestone: a multidisciplinary study on the use of the Apulian georesources in the Cultural Heritage	182
Balassone G.*, Serritella A., Rizzo M.L., De Bonis A., Valente E. & Boni P. - Archaeometric investigations on iron slags from the metallurgical workshop of Caselle in Pittari settlement (Campania region, southern Italy): a first look	183
Bruzzone L.*, Gaggero L. & Pallecchi S. - Reconstructing Pompeii's past: insights from fossilized archaeological remains in reused amphorae from Civic Building 3, Via dell'Abbondanza	184

Bruzzone L. *, Gaggero L., Zucchiatti A. & Molera J. - Evaluating erythrite as a potential source for arsenic-free cobalt blue pigment production: replication of historical recipes and thermal treatments	185
Calia A., Melica D., Pellegrino E. & Quarta G.* - Surface degradation and conservation strategies in the marine environment: the case of the church of S. Salvatore, in Monopoli (Bari)	186
Calzolari L. *, Fernandez-Martinez A., Magnin V., Medeghini L. & Mignardi S. - Ancient Roman mortars under synchrotron light: unravelling the nature of disordered phases	187
Cantisani E., Cappuccini L., Gaucci A., Legnaioli S., Mangani S.M.E.*, Menchelli S., Rosselli L. & Volpe L. - APENNINESCAPE: a transdisciplinary approach to investigate the relationship between settlement dynamics and material exploitation in the northern Apennines during the 1 st millennium BC. Preliminary archaeometric results	188
Capriotti S. *, Mignardi S., Stasolla F.R., Scardapane S. & Medeghini L. - Deep Learning as new approach for the classification of Holy Sepulchre ceramics	189
Collina C., D’Aniello M., Izzo F.*, Langella A., Repola L. & Donadio C. - Geomineralogical and geoarchaeological findings in Roccia San Sebastiano cave at Mondragone, central Italy	190
Comite V. *, Formenti M., Bergomi A., Lombardi C.A., Borelli M., Morale D., Ugolini S., Fermo P., Cavaterra C., Castellano C. & Della Pina C. - Exploring the role of heavy metals in sulphation processes and black crust formation on outdoor exposed monuments	191
Conforti J. *, Allegretta I., Muntoni I.M., Delluniversità E., Terzano R., Angeli L. & Eramo G. - Chert supplies in Early Neolithic of Matera area: new data from Giavarra, Murgia Timone and Trasanello	192
d’Aniello F., Germinario C., Izzo F., Pagano S., Scanu M. *, Sernicola L., Verde M. & De Bonis A. - De-faience. Unveiling ancient craftsmanship: egyptian faience technique in Early Ethiopian beads	193
Di Benedetto C. *, Graziano S.F., Naso A. & Rispoli C. - The Etruscan necropolis of Sasso Pinzuto (Tuscania, VT): preliminary mineralogical characterization of geomaterials	194
Di Leo P. *, Lubraco G., Corrado G., Ferrara V. & Vita C. - A multidisciplinary approach to understand exploitation of ancient georesources for the matt painted pottery production from Basilicata: technology and provenance in the north-Lucanian district	195
Dimuccio L.A., Micheletti F., Amaral D. *, Vicente S., Mendes A.L., Simões F., Duarte M. & Acquafredda P. - Provenance analysis of stone tesserae and mortars used in the mosaic pavements of São Simão Roman Villa (Penela, central Portugal): preliminary data	196
Eramo G. *, Bertola S., Carletti E., Conati Barbaro C., Conforti J., Ferrero A., Fioretti G., Moscone D., Pizziolo G., Santo A.P., Spalluto L. & Lo Vetro D. - The Openlit Project: a first step for an open access lithotheque of italian knappable rocks	197
Eramo G., Tema E. & Muntoni I.M. * - Archaeometric study of two Hellenistic pottery kilns in Ascoli Satriano (FG): a combined minero-petrographic and archaeomagnetic approach	198
Eroğlu M. *, Barba L., Crisci G.M., Cura M., De Luca R., Kadioğlu Y.K., Pecci A., Taranto M. & Miriello D. - Provenance of the raw materials used in the mortars and bricks take from Hagia Sophia (Istanbul, Turkey): preliminary results	199
Franceschini M. *, Cantisani E., Vettori S., Chelazzi L., Di Benedetto F. & Ismaelli T. - Further insight into the provenancing of terracottas from the Athenaion in Castro (Apulia, Italy)	200
Franceschini M.M.N. *, Calandra S., Vettori S., Ismaelli T., Scardozzi G., Caggia M.P. & Cantisani E. - Mortars in the archaeological site of Hierapolis of Phrygia (Denizli, Turkey) from Imperial to Byzantine age .	201
Gadaleta E. *, Acquafredda P., De Giorgi M., Eramo G., Neri E., Scandale E. & Tempesta G. - Natural and artificial glass in the floor mosaic of Otranto Cathedral (Apulia, Southern Italy)	202
Indelicato V. *, Punturo R., Mineo S., Pappalardo G., Lanzafame G., Visalli R. & Cirrincione R. - Multi-analytical characterization of main lithotypes employed in the Val di Noto UNESCO sites (south-eastern Sicily)	203
Krizova B. *, Zini L., Calligaris C., Busetti A., Corradetti A., Černok A., Consorti L., Bensi S., Piano C. & Franceschi M. - Kras-Carso II Interreg European project. Multidisciplinary research towards promoting the geological heritage of the Classical Karst	204
La Russa M. *, Ricca M., Barbieri L., Bruno F., Baika K., Raxis P., Sillion M., Nunes C., Padovan R. & Ferreira F. - Bridging gaps in blue expertise through a triple transition training model for the UCH field: new challenges in uBlueTec project	205

Lepore A.*, Arzarello M., Germinario C., Mercurio M. & Grifa C. - Multianalytical study of lithic materials from the prehistorical site of Pirro Nord: preliminary results	206
Lezzerini M.*, Aquino A. & Pagnotta S. - Lime mortar production: the case of Panchina calcarenite from Tyrrhenian coast	207
Lo Riso M., Buccione R., Rizzo G.*, De Bonis A. & Teghil R. - Preliminary results of the petrographic and mineralogical study of the Oenotria ceramic artifact (Southern Italy)	208
Luconi I.*, Ercoli R. & Paris E. - Artificial weathering and surficial consolidation techniques applied to the ‘Peperino’ from the Alban Hills volcano (Latium, Italy)	209
Macchia A., Diliberto Cascio C., Zicarelli M.A., Alisi C., Catania V., Schillaci D., La Russa M.F. & Ruffolo S.A.* - Evaluating biosurfactants as eco-friendly biocides (TEch4YOU Project)	210
Mancini S.*, Dino G.A., Tazzini A. & Gambino F. - The Mg/Ca ratio in mortars used in ancient rural buildings in the north-Eastern Piedmont plain: a methodology to support archaeological studies	211
Maritan L.*, Filippou V., Renson V., Pasqual D., Cattò S., Koutovaki E., Nodarou E., Cantisani E., Dikomitou Eliadou M. & Zomeni Z. - Influence of clay processing on bulk chemistry signature in ancient pottery productions	212
Mascaro M.E.*, Auriemma R., Mazzoli C. & Maritan L. - Investigating post-depositional alterations in underwater ceramics. The case of the archaeological site of Torre Santa Sabina (south-eastern Italy) .	213
Mastrorilli M.*, De Felice G., Turchiano M. & Eramo G. - The POW camp 65 (Altamura, Southern Italy) as a case study for archeometry and contemporary archaeology	214
Menta S.*, Stroschio A., Mazzoleni P. & Belfiore C.M. - Reproduction of ancient lime mortars from the Baroque built heritage of Catania (Sicily): an experimental study	215
Morabito G.*, Gatta G.D., Marinoni N., Colombo C., Catrambone M., Botto M. & Pedrazzi T. - Investigating the past: a multi-analytical approach for the analysis of Phoenician pottery from the archaeological site of Pani Loriga	216
Muntoni I. M.*, Eramo G., Ruggiero G. & Clemens L. - Sand slaking in the lime mortars of Tertiveri (Foggia, 12 th -15 th century)	217
Occhipinti R.*, Belfiore C. M., Fugazzotto M., Barone G. & Mazzoleni P. - The mortars as a marker of the evolution over time of materials and construction techniques in the Benedictine Monastery of Catania	218
Pagano S.*, Germinario C., Giorgi E., Mercurio M. & Grifa C. - Preliminary diagnostic analyses of the wall painting materials of the Vignale’s villa (Tuscany region, central Italy)	219
Pantuso A.*, Apollaro C., Fuoco I., La Russa M.F. & Ricca M. - New application perspectives of reaction path modelling for the conservation of cultural heritage: preliminary presentation of a novel research project	220
Ravasi T., Haynes I., Vagnuzzi S., Rispoli C., Randazzo L.* & La Russa M.F. - Assessing construction techniques through mineralogical-petrographic analysis of Roman mortars: insights into Imperial economic investments in building projects	221
Rea C.*, Di Fazio M., Mercuri L., Calzolari L., Capriotti S., Mignardi S., Dallai L., Stasolla F.R. & Medeghini L. - Archaeometric investigation of lithic materials from the archaeological site of the Holy Sepulchre (Jerusalem)	222
Rea C., Bastida Armesto M., Calzolari L., Di Fazio M., Capriotti S., Mignardi S., Stasolla F.R. & Medeghini L.* - Statistical analysis of IR spectra of mortar for studying the relationship between building phases	223
Ricca M.*, La Russa M., Lagudi A., Bruno F., Chronakis A., Davidde B., Emde B., Kyprouli V., Krebs P., Krinidis S., Manglis A., Michailidis T. I., Mizaikoff B., Podvorica L., Perasso Sacco C., Rajpal S., Rieck M., Tamburrino S. & Kotsidis E. - Advancing in underwater cultural heritage monitoring: the case of NERITES Project	224
Ricca M., La Russa M.F., Sfravara F., Catania V., Montana G. & Randazzo L.* - SOUTH - Safeguard Of sUbmerged cULtural Heritage: project presentation	225
Rovella N.*, Cirone M., Belfiore C.M., Török Á., Figoli A. & La Russa M.F. - Inside the stone: new elements for targeted conservation of Sicilian Baroque Monuments	226
Santarsiere C.*, Palladino G. & Bentivenga M. - The “Cantine di Sant’Angelo Le Fratte” geosite and the historical-cultural heritage used as a growth driver for an inland area of Basilicata	227

Scanu M.*, Capaldi C., Ciotola A., D'Uva F., Morra V., Verde M. & De Bonis A. - African amphorae from Cumae: archaeometric study for provenance and technological features	228
Spadavecchia S.*, Cappelletti P., Rispoli C., Montesano G. & Cesarano M. - Mineralogical and technological characterization of pozzolan mortars from the Brick Amphitheater in Nola (NA)	229
Torok A.* - Air pollution related deterioration of limestone heritage: an overview	230
Valdrè G.*, Grillini G.C., Moro D. & Ulian G. - Finishes in architectural elements: "Domus Pasolini" of Faenza	231
Verde M., De Bonis A., Di Benedetto C.*, Izzo F., Picone R. & Morra V. - Arianna's Palette: a diagnostic study of the painting walls of the house of Arianna in Pompeii	232
S6. Geosciences on display: the role of Natural History Museums in the future of our planet	
Barbagli F.* - What is the role of Natural History Museums in the future of our planet?	234
Barone G., Carbone C., Fugazzotto M., Mauro D., Merlini M., Nazzareni S.* & Pratesi G. - The SIMP Commission on Museums: a network for sharing and promoting museum activities	235
Belmonte D.* & Carbone C. - Development and valorization of the historical and modern mineral collections of the Department of Earth, Environment and Life Sciences (DISTAV), University of Genova	236
Benvenuti M.*, Barbagli F., Fabrizi L., Manca R. & Moggi Cecchi V. - An "enlightened" museum of Nature, Art and Science. Rediscovering Specola 250 years after its foundation	237
Bosi F., Lapaire J., Meisser N., Pasero M.* & Rumsey M. - On the preservation and the availability of holotype minerals	238
Bruno F.*, Mollo F., Di Cuia P., Cozza M., Sardella R., Iurino D.A., Strani F., Franzese F. & Bellucci L. - Interactive exhibits, gamification and digital storytelling in Scientific Museums: the case of MUGEPA in Rotonda	239
Ciani F., Manca R.*, Lastrucci L., Costagliola P., Benvenuti M. & Rimondi V. - Enhancing the accessibility of the Herbaria of the University of Florence by reducing mercury contamination due to historical conservation treatments	240
Contessi M.*, Balzani R., Fanti F., Caruso C. & Managlia A. - From a XIX century museum to a 3D digital experience: the challenges of making a geological museum appealing to modern audience	241
D'Arpa C.*, Di Patti C., Surdi G. & Incarbona A. - The Arab-Norman itinerary stones: where geological history meets the local artistic heritage	242
Fabrizi L.*, Moggi Cecchi V., Barbagli F. & Benvenuti M. - A dual approach to enhance the Targioni Tozzetti collection, a little-known mineralogical heritage: digital and analytical methods	243
Franza A.* & Pratesi G. - Stories for the future. The cataloging of the Italian geo-mineralogical heritage	244
Furlan A.*, Contessi M. & Fanti F. - Taxonomic diversity of fossil vertebrates from the quaternary deposits of the Karst Pit of Cà Negra (Croatia)	245
Majorana S.* & Barone G. - The cataloguing of the scientific instruments of the University of Catania: research and prospects	246
Mauro D.*, Biagioni C. & Bonaccorsi E. - The Angelo Da Costa mineral collection: a new acquisition of the Natural History Museum of the University of Pisa	247
Merlini M.* & Mangano C. - The mineralogical collections at the Earth's Science Department, University of Milano: history, conservation, digitization, and valorization	248
Micheletti F.*, Coppola G., Fanelli G., Fornelli A., Montenegro V., Santarcangelo S., Semeraro V., Venisti N. & Monno A. - Museums for the development of inclusive education practices: a case study in the Earth Sciences Museum - University of Bari Aldo Moro	249
Moggi Cecchi V.*, Fabrizi L., Barbagli F. & Benvenuti M. - From the past to the future: the new exhibition of the Mineralogical collection of the Florence University Natural History Museum and its relocation to the "La Specola"	250
Petrizzelli M., Francescangeli R., Mesto E., Monno A., Sabato L., Scillitani G., Simone O., Spalluto L. & Tropeano M.* - The late Cenomanian Aigialosaur (Reptilia, Squamata) exposed in the Earth Science Museum of Bari University (Italy)	251
Senesi M.* & Fino M. - The mineralogical and petrographic collections of the Regional Museum of Natural Sciences in Turin, Italy: a dazzling journey through the wonders of nature	252

Spironello M.Y.*, Majorana S., Barone G. & Fugazzotto M. - A multi-sensory experimental laboratory for Earth Sciences at the Museum of Sicilian Knowledge and Mirabilia of the University of Catania	253
Storta E.*, Senesi M. & Borghi A. - Mèmora: a showcase for the cultural heritage of Piemonte Region	254
Terranova E.*, Casati S., Bosio G., Di Cencio A., Pieri A. & Collareta A. - “Fauglia... un mare di anni fa”: a new palaeontological exhibition and an example of valorization of the palaeontological heritage in the Fauglia Municipality (Pisa Province, Italy)	255
Tilley L.*, Kroh A., Kvaček J., Howe M., Mergen P., Miller G., Dijkema T. & Norton B. - Unveiling Earth archives: harnessing Earth Science collections to navigate modern challenges	256
Veronese M.* & Artioli G. - Falsification techniques and materials in Geoheritage	257
Zazzera A.*, Spisso N., De Prezzo G., Bruno Stamerra F., Spada I., Marsico A., La Perna R., Marino M., Venisti N. & Girone A. - Digitalization and reconstruction of Pleistocene vertebrates from Museo di Scienze della Terra (University of Bari Aldo Moro) for the valorization of the Apulian paleontological heritage and territory	258
 S7. Vibrational spectroscopy studies of geomaterials: case studies and new perspectives	
Bernabale M.*, Cognigni F., Contessi S., Silvestri S., La Penna G., Spagnoli F., De Vito C. & Rossi M. - Investigating corrosion systems in archaeological artifacts from Motya (Sicily, Italy): a micro-Raman spectroscopy and correlative imaging approach	260
Calzolari L.*, Fernandez-Martinez A., Capriotti S., Di Fazio M. & Mignardi S. - Archaeological mortars under IR light: application of IR spectroscopic techniques for the study of hydraulic Roman mortars	261
Capriotti S.*, Di Fazio M., Miele F., Mattia V. & Annoscia G.M. - An Archaeometric Investigation to analyze some medieval rings from Cencelle (Tarquinia, VT)	262
Ciccola A.*, Ioele M. & Postorino P. - The Deposition by Raffaello: a rediscovery of old cross-sections through vibrational spectroscopies	263
Coccatto A.*, Barone G., Mazzoleni P. & Prag J. - Raman spectroscopy reveals pigments on ancient Sicilian inscriptions	264
Conti C.* - Advanced deep Raman Spectroscopy methods for the non-invasive investigation of materials subsurface: impact on Heritage Science	265
Corrente G.*, Caggiani M.C., Eramo G., Lanzafame G., Mazzoleni P., Militello P.M. & Barone G. - Characterization of chert raw material using a non-invasive approach: the case of Hyblean foreland (South-Eastern Sicily)	266
Di Fazio M.*, Calzolari L., Rea C., Capriotti S. & Medeghini L. - Evaluation of an IR multi-methods protocol for the study of Cultural Heritage	267
Di Fazio M.*, Chiarello F., Miele F., Melega A., Nastasi A., Annoscia G.M. & Mignardi S. - The evolution of the corrosion process of medieval objects through IR-spectroscopy	268
Fornasini L.*, Achilli A., Mantovani L., Barone G., Mazzoleni P. & Bersani D. - Pros and cons on the investigation of geopolymers through micro-Raman spectroscopy	269
Fornasini L.*, Bersani D., Saviane L., Mantovani L., Iacumin P. & Villicich R. - A multi-technique investigation for provenance determination of white marbles from the Roman villa in Fiumana (Forlì-Cesena, Italy)	270
Gadaleta E.*, Tempesta G., De Giorgi M., Neri E. & Scandale E. - Proposal of an interdisciplinary protocol for the archaeometric study of mosaics by spectroscopic methods and history of art	271
Giustetto R.*, Ricchiardi G., Bonino F. & Barbero N. - Novel hybrid materials inspired by ancient technologies: the case of ‘PALY@DAPI’	272
Lubraco G.*, Ferrara V., Medici L., Sogliani F. & Di Leo P. - Answering archaeometric questions on technology and provenance relative to emblematic ancient ceramic productions in Basilicata by combining micro-Raman spectroscopy, micro X-ray fluorescence and micro X-ray diffraction to the study of pigments	273
Martiniello S.*, Capitanio A., Legnaioli S. & Raneri S. - Gemstone, treatments and imitations in medieval goldworking: a gemmological and spectroscopic combined approach	274
Moricca C., Ciccola A.*, Matassa R., Favero G., Nottola S., Nigro L., Spagnoli F., Nucara A. & Sadori L. - Phoenician seeds are rich in minerals: a multi-analytical study of mineralised archaeobotanical remains from the archaeological site of Motya	275

Porcaro M.*, Cognigni F., La Penna G., Proietti A., Regoli C., Casi C., Carosi S., Rossi M., Brunetti A. & De Vito C. - Analyzing the structure and chemical composition of an Etruscan bronze fibula from Tomb Number 129 at Vulci (VT, Italy) through a non-destructive multi-analytical approach	276
Porcaro M.*, Mazzotta G., Michetti L.M., Conti A., De Caro T., Brunetti A. & De Vito C. - Microstructure, chemistry and corrosion products of copper and copper alloys of artefacts from Pyrgi (Italy) through a multi-analytical approach	277
Rea C.*, Calzolari L., Capriotti S., De Vito C., Aurisicchio C., Mignardi S. & Medeghini L. - Application of infrared external reflection spectroscopy in the identification of emerald provenance	278
Spironello M.Y.*, Barone G., Mazzoleni P., Caggiani M.C. & Fugazzotto M. - Precious votive offerings in 17 th - and 18 th -century Sicilian production: non-invasive gemmological analyses	279
Stagno V.*, Di Fazio M., Giuliani L. & Capuani S. - Non-invasive combined FT-IR and NMR protocol to assess the cleaning action of a lignin-based hydrogel on stones	280
Tempesta G.*, Monno A., de Ceglia F.P. & Maraschi A. - On site analyses of geomaterials in Sansevero Chapel Museum (Naples)	281
Tempesta G.*, Calvano C.D. & Rigante E.C.L. - Spectroscopic studies of white and black pigments in a Dali painting	282
 S8. Geodiversity, Geoheritage and Geotourism: wondering about awareness for a sustainable Planet	
Adanti B.*, Corrado S., Cecili A. & Coppola D. - Virtual geological walk to discover the historical-artistic heritage of Rome and its lithoid resources: the Basilica di San Paolo fuori le mura	284
Alvioli M.* & Melelli L. - URGERE: URban GEodiversity for a Resilient Environment	285
Bellini F.*, Sabato S. & Tropeano M. - Exploring geodiversity through historical fountains and ancient springs: geotouristic paths in the Premurgia Region for sustainable development (Puglia, Southern Italy)	286
Burnelli M.*, Melelli L. & Alvioli M. - High-resolution geomorphodiversity and anthropization indices of Italy for urban geomorphology	287
Calderón-Cucunuba L.P.*, Melelli L., Burnelli M., Pica A., Vergari F. & Del Monte M. - Geomorphodiversity in urban areas and the role of geomorphological maps: the study case of Perugia (Central Italy)	288
Casale M.*, Gambino F., Borghi A., Beltramo R., Vesce E., Vari C., Giardino M. & Dino G.A. - Unveiling the interplay of mining activities and geo-tourism: an analysis in the Northern Italian region	289
Delmonaco G.*, Brustia E., Pompili R., Primerano P. & Traversa F. - The PanAfGeo Project: the role and experience of ISPRA, Geological Survey of Italy for the enhancement and protection of geological heritage	290
Delmonaco G.*, Pompili R., Puzzilli L.M. & Traversa F. - Geology and cultural heritage in Petra (Jordan): evolution and degradation in relation with tourism management	291
Dimuccio L.A.*, Aubry T., Rodrigues N. & Cunha L. - Multidisciplinary scientific investigation supporting assessment, valorisation, and management of geoheritage: lessons from CLIMATE@COA project	292
Ferrando A.*, Faccini F., Coratza P., Vandelli V. & Reynard E. - Degradation risk and sensitivity to climate change of geosites: a methodology for quantitative assessment	293
Festa V.*, Sabato L. & Tropeano M. - In search for a key area for geotourism? The example of “Sassi”, the old town of Matera (Southern Italy)	294
Gianoglio F.*, Caprioglio M.C., Castello G., Fiori C. & Marescotti P. - Geotourism as a tool for geoheritage promotion: a geotrail project in Beigua UNESCO Global Geopark (Liguria, Italy)	295
Giardino M.*, Negri A., Storta E., Mantovani A. & Guerini M. - The role of geosciences to activate the virtuous circle: awareness of geodiversity values - enhancement of geoheritage - growth of sustainable geotourism - public engagement	296
Lozar F.*, Gerbaudo A., Giardino M., Perona S. & Zambrotta M. - Dynamic geodiversity and environmental sustainability within alpine glacial areas: educational values for the secondary schools	297
Lozar F., Gerbaudo A. & Tonon M.D.* - Geosites as a tool for climate change education: a case study in Piedmont, IT	298
Lucarini M.*, Brustia E., Olivetta L., Pompili R. & Primerano P. - Geosites inventory and territorial planning	299

Micheletti F., Fanelli G.*, Festa V., Fornelli A., Bruno G., Gjata I. & Tommasi F. - Geosites as natural scientific laboratory: investigating the links between geology, soil chemistry and botany	300
Morsilli M.* - Urban geology and geoheritage conservation: enhancing aspiring UNESCO geopark development in the Gargano promontory	301
Motti A.*, Berti F. & Natali N. - The new geosites identified by the Sezione Geologica regionale and the geological forms of the landscape in Umbria	302
Motti A.*, Berti F., Natali N. & Ognà M. - Geotourism: empowering geologists or engaging the masses?	303
Muscioni M.*, Arbullà D. & Fanti F. - The relevance and current state of the Villaggio del Pescatore lagerstätte (Campanian, Italy)	304
Negri A.*, Storta E., Guerini M., Khoso R.B., Mantovani A. & Giardino M. - Geoheritage and cultural heritage in the Sesia Val Grande UNESCO Global Geopark (North-West Italy): new approach for monitoring and assessing geosites and cultural sites	305
Pica A.*, Montaldi A., Capotorti G. & Del Monte M. - Geodiversity - biodiversity relationship for the identification and conservation of priority natural areas in urban ecosystems. The case study of the city of Rome	306
Pirani G.* & Mengarelli M. - Eastern side of Monte San Vicino: discovering its geo-environmental and architectural heritage	307
Primerano P.*, Brustia E., Funaro M., Gerardi M., Lucarini M., Olivetta L. & Pompili R. - The Italian Geosites Inventory: making travellers aware through knowledge of geodiversity	308
Punturo R., La Rosa A., Maniscalco R. & Cirrincione R.* - Gabara Park: a magic place to recall sicilian mining history	309
Sabato L.* & Tropeano M. - Paintings and writings by Carlo Levi: an unlikely combination with geology? ..	310
Tropeano M., Caldara M.A., De Santis V., Festa V.*, Parise M., Sabato L., Spalluto L., Francescangeli R., Iurilli V., Mastronuzzi G.A., Petruzzelli M., Bellini F., Cicala M., Lippolis E., Petti F.M., Antonelli M., Cardia S., Conti J., La Perna R., Marino M., Marsico A., Sacco E., Fiore A., Simone O., Valletta S., D'Ettore U.S., De Giorgio V., Liso I.S., Rosati A., Stigliano E. & Venezia V. - Evidences of geodiversity in Murge and Premurge territories (Southern Italy), potential training grounds for geotouristic experiences	311
Urban I.*, Bridi E., Cesare B., Mazzoli C. & Preto N. - Heritage stones: the case of Aurisina Limestone to promote geodiversity in the Classical Karst cross-border area	312
Venezia V.*, Bellini F., Festa V., Sabato L. & Tropeano M. - The Water and the Rock: a geotouristic route through the geology of springs and fountains in Matera (Basilicata, Southern Italy)	313
Youm C.I.*, Doumbouya M.F., Gueye A., García-Villalba E., Sow I.S., Samba R., Thiao G., Errami E., Morales J.A. & Sow E. - Promotion and enhancement of the geoheritage of the Dindéfélo Geopark Project of the Dindéfélo Community Nature Reserve (Kédougou, Senegal)	314
S9. Advances in remote sensing for hazard monitoring and geo-resource management through multi-dimensional digital models	
Bellini F.*, Colacicco R., Marra M., Sabato L. & Tropeano M. - Digital geotourism: unveiling the geological heritage of Laterza (Puglia, Southern Italy)	316
Binetti M.S.*, Massarelli C. & Uricchio V.F. - Monitoring and identification of environmental crimes: a satellite imagery and machine learning approach	317
Caso F., Piloni C.B., Filippi M., Pezzotta A., Fazio E., Visalli R., Ortolano G., Roda M.* & Zucali M. - Combining traditional and quantitative multiscale structural analysis to reconstruct the tectono-metamorphic evolution of migmatitic basements: the case of the Valpelline Series, Dent-Blanche Tectonic System, Western Alps	318
Corradetti A.*, Tavani S., Delogkos E. & Camanni G. - Structural characterization of a quarry showing normal faulting and bedding parallel slip: insight from virtual outcrop modeling	319
Fazio E.* & Cirrincione R. - Improving geological understanding through the integration of UAV aerial survey and LiDAR scanning: advantages and limitations of a multiscale hybrid approach	320
Foletti M.G.*, Menegoni N., Poggi E., Maino M. & Benedetti G. - Development of innovative digital methods for assessing the stability of rock masses in the context of railway infrastructure	321

Grita S.*, Casu M., Sedda L., Asadzadeh S., Boccardo P., Melis M.T., Naitza S. & De Giudici G. - Characterization of Sardinian mine residues using Remote Sensing	322
Guerriero V.*, Sciortino A., Marini R., Mazzanti P. & Tallini M. - InSAR pattern recognition and data analysis in characterizing high-risk seismic areas: a case study from L'Aquila city, Italy	323
Lippolis E.*, Spalluto L. & Tropeano M. - A 3D model to enhance, study and make an inaccessible quarry "virtually accessible": the example of Cava Porcili (Minervino, southern Italy)	324
Marino L.*, Cecere G., Di Maio R., Di Martire D., Devoti R., Calcaterra D. & Vicari A. - Fiastra DSGSD spatio-temporal evolution analysis by means of GPS and DinSAR data	325
Marsico A.*, Colacicco R., La Salandra M. & Capolongo D. - Monitoring badland features and dynamics through LiDAR and UAV technology	326
Minervino Amodio A.*, Gioia D., Corrado G., Abate N., Masini N., Lasaponara R. & Schiattarella M. - Monitoring and quantifying soil erosion rates using LiDAR data and soil erosion models in a Post-Fire area: the Pisticci (Italy) case study	327
Occhipinti M.*, Carboni F., Amorini S., López-Martinez C., Paltriccina N. & Porreca M. - SNAP2DQuake: an implemented and automatic tool of ESA SNAP's Python module for DInSAR technique on ground deformation estimation from Sentinel-1 data	328
Ortolano G.*, Fazio E., Visalli R., D'Agostino A., Menta S., Portale S. & Cirrincione R. - Multiscale geological structural analysis of the late-Eocene to Early-Miocene mylonites from the southern Calabrian Peloritani Orogen (Aspromonte Massif-Southern Italy): new insights for the western Mediterranean geodynamics	329
Ortolano G.*, Fazio E., Visalli R., D'Agostino A., Menta S., Portale S. & Cirrincione R. - The overturned nappe-like structure of the Peloritani Mountains Upper Complex in the light of the new multiscale structural investigations (Peloritani Mountains - Sicily): new insights for the western Mediterranean geodynamics	330
Pedone M. & Manzari P.* - Insights on the geological characterization of Solfatara using data from PRISMA mission	331
Roseto R.*, La Salandra M., Dellino P. & Capolongo D. - Integrating probabilistic and hydrodynamic models for enhanced Flood Hazard Assessment and Mapping in the Basento River Basin (southern Italy)	332
Russo D., Fazio E.*, Fiannacca P., Vento S., Portale S. & Cirrincione R. - Digital field mapping of granitoid outcrops: a study case of late Variscan granitoids from Michelino Beach, Capo Vaticano Promontory (southern Calabria)	333
Russo D.*, Fiannacca P., Fazio E., Portale S., Cirrincione R. & Mamtani M.A. - Macro- to micro-scale investigation of the relationships between granitoid magma emplacement and tectonics at Capo Vaticano Promontory (southern Calabria, Italy)	334
Spadaro A.*, Piras M., Grasso N., Lollino P., Parisi A. & Giordan D. - The role of advanced surveying technologies for geomechanical analysis of artificial caves: the case study of Gravina in Puglia (Puglia region, Southern Italy)	335
Tavani S.*, Corradetti A., Rizzo R. & Seers T.D. - Measuring geological surfaces in virtual outcrop models	336
Ursi A.*, Tapete D., Montuori A., Sacco P., Virelli M., Zoffoli S. & Coletta A. - The role of ASI in the development of novel user-driven EO-based products for geo-hazards applications: the "Multi-mission and Multi-frequency SAR" and "I4DP_SCIENCE" Programs	337
Zaragoza Alonzo A.D.*, Zambrano M., Luzi L. & Tondi E. - Leveraging machine learning for ground motion prediction: advancements in seismic hazard assessment	338
Zito C.*, Mangifesta M., Francioni M., Guerriero L., Di Martire D., Calcaterra D., Pasculli A. & Sciarra N. - Cascading landslide risk assessment by means of an integrated approach	339

S10. The role of multidisciplinary approach in the geochemical study of natural systems

Chemeri L.*, Nisi B., Pierozzi A., Cabassi J., Taussi M., Venturi S., Delgado-Huertas A. & Vaselli O. - Assessing the origin of N-bearing species in the surface waters from the Arno River Basin (Tuscany, central Italy): insights from nitrogen and oxygen isotopes in dissolved nitrate and nitrite	341
Chicco J.M.*, Giordano N., Mandrone G. & Comina C. - Geothermal energy as an integration of existing district heating and cooling grids: evaluation of the thermal performance of the system and of thermal disturbance on the ground from a real case study in NW Italy	342

Dallara E.*, Chelle-Michou C., Fulignati P., Gioncada A., Tavazzani L., Tattitch B. & Lelli M. - Fluid evolution in the deep reservoir of the Larderello geothermal system: insights from microthermometry and LA-ICP-MS analyses of quartz-hosted fluid inclusions	343
Franchini S.*, De Filippi F.M., Ferranti F., Barbieri M. & Sappa G. - Comparison of the isotope based early warning model application to two different municipal solid wastes landfills in Central Italy	344
Funari V.*, Toller S., Nestola Y., Riminucci F., Iorio M., Mercadante A., Angelino A., Ape F., Greggio N., Dinelli E., Varola G., Graziano L., Coppola D., Vitale L., Tedesco P., de Pascale D. & Mantovani L. - Geochemical characterization and biotechnology potential of marine sediments from a small maritime area around Elba-Argentario Basin (Tyrrhenian Sea, Italy)	345
Hernández De la Cruz A., Benet D., Carrazana di Lucia A., Novembre D. & Gimeno D.* - S behavior, sulfate and SO ₂ emissions during a basaltic eruption in Central America: the case-study of the December 29 th , 2013 eruption of the San Miguel volcano, El Salvador	346
Inguaggiato S.*, Vita F., Inguaggiato C., Mazot A., Schiavo B. & Cangemi M. - Decadal geochemical monitoring of CO ₂ and SO ₂ outgassing activity of Vulcano Island, Aeolian Archipelago, Italy	347
Mammoliti E.*, Fronzi D., Ruggeri P., Magi Galluzzi L. & Tazioli A. - Unravel the groundwater dynamics in a landfill with water isotopes: the peculiar case of Corinaldo Municipality landfill	348
Natali S.*, Doveri M., Franceschi L., Gianneccchini R., Menichini M., Nigro M., Delgado-Huertas A., D'Orazio M. & Zanchetta G. - Isotope composition of dissolved sulfates reveals solutes origin and groundwater flows: insights from aquifer systems in Tuscany	349
Schito A.*, Muirhead D., Bowden S. & Parnell J. - Hydrothermal hydrocarbons generation and migration into the basement rocks of Southern Tuscany	350
Scolamacchia T.* - Variations in elemental sulfur viscosity and volcanic hazard assessment implications	351
Tardani D.*, Álvarez-Amado F., Poblete-González C., Godfrey L. & Matte-Estrada D. - Decoding the processes that lead to the extraordinary enrichment of lithium in the Salar de Atacama (northern Chile): new insights from Li, B and Sr isotopes in surface and groundwater	352
Tardani D.*, Álvarez-Amado F., Taucare M., Sánchez J., Taussi M. & Daniele L. - The effect of anthropogenic pressure on the coastal groundwater resources: the case of Toro Bayo aquifer, Southern Chile	353
Taussi M.*, Vespasiano G., Tardani D., Chemeri L., Nisi B., Vaselli O., Gozzi C., Delgado-Huertas A., Agostini S., Apollaro C. & Renzulli A. - Synergic application of stable isotopes (N-O, B, C) to recognize nitrates sources and processes in the shallow phreatic aquifer of the Metauro River Basin (Central Italy)	354

S11. BACK TO THE FUTURE. History of geological studies and mapping as a key for sustainable development

Argentieri A., Centamore E., Petti F.M.* & Tavarnelli E. - Two forerunners of Northern Apennines tectonics: a tribute to Roberto Signorini and Carlo Ippolito Migliorini	356
Argentieri A., Occhigrossi B.C. & Rotella G.* - Tommaso Tittoni, a geologist to the Prime Ministership	357
Barale L., Console F., Mosca P.* & Pantaloni M. - The problem of the age of “greenstones” in the Western Alps: the perspective of Carlo Bruno (1831-1916)	358
Bilotta A.M., Canali M.G., De Caterini G., Fiorelli C., Lucarini M.*, Milighetti C., Nappo E. & Mattei A. - Children’s Eco-Museum (I.C. Via Santo Savarino, Rome): history and memory of the Genius loci of the “Agro romano”	359
Capozzoli A.*, Paoletti V., Porfido S. & Nappi R. - Historical data revision of the 1688 Sannio-Matese earthquake: dataset of environmental effects for constraining the seismogenic source	360
Cofano A.* & De Ceglie R. - The “Signora” of limnology. Rina Monti: geological experience, ecosystem protection and the impact of human activity	361
De Caterini G.*, Ferranti N., Finocchiaro G., Fumanti F., Giarda M., Guerrieri L., Leoni G., Mestriner T., Roggero F., Savoca D., Spizzichino D. & Tria N.G. - Microhistory of the civilization of mines: from the golden fleece to the critical raw material act	362
De Caterini G., Leoni G.*, Andrisani M.G., Carta R., De Benedetti A.A., De Corso S., Ferrigno F., Fumanti F., Guerra M., Guerrieri L., Lucarini M., Naitza S., Olivetta L., Pantaloni M., Patanè R.A., Serra M., Spizzichino D. & Amanti M. - The relevance of the 1973 mining map of Italy: its revamping in the GeoSciencesIR project	363

De Ceglie R.* & Petrocelli C. - On the burning earth: the fascination of Vesuvius and the origins of modern geology	364
Fabbi S.*, Cestari R. & Dominici S. - The De Filippi expedition (1913-1914) and the geological exploration of the Aksai Chin (western Tibet)	365
Garzarella A.* - Military geology and historical archives: from De Ambrosis' monographs to Bulow-Krantz-Sonne's Wehrgeologie, the role of geology in the Second World War	366
Innamorati G.*, Fabbi S., Romano M. & Argentieri A. - One against all: fifty years after the geological scheme of Calabria by Leo Ogniben (1973)	367
Macini P.* & Pantaloni M. - Geosciences and engineering of Lungro rock salt: unveiling Italy's longest-lived underground mining site in Calabria	368
Macini P.*, Mesini E. & Argentieri A. - Reflection vs. refraction seismic: Tiziano Rocco and the development of applied geophysics in Italy	369
Macini P., Pantaloni M.* & Console F. - Antonio Stoppani: a pioneer of petroleum geology and his activity in the Italian oil production industry	370
Musumeci D.* & Furlani S. - The conquest of the submerged landscape: a neglected history	371
Musumeci D.*, Branca S., Ingaliso L., Baumann B., Briole P., Cirrincione R., Corsaro R.A., Monaco C., Napolitani M. & Privitera F. - The <i>Der Aetna</i> and the studies on Etna by Sartorius von Waltershausen (1809-1876)	372
Palladino G.*, Prosser G., Grimaldi S., Olita F., Cascini L. & Dello Iacovo B. - The geological map of the western side of the high Agri Valley	373
Romano M.* & Chiocci F.L. - The woman who painted the ocean floor: celebrating Marie Tharp's legacy ...	374
Romano M.* & Carnevale G. - Early interpretations of the Eocene Bolca Fossil-Lagerstätte (Italy): three centuries of debates for the emerging Earth Sciences	375
Romano M. & Petti F.M.* - The legendary Central Asiatic Expedition: celebrating 100 years of Oviraptor ...	376
Rosati A.*, Sabato L. & Tropeano M. - Staring into the abyss: the unfathomable true age of the Earth or how to reshape the way we perceive Time	377
Sabato L.* - Maria Matilda Ogilvie Gordon: the "Lady of Dolomite", a pioneer of geological surveying and more... ..	378
Saltarelli C.* - Seismic maps between historical approach and scientific research. A contribution from the history of science to risk reduction	379
Sammuri P.* - The ancient mine of Poggio Mozzeto in the Bai Valley (Roccastrada, Grosseto)	380
S12. Field and digital geological mapping: the numerous facets of CARG project from crystalline basement to sedimentary deposits	
Amato V.*, Aucelli P.P.C., Auciello E., Cesarano M., Pappone G., Petrosino P. & Roskopf C.M. - Timing and lithofacies of the intermountain basins quaternary infilling from 1:50.000 geological maps (Piedimonte Matese, Isernia and Castel di Sangro sheets)	382
Amodio S.*, Barattolo F., Bravi S., Cesarano M., Angiolilli D., Auciello E., Boscaino M., Girardi G., Randisi A. & Pappone G. - The Jurassic-Miocene Apenninic limestones in southern Matese: biostratigraphy and sedimentary evolution from geological mapping of the Sheet 418 Piedimonte Matese	383
Antonelli M.*, Caldara M.A., Sacco E. & Spalluto L. - Geological map of the Mesozoic and Cenozoic carbonate units cropping out in the southern Gargano Promontory: new stratigraphic constraints for the tectonic evolution of the area	384
Balsamo L.*, Sulli A., Agate M., Budillon F., Gasperini L., Monaco C. & Carbone S. - Offshore geological map in south-eastern Sicily: the "Siracusa - 646" (CARG project)	385
Bruno L.*, Cicala M., Festa E., Marroccoli M., Parisi A., Sabato L., Tropeano M. & Vescogni A. - Surface and subsurface geology of Gravina in Puglia, Southern Italy	386
Capotorti F.* & Tomassetti L. - Paleotectonics imprint on the southern edge of the M. Morrone structure (Central Apennines)	387
Cerone D.*, Notaro A., Parente M. & Prosser G. - New geological map at a 1:10.000 scale and tectono-stratigraphic review of the NW Campania-Basilicata boundary (Southern Apennines, Southern Italy)	388

Cesarano M.*, Amodio S., Barattolo F., Bravi S., Angiolilli D., Auciello E., Bollati A., Boscaino M., Randisi A., Girardi G., De Matteis M., Grella M., Rosskopf C.M., Silvestri S., Cipriani A., Tomassetti L. & Pappone G. - Stratigraphic and structural relationships between the Matese Mts and the Montagnola di Frosolone: new field data from the Geological Sheets 404 “Isernia” and 418 “Piedimonte Matese” (CARG Project)	389
Cilumbriello A.*, Sabato L. & Tropeano M. - The highest regressive coastal deposits of the Bradanic Trough (Basilicata, Southern Italy): old vs new stratigraphic schemes in the official geological cartography ..	390
Cipriani A. *, Fagioli G., Capotorti F., Consorti L., Fabbì S., Muraro C., Pampaloni L., Prinzi E.P. & Tomassetti L. - Towards a lithostratigraphic correlation of Mesozoic-Cenozoic carbonate platform-to-basin successions of central and southern Apennines: insights from the CARG Project	391
Colzada G.*, Arrigoni F., Marinoni A., Pigazzi E., Tantardini D., Apuani T. & Tartarotti P. - Recognition of a pre-LGM, km-wide collapsed DGSD in Bregaglia Valley (Italian Central Alps): a case study in the frame of the CARG Project sheet n. 038 “Chiavenna”	392
D’Abbicco V.*, De Giosa F., de Luca A., Fracchiolla T., Lisco S., Mastronuzzi G. & Moretti M. - Sedimentary dynamics and biological-anthropic processes on the seafloor: the natural laboratory of Taranto seas (northern Ionian Sea, southern Italy)	393
Fagioli G.*, Artegiani F., Pietrosante A., Parente M. & Putignano M.L. - The Mesozoic stratigraphic succession of Mt. Massico ridge in the southern Apennines (northern Campania, Italy): new data from geological mapping (Sheet 429 Mondragone - CARG Project)	394
Foti A. *, Cianflone G. & Dominici R. - New geological evidence in the Miocene successions of the eastern part of the Catanzaro Strait (Calabria-Southern Italy)	395
Frezza V.*, Garzarella A., Notaro A., Pampaloni M.L., Berti D., Chiarini E., Marino M., Romagnoli G. & Silvestri S. - Biostratigraphic data in the Pliocene-Pleistocene sediments from the CARG Project surveys in the Central Apennines (Italy): new evidence from the Sheet n. 370 “Guardiagrele”	396
Gambino S., Barreca G., Tarascio S., Carbone S. & Monaco C.* - Quaternary faulting in the NE sector of the Hyblean Plateau (SE Sicily): new insight from survey within the CARG project (sheet N. 646 Siracusa)	397
Gennuso M.*, Rizzo G.F., Bonfardeci A., Avellone G., Todaro S. & Gasparo Morticelli M. - Tectono-sedimentary evolution of a Meso-Cenozoic slope from south-western Sicily (Italy)	398
Innamorati G.*, Fabbì S., Notaro A., Tentori D., Tancredi S. & Santantonio M. - New constraints on the southernmost portion of the Ligurian and Sub-Ligurian Domains: insight from the Sheet “363” Civitavecchia	399
Lombardi S. *, Stori L., Federico L., Crispini L., Seno S. & Maino M. - Pre to syn orogenic evolution of the European margin: clues from the Flysch units of the Ligurian Alps (CARG Project - Ormea sheet 244)	400
Maino M. *, Perozzo M., Seno S., Niccolò M., Morelli D., Crispini L., Locatelli M., Corradi N., Federico L. & Notti D. - A geological dive from the western Alps into the Ligurian Sea: the experience of the CARG 245 - Albenga sheet	401
Marcelli I. *, Piana F., Barbero E., Ossella L., Fioraso G., Irace A., Mosca P., Barale L., Frasca G., Catanzariti R., d’Atri A., Bertok C. & Festa A. - CARG geo-tech revolution: digitizing geological maps with innovative tools (practical examples from the CARG project)	402
Marinoni A. *, Pezzotta A., Tantardini D., Arrigoni F., Pigazzi E., Colzada G., Apuani T., Zerboni A. & Tartarotti P. - Multi-scale landscape evolution of Central Alps: another side of the Valchiavenna CARG project	403
Morelli F. *, Chiarini E., Nirta G., Nocentini M., Piacentini T. & Pizzi A. - Rock avalanche deposits along normal-fault and thrust-fault-related tectonic slopes: new insights from CARG Project surveys in the Majella-Porrara ridges (central-eastern Apennines, Abruzzo Region)	404
Orefice S. *, Pensa A. & Fiorentino A. - Geological mapping of submerged areas withing the CARG project. The example of “Asinara” sheet (n. 425)	405
Parrino N. *, Srivastava E., Caldarerì F., Burrato P., Gasparo Morticelli M., Di Maggio C., Agate M., Bonfardeci A. & Sulli A. - Tectonic imprints on Quaternary landscapes: insights from morphometric analysis and new luminescence dating in Southwestern Sicily	406
Pasqualone L. * & Urbani M. - Digital structural analysis from outcrops and VOMs: case studies from Umbria turbiditic successions	407

Perozzo M.*, Maino M., Menegoni N., Crispini L., Federico L. & Seno S. - Fracture network analysis in a polyphasic tectonic framework: the importance to integrate field-based structural data in the era of digital geology (CARG Project 245-Albenga)	408
Pieruccioni D.* & Simonetti M. - The medium- to high-grade metamorphic basements of NW Sardinia: the example of the Sheet n. 425 “Isola Asinara”	409
Relvini A., Ascione A., De Luzio E., Artegiani F., Cascini L., Muraro C., Parente M., Ogata K., Di Donato V. & Iannace A.* - Inheritance of pre-orogenic faults in Miocene foredeep evolution in Southern Apennines, Italy	410
Riva A.*, Caggiati M., Preto N., Fioraso M. & Crocitto L. - Rosso Ammonitico Veronese (Bajocian - Tithonian, Jurassic) from the Trento Platform to the Belluno Basin: can we really map it?	411
Rizzo G.F.*, Maiorana M., Avellone G., Gennuso M., Bonfardeci A. & Gasparo Morticelli M. - 3D reconstruction of an integrated onshore/offshore geological model: the example of geological sheet 628 Sciacca (Southwestern Sicily)	412
Romagnoli G.* & Muraro C. - Field preliminary data to reconstruct the tectono-stratigraphic evolution of the Mt. di Muccia-Mt. Val di Fibbia area (Northern Apennines, Italy)	413
Rossi G.*, Cipriani A. & Fabbi S. - Jurassic evolution and paleogeography of the Fiastrone gorge (Marche, Italy): new data from detailed geological mapping	414
Silvani F.*, Mirabella F., Pazzaglia F.J. & Barchi M.R. - A previously unknown loess deposit in the Quaternary Gubbio basin (Umbria, central Italy): a stratigraphical record of the paleoenvironment of the area	415
Srivastava E.*, Parrino N., Caldareri F., Gasparo Morticelli M., Burrato P., Pucci S., Agate M. & Sulli A. - Late Pleistocene eustatic variations and fluvial terrace development in the Carboj River catchment, Southern Sicily	416
Sulli A.*, Agate M., Gasparo Morticelli M., Todaro S., Lo Presti V., Avellone G., Bonfardeci A., Maiorana M., Rizzo G.F., Gennuso M., Petrella F., Parrino N. & Muraro C. - From onshore to offshore, from outcrop to subsurface: an innovative multi-scale approach to the geological mapping of the Sheet 628 Sciacca (southwestern Sicily)	417
Venezia V.*, Festa V. & Tropeano M. - The small-scale problem: loss of significant geological features in small scale geological maps. The case of the northern sector of the Murgia Materana, South Italy	418
Zanellato N.*, Dela Pierre F. & Festa A. - Sheet 158 “Casale Monferrato” of the Geological Map of Italy at 1:50.000 scale (CARG Project): preliminary results	419
S13. Geomorphology in the Anthropocene: from human-landscape interaction to geoheritage and geohazard management issues	
Annibali Corona M.*, Guerriero L. & Calcaterra D. - Geomorphological evolution and activity of some large earthflows in southern Italy	421
Azzoni R.S.*, Forti L., Pezzotta A. & Zerboni A. - The Derna dam collapse erased a century of urban sprawl	422
Borzi A.M.*, Minio V., De Plaen R., Lecocq T., Cannavò F., Ciraolo G., D’Amico S., Lo Re C., Monaco C., Picone M., Scardino G., Scicchitano G. & Cannata A. - Distinguishing between Medicanes and common seasonal storms using microseism	423
Brandolini P.*, Faccini F., Ferrando A., Bollati I., Pelfini M. & Azzoni R.S. - Geoheritage along the high rocky coast of Eastern Liguria: an emblematic case of interaction between natural hazard and human impact	424
Brenna A.*, Poletto G. & Surian N. - Evaluating the effectiveness of “River Morphodynamic Corridors” for flood hazard mapping: insights from an application in the Cordevole River catchment (Italy)	425
Contillo L.*, Dimola G., Giannandrea P. & Schiattarella M. - How the interplay among geological and geomorphological factors, land use, and changing climate can bias very short-term landscape evolution: an example from Basilicata, southern Italy	426
Ferrando A.*, Facciolo M., Mandarino A., Faccini F. & Brandolini P. - Ancient slate quarries as geosites: degradation risk and enhancement issues	427
Forti L.*, Degli Esposti M., Cremaschi M., Borgi F., Azzoni R.S. & Zerboni A. - Geomorphological reconstruction of the Umm al-Quwain (UAE) coastal-lagoon system and effects of the present-day human impact	428

Gioia D., Bloise L., Casella V., Corrado G., Minervino Amodio A.*, Muto F., Sfacteria M., Capozzoli L., De Martino G., Romano G. & Mollo F. - Relationships between fluvio-lacustrine landscape, human occupation and historical earthquakes: a multidisciplinary study of the Santa Gada archaeological site (Pollino Geopark, southern Italy)	429
Lämmle L., Moreira V.B., D’Aniello M.*, Ilacqua S., Brandolini P., Perez Filho A. & Donadio C. - Coastal erosion in urban areas and socio-environmental challenges: the case of São João da Barra, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	430
Natale J., Ilacqua S., D’Aniello M., Terlizzi F., Lämmle L., Borges Moreira V., Conversano F., Brandolini P., Randazzo G., Perez Filho A., Stanislao C. & Donadio C.* - Urban geomorphology and geostructural aspects of Pozzuoli, southern Italy	431
Pelfini M., Bollati I., Brandolini P., Faccini F. & Azzoni R.S.* - Hiking trails for discovering the geomorphological heritage: fruition and related hazard, risk and impact scenarios	432
Pietrogrande S.*, Brandolini P., Bollati I.M., Pelfini M., Faccini F., Ferrando A., Forti L. & Azzoni R.S. - GEOTRes - Geohazard threats and resilience: mapping the impact of geomorphological and anthropic processes in sensitive morphoclimatic environments	433
Pittau S.*, Rinaldi M., Simonelli T. & Scorpio V. - Historical and remote sensing analysis as an instrument for the delineation of erodible corridor area in the Serio River: a case study aimed to its sustainable and integrated management	434
Turconi L., Coratza P., Faccini F.*, Ferrando A., Luino F., Palmieri W., Soldati M. & Gizzi F. - The contribution of toponyms to geomorphological hazard: hillslope processes and landslides highlighted by the Italian Military Geographical Institute maps at 1:25.000 scale	435
Turconi L., Luino F. & Faccini F.* - Geotoponyms as indicators of hydrogeomorphological features in the Portofino Promontory	436
S14. Interoperable and multiscale geological data-analysis for landscape evolution monitoring by applying innovative remote sensing technologies	
Argentiero I.*, Bovenga F., Borrelli R., Massimi V., Nutricato R. & Nitti D.O. - Analysis tools for supporting the exploitation of MTInSAR products in monitoring landscape evolution	438
Balsamo L.*, Calderari F., Parrino N., Maltese A. & Sulli A. - The isoradiometric shoreline extraction method as a proxy for Medicean impact quantification: a case study of Bals event along the Sciacca coast (southern Sicily)	439
Bozzolan E., Cecchetto M., Doolaege D., Taffetani E., Brenna A., Surian N. & Bizzi S.* - Systematic monitoring of river landform evolution across scales: from localized change detection to catchment connectivity	440
Calderari F.*, Parrino N., Balsamo L., Dardanelli G., Todaro S., Maltese A. & Sulli A. - A newly developed Shoreline Extraction tool from satellite imagery: case studies in Sicily (Central Mediterranean region)	441
Clementucci R.*, Uchusov E., Willett S. & Wang Y. - External forcing on drainage divide evolution in rifted margins: case of Madagascar	442
De Bellis M.*, Capolongo D., Marsico A. & Scicchitano G. - Application of morphometric indexes aimed to the monitoring of surface processes within the hydrographic basin of the Ofanto river	443
Di Pietro G.*, D’Agostino A., Ortolano G., Fazio E., Visalli R., Musumeci R.E. & Cirrincione R. - Web publication of multiscale geological data, methodology and processes	444
Kushabaha A.*, Scicchitano G., Refice A., Marsico A., Tapete D., Ursi A., Capolongo D. & Zingaro M. - Integrating multispectral normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) to analyze land cover changes in sediment connectivity analysis	445
La Gioia A.*, Scicchitano G. & Nuzzo D. - Experimental application of the Sediment Flow Connectivity Index (SfCI) in surface archaeological inter-site survey	446
Malusà M.G.*, Resentini A. & Wittmann H. - A two-stage river capture event in Corsica and its impact on erosion rates and offshore sedimentation revealed by geological and in situ ¹⁰ Be cosmogenic data	447
Pezzotta A.*, Marinoni A., Al Kindi M., Zucali M. & Zerboni A. - How long does the signature of tectonic events last in the landscape? Topographical analysis of Jebel Akhdar dome and surrounding Semail Ophiolite in the Al-Hajar Mountains (northern Sultanate of Oman)	448

Piana F.*, Mantovani A. & Lombardo V. - Geological Data and the concept of Quality. Theory and application	449
Pirulli G., Mancino S.*, Sabato G., Parise M., Scardino G. & Scicchitano G. - Landslide body segmentation from satellite imagery using artificial intelligence model: case studies Ischia island and Forlì - Cesena area	450
Remi M.*, La Salandra M., Zingaro M., Mancino S., Palombella M., Mastronuzzi G. & Capolongo D. - Full-coverage geomorphological mapping using opensource software: a tool for geomorphological risk analysis, management, and mitigation	451
Ruscitto V.*, Delchiaro M., Della Seta M., Gribenski N., Richard M., Iacobucci G., Piacentini D., Zocchi M. & Troiani F. - Fluvial record interpretation for the extraction of climatic and tectonic signals in the Adriatic Piedmont Zone of the Apennines (central Italy, Marche region)	452
Salerno A.*, Commis L. & Catalano S. - Rock outcrops classification by Sentinel-2 images: a new gis-based toolbox proposal	453
Sblano A.*, Mancino S., Lovergine F.P., Massimi V., Capolongo D. & Amatulli D. - Unified Global Landslide Catalog - A single global-scale standardized landslide dataset	454
Silvani F.*, Melelli L., Mirabella F., Cardinali M., Bucci F., Santangelo M., Pazzaglia F.J. & Barchi M.R. - Geomorphic signature of the eastward marching of Quaternary extensional tectonics in the Northern Apennines (central Italy): the Colfiorito intermontane basins key area	455
Vance G.*, Clementucci R., Picotti V. & Willett S.D. - Catchment-averaged denudation rates in the Northern Apennines and Ligurian Alps and implications for landscape dynamics	456
Vanzani F.*, Carbonneau P. & Fontana A. - Deep learning to automatically map braided palaeochannels from optical traces in the Venetian - Friulian Plain (NE Italy)	457
Yaaqoub A.*, Essaifi A., Clementucci R., Ballato P., Zayane R., Faccenna C. & Pagli C. - Incision rates into Quaternary lava flows of the Middle Atlas and Western Mesta (Morocco): implications for landscape evolution	458
Zahabnazouri S.*, Capolongo D., Wigand P., Shahbazid S. & Dimotta A. - Soil erosion assessment using the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) in Google Earth Engine in Bradano Basin	459
S15. Analysis and management of coastal areas, from risk assessment to perspectives arising from new technologies	
Anzidei M.*, Trippanera D., Bosman A., Brunori C.A., Alberti T., Vecchio A., Bignami C., Serpelloni E., Tolomei C., Aucelli P.P.C. & Mastronuzzi G. - Vertical land movements and relative sea level rise scenarios up to 2150 along the Italian coasts: implications for multi-risk assessments	461
Bertoni D.*, Diana E., Luppichini M., Trembanis A. & Sarti G. - Spheres vs. disks: real-time movement of pebbles in the swash-zone of coarse-clastic beaches	462
Borzi L.*, Marino M., Stagnitti M., Sciandrello S., Cavallaro L., Di Stefano A., Foti E. & Musumeci R.E. - Coastal land use transformation as a key driving factor for coastal erosion, the case study of Southern Sicily (Italy)	463
Bosman A., Trippanera D.*, Anzidei M., Greco M., Vecchio A., Muccini F., Alberti T., Serpelloni E., Doumaz F., Charalampos G. & Raso E. - Relative sea level rise and storm surge scenarios along the coasts of Cinque Terre National Park (Liguria, Italy)	464
Caldareri F.*, Balsamo L., Parrino N., Maltese A. & Sulli A. - A new isoradiometric remotely-sensed shoreline extraction method: a time series case study in southern Sicily (Central Mediterranean region)	465
Faccini F.*, Allasia P., Godone D. & Notti D. - Analysis of the sea cliff collapse and the subsequent fall of the Camogli cemetery on February 22 th , 2021 (Liguria, Italy)	466
Faccini F.*, Ferrando A., Picchio F. & Scannapieco A. - Analysis of coastal retreat and slope movements on rocky coastal cliff between Sori and Pieve Ligure (Eastern Liguria, Italy)	467
Fasciglione G.*, Benassai G., Mattei G., Mucerino L., Pappone G. & Aucelli P.P.C. - Erosive effects of sea-storms, human pressure, and sea level rise on Volturno coastal plain (mid-Tyrrhenian area): present to future coastal hazard	468
Fontolan G., Bertoni D.*, Bezzi A., Casagrande G., Conforti A., De Falco G., Deiana G., Orrù P.E. & Simeone S. - Beach-dune systems in a transgressive domain along the Sardinian coasts	469

Imam C.*, Chaibi M., Ayt Ougougdal M. & Charif A. - Analyzing coastal cliff stability and recession rates along the Safi Atlantic Coast, Morocco	470
Kushabaha A.*, Scardino G., Sabato G. & Scicchitano G. - Mediterranean Sea surface response during the cyclone events: impacts on physical and biogeochemical parameters	471
Mattei G.* & Aucelli P.P.C. - Ongoing vs. Holocene morphodynamic effects of sea-level changes: a new perspective for the assessment of coastal resilience to climate changes	472
Mellone G.*, Scarrica V., Mattei G., Staiano A., Ciaramella A. & Aucelli P.P.C. - New approaches for coastal zone monitoring aimed at litter detection in emerged and submerged environments	473
Musumeci R.E., Di Pietro G.* & Ortolano G. - Methodology for the assessment of coastal morphodynamics due to storm surges in the Mediterranean area using machine learning and remote sensing data	474
Sabato G.*, Scardino G., Kushabaha A., Casagrande G., Chirivì M., Fontolan G., Fracaros S., Luparelli A., Spadotto S. & Scicchitano G. - Using deep learning system-based for tide and surge measurement	475
Sorrentino A.*, Fasciglione G., Mattei G., Pappone G. & Aucelli P.P.C. - On the resilience to climate change of sites of community importance (SCI): the case of Cala del Cefalo (Southern Italy)	476
Spadotto S.*, Fracaros S., Bezzi A., Casagrande G., Popesso C. & Fontolan G. - Coastal flooding risk scenario for the city of Grado, northern Adriatic Sea	477
Tripanera D.*, Anzidei M., Bosman A., Vecchio A., Alberti T. & Doumaz F. - Relative Sea Level Rise projections and flooding scenario for 2150 A.D. for the Panarea Island and Islets (Aeolian Islands, Italy) by Ultra High-Resolution terrestrial and marine Digital Elevation Models	478
Tursi M.F.*, Matano F., Fortelli A., Sacchi M. & Aucelli P.P.C. - Coastal hazard in tuffaceous high coast in the Gulf of Naples (South Italy)	479
Vitale A.*, Sansò P. & Giaccari E. - The drowned physical landscape of Porto Cesareo coastal area (southern Apulia, Italy)	480

S16. Geomaterials for a Sustainable Development

Animali L.*, Corrado S., Bartoli M., Mitillo N., Tuccimei P. & Giorcelli M. - Characterization and use of biochar, a sustainable material, for water purification and carbon storage	482
Arizzi A.* & Cultrone G. - The use of raw materials and residues for the manufacturing of sustainable lime mortars	483
Bertino A.*, Caggiani M.C., Fugazzotto M., Portale S., Starinieri S., Mazzoleni P. & Barone G. - Application of pigmented geopolymers in Cultural Heritage conservation and aging studies on a geopolymer mock-up	484
Brodu G.*, Murgia S., Norio N., Arca M., Aragoni M.C. & Columbu S. - Role of the application method in the calcium phosphonate consolidation of pyroclastic rocks used in the environmental heritage	485
Clausi M.*, Girardi G., Savino S., Manica M., Attrotto R., D'Accolti L. & Pinto D. - Metakaolin - Blast furnace slag geopolymers as catalyst support for water treatment	486
Cofano V.*, Clausi M., Pannu D.S., Mathew J., Barkhordari D., Khorshidi Nazloo E., Santoro D. & Pinto D. - The use of olive oil-modified geopolymers for municipal wastewater treatment	487
Comboni D., Lotti P.*, Gatta G.D., Battiston T. & Pagliaro F. - Hydrated borates at non ambient conditions: pivotal experiments in the production of neutron-shielding concretes	488
Comboni D.*, Lotti P., Gatta G.D., Battiston T. & Pagliaro F. - Inderborite: a comprehensive reinvestigation of its technological features	489
Corti M.*, D'Alessio D., Campione M., Yivlialin R., Bussetti G., Lucotti A., Tommasini M. & Malaspina N. - Incipient carbonate phases formation on brucite [Mg(OH) ₂] single crystals surfaces during microwave-driven carbonation	490
Coticelli S.*, Abad I., Balassone G., Cappelletti P., Rispoli C., Granitzio F., Farenzena M. & Mondillo N. - Geology and mineralogy of the Sa Pigada Bianca bentonite deposit (Sardinia, Italy): preliminary data	491
D'Alessio D.*, Corti M., Campione M., Giuntoli F., Ceccato A. & Malaspina N. - From field to laboratory: geo-inspired strategies for the enhancement of the water-mediated mineral carbonation for the reduction of its energy and environmental impacts	492

d'Aniello F., Arizzi A., Cappelletti P., Cultrone G., Di Benedetto C., Izzo F., Langella A., Rispoli C. & De Bonis A.* - Optimizing traditional materials: a systematic approach to formulate restoration mortars for improved substrate compatibility	493
Di Chiara G.*, Farina I., Fraternali F. & Petrillo A. - New materials for civil engineering through solidification and stabilization processes	494
Dore E. *, Biddau R., Fancello D., Frau F., Medas D., Musu E. & Podda F. - Investigations on simultaneous Sb and As removal from mining drainages by Layered Double Hydroxides (LDHs)	495
Fastelli M.*, Vivani R., Sassi P., Speranzini E., Schoubben A., Di Michele A., Zucchini A., Mortaro F. & Comodi P. - Effect of nano Mg-Al layered double hydroxides (LDHs) on chemical and physical properties of cement paste: preliminary results	496
Finocchiaro C.*, Occhipinti R., Barone G., Mazzoleni P., Andreola F., Romagnoli M. & Leonelli C. - Optimization with slaked lime of alkali-activated pastes based on Mt. Etna's volcanic ash: rheological and physical-mechanical assessment	497
Fugazzotto M.*, Barone G. & Mazzoleni P. - "Cradle-to-cradle": waste geopolymers as precursors for new geopolymers in the restoration and construction sectors	498
Gambino F.*, Longhitano N., Tazzini A., Mancini S., Ghignone S. & Dino G. : <i>Tadelakt</i> : a thousand-year-old technique for the production of special plasters with unique properties	499
Gatta G.D., Comboni D.*, Chiappella L., Battiston T. & Lotti P. - The role of temperature on the pressure-mediated adsorption in natural zeolites: the case of leonhardtite	500
Lezzerini M.*, Aquino A. & Pagnotta S. - Investigation on geopolymeric mortar production by using clay bricks waste	501
Mameli P.*, Martucci A., Alberti A., Mancinelli M. & Oggiano G. - First insights on the synthesis of cordierite from Sardinian raw materials	502
Mancinelli M.*, Spagnoli E., di Benedetto F., Cristino V., Montegrossi G., Vola G., Barion L., Martucci A. & Ardit M. - New insights in the optimization of sulfur dioxide flue gas desulfurization (FGD) using porous materials in a semi-dryer system	503
Massa M.*, Vola G., Ardit M., Bresciani P. & Colombari V. - Hydration processes of geomaterials for green and sustainable applications	504
Meloni P., Columbu S.*, Cocco O., Carcangiu G. & Palomba M. - Lime and high zeolitic geomaterials content in mixtures: perspectives in hydraulicized eco-mortars production	505
Occhipinti R.*, Bertino A., Barone G. & Mazzoleni P. - Tripoli Formation rocks as new resources in alkaline-activation technology: a feasibility study	506
Parlapiano F.* - New method to quantify fluorite in geo-complex material: the case of Pianciano mine (Central Italy)	507
Piepoli L.*, Grieco G., Della Porta G., Marinoni N., Govoni D. & Fumagalli L. - Comparative trace element concentrations in carbonate lithologies used for the production of lime and their washing muds	508
Ranellucci F.*, Ulian G., Moro D., Sangiorgi C., Tataranni P. & Valdrè G. - Recovered silt filled geopolymers for low-strength concrete applications in road construction	509
Ulian G.* & Valdrè G. - Multi-methodological analysis of orpiment As ₂ S ₃ and related possible applications in bidimensional optoelectronics	510
Zafarana S.E.*, Achilli A., Barone G., Bersani D., Finocchiaro C., Fornasini L., Mantovani L., Portale S. & Mazzoleni P. - Valorisation of sawing sludge from Cuasso al Monte (Italy) in alkali-activation process: feasibility study	511
Zafarana S.E.*, Scanferla P., Finocchiaro C., Barone G., Mazzoleni P. & Kraxner J. - Alkali-activated materials based on volcanic ash and waste glass: sustainable and alternative geomaterials from waste to resource	512
S17. Advanced minero-chemical characterization and processing of waste for a conscious reuse	
Bernasconi A. *, Beretta M., Curetti N., Tribaudino M., Pavese A., Francescon F. & Sartori R. - Application of mineralogy to waste reuse in ceramic materials	514
Bernasconi A., Mantovani L. & Tribaudino M.* - Bottom ashes from MSWI in ceramics: a higher value reuse of waste	515

Caviglia C.*, Bernasconi D., Destefanis E., Wehrung Q., Brombin V., Mancinelli M., Martucci A., Mantovani L., Bonadiman C. & Pavese A. - The CLEAN project: a sustainable methodology to reduce the environmental impact of MSWI fly ash and to recover strategic metals	516
Curetti N.*, Bernasconi D., Servetto G.P., Vigliaturo R., Tribaudino M. & Pavese A. - Complexity of the system and plethora of crystal phases in fly ashes: a careful investigation of processes and products from cooling of the flue gas in the MSW waste-to-energy incinerators	517
Ercoli R.*, Luconi I., Renzulli A., Paris E., Buczkowska K.E., Łoś P. & Prałat K. - Innovative approaches for treating industrial byproducts: towards inertization and reutilization in advanced technological materials	518
Fornari G.*, El Chami D., Clausi M. & Pinto D. - Multi-methodical approach for a detailed characterization of cogeneration ashes and their valorisation in the fertilizer industry	519
Ghani J.*, Dinelli E., Funari V., Giuliani S. & Bellucci L.G. - Radionuclides assessment in municipal solid waste incineration plants wastes: a comparative case study of pre- and post-pandemic periods	520
Mantovani L.*, Bernasconi A., Tribaudino M., Destefanis E., Caviglia C., Nazzareni S., Fornasini L. & Bersani D. - Temperature treatments of bottom ash from municipal solid waste incinerator: new perspective and existing applications	521
Massa M.*, Calce S., Pachaiappan P. & Bontempi E. - Sewage sludge ashes characterization and microwave thermochemical treatment for fertilizer production	522
Mureddu A.* - Functional recovery of Provincial Road no. 2 and management of waste materials: from waste to by-products. Experiences of the Province of Southern Sardinia in the reuse and cold recycling of geomaterials	523
Ossoli E., Ercoli R.*, Stabile P. & Paris E. - Recycling of surgical masks into green products for the building sector	524
Pandolfi Balbi E.*, Comodi P., Fastelli M., Zucchini A., Cambi C., Corradini A., Mantovani L., Cerni G., Bou Farhat H. & Snellings R.- : Sustainable binders for the stabilisation of subgrade layers of road pavement by recycling of biomass ash, municipal solid waste incineration ash and concrete demolition waste	525
Pandolfi Balbi E., Corradini A.*, Cambi C., Fastelli M., Cerni G., Cotana F., Zucchini A. & Comodi P. - Wood biomass ash: a possible alternative to free lime and cement as stabilizing agent in clayey subgrade of road pavement	526
Radica F., Iezzi G.*, Piccioni R. & Bernardini V. - Petrographic variation of CDW in an industrial plant: a case from Central Italy	527
Radicchi A., Fastelli M., Zucchini A.*, Vivani R., Corradini A., Cerni G. & Comodi P. - Recycling and reusing of construction and demolition waste from Umbria region: a second-generation binder	528
Stabile P.*, Ercoli R., Paris E. & Carroll M.R. - Time-temperature-crystalline behavior of thermally treated MSW bottom ashes	529
Stabile P., Fornasini L.*, Bersani D., Dominijanni S., Di Genova D., Romano C. & Paris E. - A DSC-derived viscosity and Raman spectroscopy study on waste-based glasses in the CAS system	530
Stagno V.*, Mignardi S., Antonacci A., Gasperuzzo G., Carfi Pavia F., Lima S., Scargiali F. & Medeghini L. - BIO-DUST: BIO-circular 3D printable prodUctS for cultural heriTage	531
Valentini L.*, Liu Y., Molinari S., Dalconi M.C. & Artioli G. - Thermodynamic modelling in the management of industrial waste streams	532
Vitale L., Varola G., Graziano L., Coppola D., Galasso G., Tedesco P., Vitale G.A., de Pascale D., Meisel T.C., Ulian G., Moro D., Valdré G., Dinelli E. & Funari V.* - Biotechnological potential of marine extremophiles in the treatment of valuable anthropogenic materials like spent car catalysts	533
Wehrung Q.*, Pastero L., Bernasconi D., Cotellucci A., Bruno M., Destefanis E., Caviglia C. & Pavese A. - A novel in-situ method to continuously monitor the aqueous carbonation degree of high calcium (chloro) (hydr)-oxide content-industrial alkaline waste through gas flow sensors	534
Wehrung Q.*, Pastero L., Bernasconi D., Cotellucci A., Bruno M., Destefanis E., Caviglia C., Cavagna S. & Pavese A. - Carbonation performance of waste incinerator air pollution control residues (APCr) under wastewater reuse conditions - Towards a sustainable stabilization process	535

S18. Geosciences for the characterization, exploration and exploitation of primary and secondary mineral resources

Attardi A.*, Cossu D., Deidda M.L., Fancello D., Sedda L. & Naitza S. - The Mo-LREE-(W) greisen and F-LREE-(Mo) hydrothermal mineralisation in the Oschiri - Alà dei Sardi area (N Sardinia)	537
Chiaradia M.* - Distinct magma evolution processes control the formation, endowments and metal ratios of porphyry Cu-Au deposits in thin and thick arcs	538
Ciccolella A.*, Festa V., Ruggieri G., Schingaro E., Tursi F., Ventruti G. & Fregola R.A. - Trace elements and REYs signature of ore and gangue minerals in the Zn-Pb(-Cu-Fe) mineralization of Longobucco and Fonte Argentila (Sila Massif, Calabria, southern Italy)	539
Corrado F.*, Sorrentino A., Chirico R., Casarotto B., Massironi M. & Mondillo N. - Hyperspectral analysis of vanadium-bearing ore deposits in the Mibladen district (Morocco) and the Otavi Mountainland (Namibia)	540
Coticelli S.*, Abad I., Balassone G., Cappelletti P., Rispoli C., Granitzio F., Farenzena M. & Mondillo N. - Geology and mineralogy of the S'Aliderru bentonite deposit (Sardinia, Italy)	541
De Leo A.*, Pedrosa-Soares A.C., Lana C. & Farina F. - On the origin of spodumene-rich pegmatites in the Araçuaí Pegmatite District, Minas Gerais, Brazil: insights from mica and apatite mineral chemistry ..	542
Di Giuseppe P.*, Agostini S., Rielli A., Vezzoni S. & Dini A. - Iron isotope systematics and ore forming processes: first results from the ophiolite-hosted, Tuscan Cu-Zn VMS deposits	543
Dini A.* - The supergiant epithermal Hg district of Mt. Amiata (Italy): metal source and genesis	544
Filimon D.I.*, Boschi C., Fulignati P., Gioncada A. & Rielli A. - The carbonate-hosted Sb(±Au) mineralization of Southern Tuscany: insights from stibnite and pyrite trace element composition and stable isotope geochemistry	545
Fumanti F.*, De Corso S., De Caterini G., Andrisani M.G., Dacquino C., De Benedetti A.A., Carta R., Ferrigno F., Guerra M., Guerrieri L., Leoni G., Lucarini M., Olivetta L., Pantaloni M., Patanè R.A., Pieruccioni D., Serra M., Spizzichino D. & Amanti M. - National databases, starting point for compliance with the Critical Raw Materials Act obligations	546
Gioiello S., Santoro L.* & Cazzaniga A. - Re-use of granite quarry waste for REEs-recovery along the industrial production chain: results from pre-concentration tests	547
Grieco G.*, Naitza S. & Bussolesi M. - Preliminary evaluation of the antimony potential for different waste materials at abandoned mines of Villasalto and Ballao, Sardinia	548
Morelli G.*, Chmes H., Costagliola P., Dore E., Frau F., Gonnelli C., Lattanzi P., Medas D., Nannoni A., Regini G., Ruggieri G., Trumpy E., Vezzoni S. & Rimondi V. - The antimony resource in Italy: evaluation of environmental impact and ore exploration of a Critical Raw Material under the MOLIERE project ...	549
Naitza S.*, Conte A.M., Petrelli M., Giovanardi T. & Secchi F. - Petrogenetic and metallogenic constraints from dark micas compositions of late-Variscan post-collisional granite suites from southern Sardinia (Italy)	550
Natali F.*, Quaranta S., Agostini M., De Giorgio F., Latini A., Miranda Figueira B.A. & Valdrè G. - An old material for a new application: hydrous manganese dioxide from mining tailings as supercapacitor electrode	551
Natali F.*, Quaranta S., Agostini M., Latini A., Miranda Figueira B.A. & Valdrè G. - "Low cost/low end" birnessite-like MnO ₂ recovered from Amazon mining tailings as conversion anode for Li-batteries ...	552
Piepoli L.*, Della Porta G., Grieco G., Sinojmeri A. & Fociro A. - Multi analytical approach to the study of Albanian phosphorite deposits in Jurassic and Cretaceous marine carbonate successions	553
Santoro L.* & Domenighini G. - Punta Corna five-element vein system (Italy): Late-Alpine hydrothermal circulation and metallogenesis	554
Scano I.*, Moroni M., Frau F. & Naitza S. - Ore variability in five-element (Ni-Co-As-Ag-Bi) vein systems: insights from the As/S vs. S binary plot	555
Sedda L.*, Attardi A., Deidda M.L., De Giudici G., Fancello D., Naitza S. & Scano I. - Critical raw materials (CRMs) in the Fluminèse-Arburèse districts (SW Sardinia): guidelines for regional-scale mineral exploration	556
Sorrentino A.*, Asadzadeh S., Gleeson S., Chabrilat S., Boni M. & Mondillo N. - Alteration mineral mapping of Zn mineralization using EnMAP hyperspectral satellite data: a comparative study of the Skorpion-Rosh Pinah (Namibia) and Beltana (Australia) deposits	557

Tazzini A.*, Gambino F., Mancini S. & Dino G.A. - Circular economy in the dimension stone industry: problems and challenges related to fine fractions generated during marble exploitation	558
Velicogna M., Beltrame M., Barago N., De Min A., Lenaz D., Nimis P.*, Chiaradia M., Venier M., Chelle-Michou C. & Tavazzani L. - Age and evolution of the Raibl carbonate-hosted Zn-Pb deposit (NE Italy)	559
S19. Environmental mineralogy and sustainable development	
Ameur-Zaimeche O., Kechiched R., Mameli P., Mesto E., Mongelli G., Ouladmansour A.* & Schingaro E. - Critical metals distribution in bauxite residues: a multivariate statistical analysis approach	561
Belviso C.*, Mancinelli M., Abdolrahimi M., Sturini M., Cavalcante F., Lettino A. & Peddis D. - Red mud treated with KOH: from disposal material to new resource	562
Bloise A., Fuoco I.*, Vespasiano G., Pacella A., Vilella S., Piersante C., Malvasi G., Campopiano A., Ballirano P., Bruno M.R., Bruni B.M., Sinopoli F., Di Carlo M.C. & Apollaro C. - Evaluating mineralogical and geochemical characteristics for understanding groundwater quality and secondary asbestos exposure risks: the case of Calabria Region	563
Caggiano J., Cisullo C.*, Buccione R., Rizzo G. & Mongelli G. - Mineralogical and petrographic assessment of asbestiform minerals in the Timpone Seluci metabasites (Pollino Massif, Southern Italy)	564
Capitani G.*, Bernasconi A., Bianchi A., Bizjan B., Conconi R., Ferrario S., Ferrini S., Lavagna L., Marian M., Mauri M., Dalpiaz M., Pavese M., Squitieri L., Tarantino S.C., Vergani F. & Viti C. - Recycling detoxified asbestos cement in several commodities	565
Colombo F.*, Fantini R., Di Renzo F., Malvasi G., Malferrari D. & Arletti R. - Advancements in zeolite-based recovery of Rare Earth Elements: a step towards resource security and sustainability	566
D'Alessio D.*, Secchi V., Campione M., Malaspina N. & Monguzzi A. - Synthesis and surface functionalization of geo-inspired nanotubes for Alzheimer's Disease treatment with increased tolerability	567
Di Carlo M.C.*, Ballirano P., Bloise A., Campopiano A., Fantauzzi M., Montereali M.R., Nardi E., Petriglieri J.R., Rossi A., Tomatis M., Turci F. & Pacella A. - Understanding the behaviour of fibrous antigorite in artificial lysosomal fluid: evidence for toxicity assessment	568
Indelicato V.*, Punturo R., Visalli R., Pistorio A., Cirrincione R., Cantaro C. & Pinizzotto M.R. - Approaching knowledge of naturally occurring asbestos in volcanic geological contexts of southern Italy	569
Mancinelli M.*, Adami L., Gigli L., Sousa N.C.O., Pedrotti J.J., Plaisier J., Pasti L., Stevanin C. & Martucci A. - Structural behaviour of graphene and silver functionalized graphene oxide loaded with perfluorinated compounds during thermal heating	570
Mancinelli M.*, Ardit M., Chenet T., Pasti L. & Martucci A. - Thermogravimetric and High-Temperature X-ray Diffraction study on the desorption of humic monomers from Y zeolites	571
Molinari C.*, Conte S., Zanelli C., Ardit M., Mantovani L., Cruciani G., Tribaudino M. & Dondi M. - Mobility of hazardous elements in ceramic bodies	572
Morelli G., Ciani F.*, Costagliola P., Fagotti C., Lattanzi P., Manca R., Monnanni A., Nannoni A. & Rimondi V. - Mercury (Hg) pollution in riparian vegetation along the Paglia River in the Monte Amiata Hg mining district (Italy): implications for a sustainable environmental management and risks	573
Ouladmansour A.*, Mesto E., Lacalamita M., Mongelli G., Mameli P., Cerri G., Capitani G., Conconi R., Agrosi G. & Schingaro E. - Mineralogical and geochemical characterization of red muds from Portovesme (SW Sardinia, Italy)	574
Punturo R.*, Rizzo G., Buccione R., Visalli R., Indelicato V. & Cirrincione R. - Petrography, geochemistry and mineralogy of serpentinite rocks in the ophiolite units at the Calabria and Basilicata regions, Southern Apennine (Italy): state of the art and ongoing research	575
Sisti M.*, Andreola F., Barbieri L., Guidetti D., Gualtieri A.F., Fantini R., Colombo F. & Arletti R. - Sustainable development in traditional ceramic glazes: harnessing MMVF waste for environmental innovation ...	576
S20. High-resolution chemical and textural imaging techniques as analytical tools in Earth Sciences	
Agrosi G.* - From Earth's mantle to Cosmo: case studies by imaging techniques	578
Barni L.*, Marras G., Morana M., Angellotti A., Cinque G., Mikhailenko D.S., Bindi L. & Stagno V. - Heterogeneity of N distribution into diamond single crystal: a closer look into the role of inclusions in the distribution of N aggregation state	579

Bernardini S.*, Della Ventura G., Sodo A. & Jovane L. - Micro-Raman mapping of the oxidation state of Mn in deep-ocean polymetallic deposits	580
Capitani G.* - Transmission electron microscopy in Earth Sciences: conventional and advanced applications	581
Casarin A.*, Radica F., Iezzi G., Galderisi A., Bravo M., de Brito J., Brando G., Nazzari M. & Scarlato P. - 2D image analysis of mortars: amount of cement paste and texture of the aggregates	582
Conconi R.*, Capitani G., Cossio R., Pastero L., Berretti E. & Lavacchi A. - Micro-chemical and micro-structural studies of minerals and clues on the associated geological processes	583
Della Ventura G.*, Bernardini S., Viti C., Agrosi G. & Lucci F. - Imaging techniques as analytical tools in Earth Sciences	584
Elettivo G.S., Tempesta G.*, Bernardini S., Vadrucci M. & Agrosi G. - Color changes in topaz treated via irradiation and heat	585
Moro D.*, Ulian G. & Valdrè G. - SPM of layer silicates and interaction with single biomolecules at the nano-atomic scale	586
Moro D.*, Ulian G. & Valdrè G. - Atomic force, Kelvin probe, electric force microscopy and nanolithography of clinocllore	587
Palazzo Q.*, Raaijmakers S., Belleman R.G., Prada F., Hammel J.U., Kaandorp J.A., Goffredo S., Falini G. & Valdrè G. - Unveiling the acoustic-morphological features of fish otolith structures by multiscale imaging investigations	588
Pronti L.*, Romani M., Balerna A. & Cestelli Guidi M. - Micro and macro mapping and imaging analyses for the identification of mineral pigments on paintings by using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopies	589
Ranellucci F.*, Ulian G., Moro D. & Valdrè G. - Theoretical and experimental study of structural, vibrational, and electronic properties of dolomite	590
Rizzo F.* - Study of color zoning in tourmalines from different localities before and after treatments using chemical analysis and high-resolution images	591
Romani M.*, Pronti L. & Cestelli Guidi M. - SINBAD-IR beamline at DAFNE-Light: application and developments of FT-IR spectroscopy in the field of Earth Sciences	592
Visalli R.*, Ortolano G., D'Agostino A., Fiannacca P., Rebay G. & Cirrincione R. - Unraveling symplectite development during granulite/amphibolite facies retrogression through X-ray quantitative image analyses	593
Vitrano A.*, Viti C., Della Ventura G., Lucci F. & Vetere F. - A preliminary petrological study of refractory inclusions in NWA12800 meteorite	594
Vitrano A.*, Viti C., Della Ventura G., Lucci F. & Vetere F. - A preliminary petrological study of chondrules in NWA12800 meteorite	595
S21. Mineralogy behind Earth processes: insights from the atomic to the macroscopic scale	
Biagioni C., Pasero M.*, Sejkora J. & Števkò M. - "Carbonato-apatite" is not a fake: the first reliable SCXRD proof of the incorporation of [CO ₃] groups within the apatite framework	597
Bindi L.* - The strange case of a mineral with pyroxene chemistry and HP-olivine structure	598
Campomenosi N.* & Mihailova B. - Atomic dynamics of chalcedony under non ambient conditions: a Raman spectroscopy study	599
Chrappan Soldavini B.*, Merlini M., Gemmi M., Fumagalli P., Joseph B., Bais G. & Polentarutti M. - New thermo-elastic and crystal-chemical insights on 11.5 Å phase: a major water carrier to the mantle transition zone	600
Conconi R.*, Fumagalli P. & Capitani G. - Micro- and nano-scale investigation of (Ca-REE) fluorcarbonates: clues for REE partitioning and mobility	601
D'Angeli I.M.*, Rilievo G., Magro M., Molinari S., Favero M., Barbaro A., Brenker F., Singerling S.A., Vianello F. & Salviulo G. - A new synthetic strategy to produce hollandite-type nanocrystals, useful for environmental application	602

Fregola R.A.*, Ciccolella A., Ruggieri G., Ventruti G. & Schingaro E. - Sphalerite from Longobucco and Fonte Argentila mineralization (Sila Massif, Calabria, southern Italy): crystal chemistry and genetic implications	603
Giuli G., Nazzareni S.* & Skogby H. - Dellen crater impact melt rock: pyroxenes as a proxy for melt thermal history and water content	604
Guagliano M.*, Mostoni S., Dotelli G., Finocchio E., Mesto E., Schingaro E., Scotti R., Bellotto M., Cristiani C. & Lacalamita M. - Spectroscopic study of the interaction mechanism of heavy metals and clay and organo-clays as sorbents in wastewater treatment	605
Lepore G.O.*, Bindi L., d'Acapito F., Landi A.I. & Bonazzi P. - Twinning and superstructure in janchevite, $Pb_9VO_{10.25} \square_{0.75} Cl_{2.5}$	606
Mancinelli M., Precisvalle N., Ardit M., Beltrami G., Gigli L., Catizzone E., Migliori M., Giordano G. & Martucci A.* - An in-situ synchrotron X-ray powder diffraction study of the thermal stability of templated ZSM-5 zeolites	607
Mauro D.*, Sejkora J., Biagioni C. & Dolníček Z. - Second world occurrence of badalovite, $Na_2Mg_2Fe(AsO_4)_3$, from the Etna volcanic complex, Sicily	608
Mesto E.*, Lacalamita M., Kaneva E., Shendrik R., Bogdanov A., Merli M. & Schingaro E. - High temperature study of fluorocarletonite from Murun alkaline complex (Russia): a synergic experimental and theoretical approach	609
Mesto E.*, Lacalamita M., Zucchi M., Iaccarino S., Vezzoni S., Pieruccioni D., Brogi A. & Schingaro E. - Crystal chemistry of carpholite of the Middle Tuscan Ridge (inner Northern Apennines)	610
Monico S.*, Marinoni N., Gatta G.D., Adamo I., Prospero L., Mácová P. & Ševčík R. - Partially crystalline silica varieties in gemmology: the case study of the blue Andean opal	611
Pavese A.* - Interpreting mineral transformations	612
Rizzo F.*, Bosi F., Tempesta G., Skogby H., Bernardini S., Vadrucci M. & Agrosi G. - Causes of color changes in tourmalines after thermal and irradiation treatments	613
Sist E.*, Parisi F. & Princivalle F. - Crystal chemistry of clinopyroxenes and spinels enclosed in mantle xenoliths (Mandakh-Mandal-Gobi area, Mongolia)	614
Ulian G.* & Valdrè G. - Graphene-brucite 2D heterojunctions: an ab initio crystal-chemical investigation ...	615

S22. The science of clays and zeolites: from genesis to sustainable applications

Annibaldi Corona M.*, Calcaterra D., Cappelletti P., Izzo F., Langella A., Mercurio M. & Guerriero L. - Mineralogical analysis of clayey earthflow materials and implications for assessing susceptibility to solid-to-fluid transition	617
Balzan S.*, Botezatu C., Faccini B., Ferretti G., Galamini G., Mattioli L., Tassoni G. & Coltorti M. - A comprehensive study of ammonium removal from livestock effluents using zeolites in various operational scenarios	618
Battiston T., Comboni D.*, Lotti P. & Gatta G.D. - Exploring pressure-induced crystal structure and fluid interactions in ABC-6 zeolite group	619
Belviso C.*, Abdolrahimi M., Lettino A., Cavalcante F. & Peddis D. - Magnetic properties of bauxites and pre-fused hydrothermal product (zeolite)	620
Bolla A.*, Pinto D., Lenaz D., Del Fabbro M. & Paronuzzi P. - The clays involved in the 1963 Vajont slide: mineralogy, geotechnical characterization and geomechanical implications	621
Borsatto F.* & Jabbour C. - Analysis of practices with the potential to create sustainable value for the natural zeolite sector	622
Boscia S.*, Grifa C., Germinario C., Mercurio M., Langella A., Izzo F., Pauculo A., Gliubizzi R. & Pappalardo D. - Mineralogical characterization and alkaline activation of commercial metakaolins: potential applications	623
Cavalcante F., Belviso C. & Prosser G.* - Detailed characterization of mixed-layer illite/smectite provide new constraints for the geodynamic reconstruction of the Southern Apennines	624
Cavalcante F., Belviso C., Lettino A., Lando I.G. & Prosser G.* - Relationships between mineralogical and microstructural features in low-T metapelites from the Pollino area	625

Clausi M.*, Fernández-Jiménez A. & Pinto D. - A sustainable use of carbonates-rich clays for alkali activated materials manufacturing	626
Conte S.*, Fantini R., Nodari L., Gualtieri A.F., Arletti R., Molinari C., Dondi M. & Zanelli C. - Red clays as alternative raw materials in porcelain stoneware tiles: the effect of iron on the sintering process	627
Daković A.*, Marković M., Ožegović M., Smiljanić D., Obradović M., Kozarski M. & Krajišnik D. - Enhanced adsorption of mycotoxin zearalenone by clay-chitosan-surfactant composite	628
de Azevedo B.*, Panattoni F., Tardani M. & Masini C. - Innovative modified natural zeolites: effective strategies for hexavalent chromium removal from polluted waters	629
De Bonis A.*, Arienzo I., Ciarcia S., D'Antonio M., Ottner F., Verde M. & Morra V. - The clays from the Campania sector of southern Apennines (Italy): new mineralogical and geochemical insights to reconstruct their sedimentological and stratigraphic evolution	630
De Gregorio E., Ferone C., Izzo F., Langella A., Mercurio M., Migliaccio C.*, Occhicone A., Roviello G. & Tarallo O. - Alkaline and acid red mud-metakaolin based geopolymers: mineralogical and morphological characterization	631
Di Leo P.* - Mechanochemical technologies for decontamination of soils polluted by organic and inorganic xenobiotics based on the use of clay substrates and oxides/hydroxides	632
Girardi G.*, Clausi M., Petti R., Vitone C. & Pinto D. - Characterization and pre-treatment of low grade-clays for the preliminary evaluation of their suitability as precursor for alkali-activated binders	633
Javed S.*, Dondi M., Molinari C., Conte S., Arletti R., Fantini R., Gualtieri A., Siligardi C., Miselli P., Bignozzi M.C., Ridolfi G., Spalanzani G. & Zanelli C. - Characterization and valorization of dam sediments: potential use in building materials	634
Krajišnik D.*, Uskoković-Marković S., Pantić M., Lazić V., Daković A. & Marković M. - Chitosan-clay composite films: investigation of functional and antibacterial properties for potential biomedical application	635
Langella A., Bellino A., De Feo G., De Nicola F., De Sanctis M., Izzo F., Luciani E., Mercurio M., Napoletano M.*, Oppido S., Picariello E., Romano C., Trasacco F. & Baldantoni D. - Enhancement of Microbial and plant Biodiversity by Restoration of degraded soils in Mediterranean Areas through marine Compost and zeolites Exploitation (EMBRACE project)	636
Medini M., Clausi M., Cofano V.*, El Chami D. & Pinto D. - Tailored porous geopolymers for efficient ammonium adsorption: towards sustainable agricultural nutrient recovery	637
Molinari C., Graziano S.F., Guarini G., Conte S., Dondi M., Cappelletti P. & Zanelli C.* - Suitability of zeolitized tuff use in porcelain stoneware tiles production	638
Montesano G.*, Rispoli C., Petrosino P. & Cappelletti P. - Secondary and authigenic phase formation in the 50-year-old tuff from Surtsey (Iceland)	639
Pinto D.*, Lenaz D., Paronuzzi P. & Bolla A. - Application of Rietveld refinement for quantitative phase analysis of clays containing illite-smectite mixed-layer structures: the case study of Vajont bentonites	640
Salamè E., Cinelli C., Tonutti P., Brizzolara S., Panattoni F., Tardani M., Freitas Pio de Azevedo B.* & Masini C. - Ethylene capture using natural and altered zeolites during the storage period of kiwifruits	641
Tateo F.* - Clay sediments for health in the special geological area of the Euganean Hills	642
Tsitsishvili V.*, Panayotova M., Mirdzveli N. & Bish D. - Thermal stability of some natural zeolites from Georgia, Kazakhstan, and Armenia	643

S23. Assessing and mitigating natural risks: a multidisciplinary path from Geosciences to Citizen Science

Bonelli P.*, Abbatangelo G., Becci G., Cardinale D., Conelli A., Liuzzi G. & Morigi M. - An early warning system experiment for landslides in Grassano (Matera, Basilicata, Italy) with the active participation of the local population and self-made open-source instruments	645
Clemente E.*, Lapietra I., Colacicco R. & Rinaldi A. - Climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies in the Kenyan Rift Valley: the case of Baringo and Bogoria lakes	646
Colacicco R.*, Lapietra I., La Salandra M., Roseto R., Bellini F. & Capolongo D. - Citizen Science for the enhancement and knowledge of the territory: the YouthMappers@Uniba experience	647

Fracassi U.* - The (un)stable stewardship: The Earth Sciences amid accrued vulnerabilities, climate disruption, and resource management	648
Lisco S.*, Marangi M., Sini V. & Lapietra I. - Coastal and marine hazard awareness through citizen science in School	649
Lisco S.*, Rizzo A., de Luca A., Fracchiolla T., Sozio A., Bitetto F., Ravisato M., Trani R., Di Coccia I., Schiavo A., Giannattasio L., Pierri D. & Tamma M. - Students' engagement in coastal monitoring activities: preliminary outcomes from the Marevivo NauticinBlu project	650
Lo Presti V., Agate M., Balsamo L., Bracci M., Cassataro R., Maiorana M.G.* & Sulli A. - Submarine fluid escapes: their role on ground instabilities. Learning examples of RETURN project	651
Mele D.*, Dellino P., Dioguardi F. & Sulpizio R. - Probabilistic hazard maps of pyroclastic density current at Vesuvius volcano (Italy): a new strategy for risk reduction	652
Mureddu A.* - Zoning of territorial hazard for the evaluation and mitigation of hydrogeological risk: morphometric, meteorological, climatic, geolithological and hydrogeological - hydraulic analysis of the Rio Corr'e Pruna basin (Sardinia - Italy)	653
Ranaldi M.*, Carapezza M.L., Tarchini L. & Barberi F. - Hazard from endogenous gas emission in the north and center Lazio Region	654
Rinaldi A., Bonamassa G., Fracchiolla R.*, Lapietra I., Liso I.S., Lollino P., Lorusso G. & Parise M. - Sinkhole risk perception in the urban area of Altamura (Southern Italy)	655
Sandron D.*, Saraò A., Tamaro A. & Rebez A. - Citizen Science for seismic risk reduction strategies and sustainable management	656
Tarchini L.*, Carapezza M.L. & Ranaldi M. - Assessing and mitigating natural gas risk at Cava dei Selci (Colli Albani volcano) through combined geochemical, epidemiological and agro-environmental studies	657
Tavecchio W.* - Protects and heats	658
Trigila A.* & Iadanza C. - Data and maps on natural hazards to support risk mitigation measures	659
Valensise G.* - Beyond fault scarps: the role of geologists in the assessment of seismic hazard and risk	660
S24. Assessment of multihazards and seismic microzonation in urban areas	
Acunzo G., Pagliaroli A. & Giallini S.* - P4Quad a Pre- and Post-Processor for QUAD4M 2D site response analyses	662
Andriani G.F.*, Diprizio G., Liso I.S., Lollino P., Milella D., Morelli P. & Parise M. - Dynamic properties of soils obtained by means of combined resonant column and cyclic torsional shear tests for the Seismic Microzonation studies of Apulia (SE Italy)	663
Argentieri A., Ballarini V., Bordoni P., Cara F., Cultrera G., Doglioni C., Naso G., Orsini G., Perniola B., Pischiutta M., Puglia R., Rotella G.*, Spina D. & Stecchiotti R. - From top to bottom: characterizing the strategic site of Palazzo Valentini (Rome)	664
Ariano M.*, Fantozzi P.L. & Albarello D. - A systematic analysis on Italian national territory to test the role of local topographic effects	665
Bausilio G., Tufano R.*, Calcaterra D., Guerriero L. & Di Martire D. - Multirisk analysis of the city of Naples (Italy) using the Rock Engineering Systems (RES) method	666
Benigni M.S., Catalano C., Giuffrè M.*, Endreny T. & Rugani B. - The neglected side of post-disaster temporary settlements: how to manage it with NbS for sustainable urban development	667
Bonorino L.*, Beccaris G., Chiozzi P., Cogorno A., Filippi E., Narizzano R., Prandi S. & Verdoya M. - Lithological control on the indoor radon concentration: the case study of western Liguria	668
Cacioli M.G., Mancini M.*, Cosentino G., Carfagna N., Coltella M., Francescone M., Pacitti P., Albarello D., Motti A., Natali N., Simone G., Ognà M., Stigliano F. & Moscatelli M. - Update of the Level 2 Seismic Microzonation in Umbria Region: methodology and perspectives	669
Calamita G.*, Stabile T.A., Falabella F., Pepe A., Gallipoli M.R., Bellanova J., Serlenga V., Piscitelli S., Gueguen E. & Perrone A. - Integrating remote sensing and geophysical techniques for assessing landslide hazard in an Italian Apennine town	670
Capone P.*, Pierri P., Romeo A., Casarano D. & Del Gaudio V. - Accelerogram selection for site response modelling in seismic microzonation	671

Carfagna N.*, Pieruccini P., Fantozzi P. & Albarello D. - Mapping seismostratigraphical amplification effects at regional scale from geological data	672
Ciaglia S.*, Francescone M., Pagliaroli A., Amoroso S., Salvatore N., Giallini S., Milana G., Di Giulio G., Vassallo M., Cara F., Lanzo G., Basi M. & Pizzi A. - First results from level 3 Seismic Microzonation of Sulmona (AQ), Central Italy	673
D'Agostino A.*, Porchia A., Tortorici G., Pavano F., Ortolano G., Cavuoto G., Moscatelli M. & Catalano S. - Automated tools for the reconstruction and spatialization of stratigraphic successions to support seismic site effects analysis	674
Fantozzi P.L., Ariano M.*, Moscatelli M. & Albarello D. - Realization of the database of geometries and characteristic parameters of "Microzone Omogenee in Prospettiva Sismica" (MOPS) throughout the National territory	675
Fontana C.*, Tomassoni V. & Giuffrè M. - Why should we bother about risk reduction at the urban scale? A methodology to assess the effectiveness of seismic prevention measures on urban system functionality	676
Fredella F.*, Del Gaudio V., Wasowski J., Venisti N. & Capone P. - Modelling site amplification as factor of slope susceptibility to co-seismic failures in hill-top towns	677
Gallicchio S., Pepe M.*, Zucchi M., Brogi A., Del Gaudio V., Wasowski J. & Venisti N. - Geological mapping and structural analyses in seismic microzonation for Jv-based subunit discrimination: preliminary results from Gravina in Puglia (Southern Italy)	678
Lapietra I.*, Colacicco R., Dellino P., Rizzo A. & Capolongo D. - Mapping social vulnerability to multi-hazard scenarios: a GIS-based approach at census track level	679
Licata V.* - Uncertainties of soil profiles for seismic response analyses	680
Licata V.* & Conti R. - A new soil constitutive model for nonlinear 1D seismic site response analyses	681
Livani M.*, Petracchini L., Benetatos C., Marzano F., Billi A., Carminati E., Doglioni C., Petricca P., Maffucci R., Codegone G., Rocca V., Verga F. & Antoncetti I. - A geological and geophysical database of the Po Plain and the northern Adriatic Sea (northern Italy) as potential tool for the assessment and mitigation of natural and anthropic hazards	682
Lovati S.*, Massa M., Maraio S., Puglia R., Ferrari E., Rizzo A.L., Brunelli G., Varchetta F., Villani F., Figlioli A., Mascandola C. & Luzi L. - Geological and stratigraphic setting of the metropolitan area of Milan (Italy): implications for site-dependent seismic hazard assessment through high-resolution geophysical investigation	683
Nisio S., Madonna S.*, Ruggiero L. & Gentili F. - Natural and anthropogenic sinkhole in Italy: the importance of an interdisciplinary approach	684
Pietrosante A.*, Di Salvo C., Maffucci R. & Ciotoli G. - Multi-hazard map of the coastal area of Rome near the Fiumicino airport	685
Proietti Scopetta A.* & Piangiamore G.L. - Places reborn. Two cases of regenerated historic villages in Liguria and Umbria (Italy)	686
Romagnoli G.*, Muraro C., Niceforo D., Puzzilli L.M. & Ruscito V. - Geological complexity vs. seismic risk reduction strategies: preliminary results from level III seismic microzonation studies of Etna municipalities (eastern Sicily, Italy)	687
Ruggiero L.*, Ciotoli G., Mori F., Varone C., Di Salvo C., Finoia M.G., Annunziatellis A., Moscatelli M. & Nisio S. - Exploring the relationship between anthropogenic sinkholes and pluvial flooding in the urban area of Rome: a comprehensive evaluation of multiple hazards	688
Zaragoza Alonzo A.D.* & Zambrano M. - Advancing seismic microzonation: integration of deep learning for high-resolution Vs30 mapping in the Central Italy	689
S25. Landslide monitoring, modelling, and prediction: bridging new tools and data to the 'slope-failure model' perspective	
Argentieri A.*, De Ritis R., Fabiani M., Fittante L., Fubelli G., Lafavia C., Liggio F., Rotella G., Scaroni C., Seitone F. & Vitali P. - Landslides monitoring for the protection of the territory: the San Vito Romano study case (Rome metropolitan area, central Italy)	691
De Guidi G.*, Cassaniti C., Carnemolla F., Prisco M., Pulvirenti A.D., Pulvirenti G., Brighenti F., Giuffrida S. & Fardella A. - Geodetic-topographical monitoring of landslide affecting the urban area of Motta Sant'Anastasia (CT) Sicily	692

De Simone A. *, Guerriero L., Cevasco A., Pepe G., Tufano R., Raso E. & Calcaterra D. - Stability of terraced slopes accounting for potential hydrological scenarios in the UNESCO World Heritage Site of Cinque Terre, Northern Italy	693
Di Muro C. *, Calcaterra D., Di Martire D. & Guerriero L. - A combination of deep learning and InSAR techniques for landslide hazard assessment	694
Dogliani A. * - Large-scale landslide mapping based on deep-learning paradigms	695
Dogliani A. *, Di Taranto L., Fiorentino A., Guericchio A. & Simeone V. - Nutcracker-like masonry bridges deformation and failure due to slow gravitational deformation	696
Ferrarotti M., Chicco J.M. *, Marmoni G.M., Fiorucci M., Tufano R., Di Martire D., Esposito C., Mandrone G. & Martino S. - Multidisciplinary approach on the preparatory effect of wildfires in shallow landslides	697
Francioni M. *, Ottaviani F. & Ahmed M. - Survey, data visualization and numerical modelling: An overview about how the new tools and methods of analysis can influence landslide studies	698
Hameed A. *, Confuorto P., Parise M., Lollino P., Ishfaq M. & Alias Aamir Soomro M.H. - Landslide susceptibility, vulnerability, and risk assessment based on remote sensing and GIS data models: a case study at the eastern Hindukush Mountain ranges, Pakistan	699
Hu L., Donati D. *, Landi G., Zama F. & Borgatti L. - Development and application of an enhanced inversion algorithm for the reconstruction of the basal surface of landslides	700
Martinello C. *, Di Frisco G., Conte A., Mineo G., Bellomo V., Azzara G., Mercurio C., Albo S., Calderón-Cucunuba L.P., Conoscenti C., Cappadonia C., Agnesi V. & Rotigliano E. - Biased landslide inventories and illusory susceptibility model high performances: a test in western Sicily	701
Minervino Amodio A., Gioia D., Corrado G. * & Schiattarella M. - Multi-temporal geomorphological analysis and seismic surveys as tools for the investigation of a complex slow-moving landslide: an example from the southern Apennines	702
Nava L. *, Mondini A., Bhuyan K., Fang C., Monserrat O., Novellino A. & Catani F. - Sentinel-1 SAR-based globally distributed landslide detection by deep neural networks	703
Niaz J. *, Lollino P. & Niaz A. - Integrated geophysical and geotechnical investigations of Upper Sarbala Landslide: a case study of Himalayas Mountain ranges, Pakistan	704
Patera A. * & Fabbri A.G. - Assessing landslide hazards in the Volcanic Crater of Lake Albano, Rome, Italy: feasibility and challenges	705
Yurdakul E. *, Arnone E., Nardi F. & Capolongo D. - Assessment of the risk of shallow landslides integrating InSAR and optical data with a distributed eco-hydrological model	706
 S26. Sinkholes vs. land subsidence: assessment of the geological hazards and impacts on environment and society	
Bausilio G. *, Di Martire D. & Calcaterra D. - Anthropogenic sinkholes' susceptibility assessment in Palermo, Italy, using a machine learning algorithm	708
Buffardi C. * - A geological-geotechnical approach to analyze the causes of subsidence in the Volturno River plain (northern Campania, Italy)	709
Busetti A., Corradetti A., Leone C., Rai P., Zini L. & Calligaris C. * - Storm-induced coastline sinkholes monitored by means of uncrewed aerial systems (UAS) in the gulf of Trieste (NE Italy)	710
Campanale F., Liso I.S., Parise M. & Spalluto L. * - Anatomy of a small sinkhole near the Adriatic coast	711
Coda S. *, Davino S., Abagnale G., Di Martire D. & Allocca V. - Ground deformation induced by piezometric levels fluctuations in the plain of the Sarno River (southern Italy)	712
De Ritis R. *, Rotella G., Argentieri A., Calderoni G., Chiappini M., Ciotoli G., Doglioni C., Fabiani M., Marra F., Nisio S., Tolomei C. & Vitali P. - Natural risks and protection of the territory: the San Martino Valley case history (Capena, Rome metropolitan area)	713
Demurtas L. *, Bruno L. & Amorosi A. - Subsidence in the Po Plain (Northern Italy) during the last 500 ky .	714
Esposito L., Fiorillo F., Leone G., Caputo M.C. *, De Carlo L., Masciale R., Passarella G., Turturro A.C., Andriani G.F., De Santis V., Lollino P. & Parise M. - Sinkhole development along the Apulian coastlines, within the framework of the project Fu.Co.Ka. (Future scenarios in Coastal Karst)	715

Fabozzi M.A.* & Moliterno E. - Artificial cavities and risk assessment: the case study of the Cloister of Sant'Agostino (Caserta, Italy)	716
Fracchiolla R.*, Bonamassa G., Liso I.S., Lollino P., Lorusso G. & Parise M. - Building a database for the analysis of sinkholes related to artificial cavities: the case study of Altamura (Apulia, Southern Italy)	717
Guarino P.M.*, Belvederi G., Licata V., Perrotti M. & Roma M. - GNCA database for stability assessment of artificial cavities	718
Lapietra I.*, Liso I.S., Lollino P., Fracchiolla R., Parise M. & Rinaldi A. - A multidisciplinary approach for sinkhole mitigation strategies: the case of the urban area of Altamura (southern Italy)	719
Mastrobattista P., Guarino P.M.*, D'Angiò D., Fiano V. & Pompili R. - Sinkholes in the Campo Soriano karst plain (Central Italy)	720
Mevoli F.A., Fazio N.L., Perrotti M., Parise M. & Lollino P.* - A user-friendly and mechanically-based method to assess the stability of underground caves: the iSUMM abaci	721
Nisio S., Madonna S.*, Ruggiero L. & Gentili F. - Natural and anthropogenic sinkholes in volcanic areas an underestimated hazard	722
Onorato M.*, Liso I.S., Parise M., Zini L., Onorato R., Congedo M., Poto M., Palmisano G. & Puglia G. - Collapse sinkholes at Palude del Capitano (Nardò, Italy)	723
Pérez-Villar G., Bausilio G.*, Calcaterra D., Di Martire D. & Gutiérrez F. - Diapiric uplift and ground-instability processes in the Cardona salt extrusion (NE Spain) analysed by geomorphological mapping and satellite interferometry	724
Piscitelli A.*, Liso I.S., Parise M. & Mastronuzzi G. - Coastal sinkhole mapping and evolution along the Taranto coastline	725
Ruberti D.*, Buffardi C., Da Lio C., Donnici S. & Tosi L. - Land subsidence in the Italian coastal plains: an overview	726
Ruberti D.*, Fabozzi M.A., Liso I.S., Lollino P., Vennari C., Vigliotti M., Capasso G., Corbelli V. & Parise M. - Artificial cavities and sinkholes in the hydrographic district of the Southern Apennines of Italy: findings, architectural variability and risk assessment	727
Ruggiero L.*, Ciotoli G., Mori F., Varone C., Moscatelli M. & Nisio S. - Mapping sinkhole susceptibility in Italy: a machine-learning approach for risk assessment and management	728
Teatini P.*, Baldan S., Cosma M., Da Lio C., Donnici S., Ferronato M., Mazzia A., Minderhoud P., Tosi L. & Zoccarato C. - Autocompaction as a main driver of coastal depositional environments	729
Tufano R.*, Bausilio G., Di Martire D., Guerriero L., Annibali Corona M., Nisio S. & Calcaterra D. - Updated inventory of anthropogenic sinkholes in Naples (Italy)	730
Yaqoob I.*, Zini L., Forte E., Ciotoli G. & Calligaris C. - Quinis: a small hamlet in the Alta Val Tagliamento valley (NE Italy), example of resilience to sinkhole geohazard	731
S27. Caves, mines and other underground spaces as field laboratories in environmental geology	
Balestra V.*, Fiorucci A., Marini P. & Bellopede R. - A research to study the unstoppable subterranean journey of microplastics	733
Balestra V., Peruzzi A., Marini P. & Bellopede R.* - Monitoring of lampenflora growth on speleothems exposed to LED lights in show caves	734
Cossu Q.A., Arca B., Cinus D.*, Ferrara R., Arca A., Ventura A. & Duce P. - Technological innovation and environmental monitoring for the evaluation of the bearing capacity in tourist caves	735
Didonna F., Liso I.S.*, Fregola R.A., Messina F. & Serrone M. - Sustainable speleology and cave conservation	736
Fioraso M.* & Riva A. - Speleogenesis and hydrostructure development in conglomerate-dominated sedimentary sequences: the "Castel Sotterra" Cave	737
Gaudiosi I.*, Livani M., Simionato M., Mancini M., Tentori D., Paoletta L., Gozzi M., Pennica F., Polpetta F., Stigliano F., Trapasso F., Di Monda D., Terzo M., Argiolas F., Croce P., Piro S. & Moscatelli M. - CALIGOLA: a project for enhancing the knowledge of underground archaeological sites in the Palatine Hill through the integration of geological and geophysical data with new technologies	738
Idini A.*, Masala O. & Sanna L. - Metals discharge from underground mine drainage of Argentiera Pb-Zn-Ag mine, NW Sardinia, Italy	739

Mastronuzzi G.*, Fiore A., Parise M., Tropeano M. & Tarantini F. - Karst and cave environment conservation in the Alta Murgia National Park	740
Ruberti N.* & Sanna L. - Teaching sustainable planning of show caves	741
Ruberti N.*, Esposito M. & Sanna L. - Radon monitoring in underground workplaces. The case of Sardinia region (Italy)	742
Sanna L.* - Moisture on underground walls in abandoned mines as source of acid drainage	743
Sanna L.*, Pusceddu C., Sanna U. & Floris G. - Disentangling natural signal from anthropogenic contribution in the temperature dynamics within show caves	744
Tinagli L.*, La Rosa A. & Paoli G. - A long-term analysis of mining-induced sinkhole activity in Gavorrano (Tuscany, Italy) by remote sensing and field data	745
Vigna B.* & Balestra V.* - Relationship between air-rock-water temperatures in karst caves and surface temperatures	746
Vigna B.* & Balestra V. - Anthropogenic impact assessment in show caves through environmental parameters monitoring	747
Vogel B., Calaforra J.M., Uasapud Enriquez N.V., Zupan Hajna N. & Parise M.* - List of endangered caves and karst, an initiative from the International Union of Speleology	748

S28. Experiences of data sharing and use in the frame of Research Data Infrastructures

Antonucci A.*, Rovida A. & Locati M. - Sharing seismological data related to historical earthquakes in Italy	750
Cacciola L.*, Corsaro R.A., Reitano D., Federico C. & Messina G. - GeoChem: structure and tools of a database for geochemical data of volcanic areas	751
Carta R.*, Battaglini L., Clemente F., Lo Faro S., Petricca P. & Schvarcz T. - The CARG Project's experience in sharing geological data	752
Castorina G., Manganello P.L.*, Blumetti A.M., Guerrieri L. & Congi M.P. - Harmonization of the new release of Earthquake Environmental Effects Catalogue (EEE Catalogue) in the context of Research Data Infrastructures	753
Cataldi L., Zuliani D., Barnaba C.*, Magrin E., Di Bartolomeo P., Bernardi P., Galvi S., Moratto L., Tunini L., Saraò A., Poggi V., Comelli P., Rossi G. & Picozzi M. - Advancing seismological and geodetic data management at the OGS	754
Congi M.P., Petricca P., Castorina G.*, Tomassetti L., Roccatello E. & D'Ambrogio C. - The CARG project towards 3D geology: definition of standards for the construction, consultation, and distribution of three-dimensional geological models	755
Corsaro R.A.*, D'Oriano C., Di Muro A., Geyer A., Gurioli L., Pappalardo L., Pennisi M., Principe C., Pompilio M. & Re G. - How to organise a rock repository of volcanic samples: a proposal of metadata model	756
Di Giuseppe P.*, Perrone E., Gennaro S., Agostini S., Trumpy E., Baneschi I., Boschi C., Cornacchia I., Pennisi M., Regattieri E., Rielli A., Salvadori M., Vezzoni S. & Provenzale A. - The Isotope Virtual Research Environment developed within ITINERIS Project: example of mixing modelling	757
Fares M.*, Carluccio I., Danecek P., Della Bina E., Franceschi D., Mandiello A., Maniscalco M., Pintore S. & Tavani F. - EIDA Italian node: seismic data curation preservation e dissemination	758
Ferrari E., Massa M., Rizzo A.L., Lovati S.*, Scafidi D., Puglia R., Varchetta F., Figlioli A., D'Alema E., Mirena S. & Luzi L. - MUDA: the dynamic geophysical and geochemical MULTiparametric DATABASE	759
Funaro M.*, Congi M.P., Campo V. & Manganello P. - The research infrastructure of GeoSciences: from datasets analysis to harmonization process	760
Gennaro S.*, Di Giuseppe P., Perrone E., Agostini S., Trumpy E., Assante M., Candela L., Pagano P., Procaccini M., Coro G. & Provenzale A. - New tools for geo-scientific data management in the framework of the ITINERIS project leveraging D4Science e-infrastructure capabilities	761
Guerrieri L.*, Battistoni P., Cipolloni C., Passaquieti R., Rizzo M. & Sebillio M. - GeoSciences IR: a cloud research infrastructure for regional geological surveys	762

Indovina E.*, Cacciola L., Domínguez-Cerdeña I., Geyer A., Guehenneux Y., Júlíusdóttir R., Komorowski J-C. J., Labazuy P., Nave R., Puglisi G., Reitano D., Saurel J-M., Spampinato L. & Vogfjörd K. - Fostering the Open Science paradigm and strengthening the European volcanology community: contributions of the Volcano Observations Thematic Core Service to EPOS ERIC	763
Maceroni D.*, Castorina G., Blumetti A.M., Bonadeo L., Comerci V., Di Manna P., Guerrieri L. & Congi M.P. - The new version of ITHACA Catalogue supported by GeoSciences IR and MEET projects	764
Paciello R.*, Bailo R. & Freda C. - The EPOS research infrastructure and its FAIR data management approach	765
Paolillo A.*, Orefice S. & Fiorentino A. - Geological data from submerged areas: a national standardised and harmonised database	766
Pennisi M.*, Baneschi I., Vivaldo G., D’Incecco S., Raco B., Donato A., Lelli M., Berton A., Pieracci D., Puglisi G. & Provenzale A. - Instrumental enhancement to study Mt Etna ecosystem: Carbon dioxide measurements using Eddy Covariance and flux chambers (PON-GRINT project)	767
Perrone E.*, Di Giuseppe P., Gennaro S., Agostini S., Trumpy E., Baneschi I., Boschi C., Cornacchia I., Pennisi M., Regattieri E., Rielli A., Salvadori M., Vezzoni S. & Provenzale A. - The ISOTOPE Virtual Research Environment (ITINERIS project, PNRR)	768
Vallone R.* & Basili R. - Sharing data on seismogenic faulting in Europe: the EDSF platform	769
S29. Multidisciplinary and numerical modelling: a comprehensive approach for upcoming Geosciences	
Califano C.*, Salone R., Troiano A., Di Giuseppe M.G., Isaia R. & Di Maio R. - Integrating geophysical models and numerical simulations to study the dynamics of the active geothermal system of Vulcano island (Italy)	771
Castronuovo R.*, Borghetti M., Ferrara A.M.S., Spatola M.F. & Nolè A. - Vegetation cover dynamics in the Mediterranean region: a spectral-based assessment of the riparian vegetation patterns	772
Dioguardi F.*, Chiodini G. & Costa A. - Probabilistic hazard modelling of the non-volcanic gas emissions of Mefite d’Ansanto, Southern Italy	773
Fazio N.L.*, Sollecito F., Lollino P. & Fazio V. - Enhancing the assessment of underground cave stability through machine learning-driven mechanically-based methods	774
Fazio N.L., Lollino P.*, Mevoli F., de Lucia D. & Ugenti A. - 3D limit equilibrium analyses for landslide susceptibility analyses at the urban area scale	775
Ferroni L.*, Tassinari R., Martina A. & Marrocchino E. - Comparative soil-to-plant fractionation of Rare Earth Elements in chlorophyll-deficient wheat mutants	776
Leoni G., De Caterini G., Vizzini G.*, Assennato F., Bianco P.M., Decorso C., Delfini C., Ferrigno F., Finocchiaro G., Fumanti F., Guerrieri L., Lucarini M., Roggero F., Tria N.G. & Spizzichino D. - Giasone: a method to assess sustainability of georesources cultivation	777
Lucci G.*, Bruno L., Purri F., Di Martino A. & Amorosi A. - Shallow subsurface stratigraphy of the Mirandola Area (central Po Plain) reconstructed through combined sedimentological and geotechnical analysis	778
Martina A.*, Aliprandi E., Ferroni L., Tassinari R. & Marrocchino E. - Multiparameter markers of territoriality: geochemical-isotopic and fluorometric analysis for asparagus characterization	779
Massaro S.*, Costa A., Macedonio G., Dioguardi F., Tamburello G., Bini G., Rufino F., Caliro S., Chiodini G., Sandri L., Selva J., Stocchi M., Santi A. & Avino R. - Model calibration and validation of carbon dioxide dispersion in the Atmospheric Surface Layer using data from La Solfatara crater (Campi Flegrei, Italy)	780
Parrino N.*, Caldareri F., Palano M., Burrato P., Lo Presti V., Agate M., Gasparo M. & Sulli A. - Eroding edges: exploring the tectonic forcing on submarine canyon evolution	781
Perrini M.*, Gola G., Tizzani P., Fedi F., Brahim M. & Castaldo R. - Thermo-rheological modelling of the Yellowstone caldera: insights into volcanic processes	782
Purri F.*, Di Martino A. & Amorosi A. - 3D stratigraphic architecture of the late Quaternary Pescara paleovalley and seismic site characterization	783
Roseto R.*, Lollino P., Parise M., Spalluto L., Festa V. & Fazio L. - Analysis of possible failure mechanisms of a coastal rocky cliff by means of a three-dimensional discrete element model	784

Salone R.*, Troiano A., Di Giuseppe M.G., Isaia R. & Di Maio R. - A new insight into the dynamics of the Pisciarelli hydrothermal system (Campi Flegrei, Southern Italy) based on the integration of geophysical and numerical modelling	785
Schiavo M., Giambastiani B.M.S.*, Greggio N., Colombani N. & Mastrocicco M. - Integrated approach for Arsenic contamination assessment in the entire Padana Plain (Italy)	786
Silvestri S. *, Giambastiani B.M.S., Costantini F., Pezzolesi L., Guerrini F., Turicchia E., Merloni N., Archetti R., Guerrero M., Gaeta M.G., Zanutta A., Girelli V.A., Tini M.A., Lambertini A., Giordano C.M., Boninsegni A., Casadei I., Costa M., Cavaliere E., Del Bianco F., Stanghellini G., Ravaioli S., Nannini S., Bonaccorso E., Cerrano C., Scottà F.C. & Ponti M. - Past and recent evolution of the submerged beach, shoreline, and dune-beach morphology as baseline to monitor a nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement	787
Sobbe A.*, Bianchini G., Rizzo E. & Brombin V. - Geophysical and geochemical data integration for agricultural soil monitoring and prevention of the effects of salinity, organic matter, and climate change in the Province of Ferrara (Northern Italy)	788
Srivastava E.*, Parrino N., Kumar P.C., Caldarelli F., Maiorana M., Palano M. & Sulli A. - Fluid migration along fault and fracture systems in the Sicily straits: high-resolution mapping reveals connections	789
Stocchi M.*, Houzeaux G., Costa A., Folch A., Massaro S. & Sulpizio R. - Modeling the priming mechanism of phreatic and geothermal eruptions: physical model and preliminary integration results	790
Tranfa P.*, Di Renzo V., Izzo F., Langella A., Mercurio M., Mercurio V., Cappelletti P. & D'Antonio M. - A multidisciplinary approach used for winemaking process investigation: the Cantina di Solopaca (Benevento, Italy) case study	791
Watanabe D.*, Bruno L. & Amorosi A. - Holocene sedimentary and geomorphological evolution of the Po Plain between Po, Secchia and Panaro rivers, reconstructed through a morpho-stratigraphic approach	792
S30. Women in Geosciences: a journey through the social changes from the past to present and future scenarios	
Amelio A., Doria S., Faieta D., Pagliaro S., Piacentini T., Pondrelli M.*, Ranieri B. & Vessia G. - The challenge to promote equal opportunities in the daily life at university: searching for best practices	794
Bozzano F., Antonielli B., Bigi S.*, Calzolari L., Della Seta M., Coltellacci D., Medeghini L., Pacella A., Piacentini D., Sannino A., Scuderi M., Tinti E., Tullio C., Scacchia E., Ruspandini T. & Vergari F. - Gender equality plan (GEP) of Earth Science Department in the framework of the Science Faculty and Sapienza University	795
Cofano A.* & De Ceglie R. - Fossils, drawings and letters. Women's contribution to the development of early 19 th century geosciences	796
Colacicco R.* - The frontiers of the space and the sea: the records of Dr. Kathryn Sullivan	797
Contessi M.* - Anna Fiori and the balance between teaching and research in the years between the Second World War	798
De Lucia M.*, Cafarella L. & Pignone M. - Engaging Women in Science: harnessing social media for STEM and Geoscience outreach	799
Di Bucci D.*, Franceschetti C. & Postiglione T. - 30 years of Women in Science in Italy through the lens of the Major Risks Commission	800
Donato P.* & Lucà F. - Promoting the Geosciences among the young women: an example in the framework of the PLS program	801
Ducci D.* - Participation of women in engineering geology and hydrogeology research in Italy	802
Fregola R.A., Maiorano P., Micheletti F., Sabato L. & Zucchi M.* - Learning from the pioneer women in Geosciences	803
Gambino F.*, Porrone A., Mancini S., Pereira L., Bellopede R., Marini P., Faraudello A. & Dino G. - Uncovering the glass ceiling mechanisms in the Geosciences: towards equality in Academia and the private sector	804
Marinangeli L.*, Garzarella A., La Torre V., Salerno V.M. & Shahini E. - Webinars of Ud'A ex-students to valorise the professional careers of women geologist	805

Massaro S.*, Ashruf T., Anderlini L., Drymoni K., Forni F., Geyer A., Guerrero A., Pardo N., Scaini C., Tomašek I. & Viveiros F. - Is there still a price to pay for being a woman geoscientist? Perspectives and lessons learnt	806
Montomoli C.* - The Gender Equality Plan @ UniTo	807
Moretti M. *, Bianco F., Castello B., Cocina O., Cultrera G., Graziani L., Latorre D., Margheriti L., Montone P., Nostro C., Pastori M., Pondrelli S., Scognamiglio L. & Valoroso L. - The role of women in the Geosciences: the case of INGV in preparing and managing the emergencies	808
Radeff G.*, Tomassetti L., Garzarella A., D'Ambrogi C. & Lettieri M. - Women at the Geological Survey of Italy: where we were, where we are, where we are going	809
Rosati A. *, Sabato L. & Tropeano M. - Stubbornly holistic: Zonia Baber and her groundbreaking work in the field of Geosciences education	810
Sabato L., Zucchi M. & Tropeano M.* - A contribute to the PLS Project from “Women in Geosciences” of Bari University	811
 S31. The art of Geosciences communication	
Alberghina M.F.*, Ricca M., Ruffolo S.A. & La Russa M.F. - The valorisation of Cultural Heritage and the archaeometric studies as effective tools for disseminating scientific culture: the experience of the ADELE-RS project	813
Amoroso O. *, Gargiulo M.V., Napolitano F., Russo R. & Capuano P. - An educational escape room experience for teaching younger generations about seismic risk	814
Argentieri A.* & Tortonesi E. - The world in 2D: Alfonso Di Pasquale, between paintings and geological maps	815
Argentieri A., De Caterini G., De Ritis R. *, Romano M. & Rotella G. - Science in the Riviera dei Fiori: ‘traces elements’ of geology in Italo Calvino’s literary output	816
Bindellini G.*, Manucci F. & Romano M. - From bones to bulk: a 3D volumetric approach to estimating theropod dinosaur body mass	817
Bonadonna D.* - Depicting the unknown	818
Campo V.*, Antonietti D., Attanasio A., Coiro A. & Congi M.P. - GeoSciences IR: ‘Thematic geological content dissemination’ web system to support users	819
Cannone E.*, Manzella A., Galione M.R. & Criscuolo L. - Challenges and strategies in geothermal communication	820
Colizza E. *, Geniram A., Protopsalti I. & Salvi G. - The National Antarctic Museum-Section of Trieste: integrated educational approaches for understanding environmental and climate changes	821
Coluzzi R. *, Imbrenda V. & Fanti L. - Satellites, or the Big Eye at the time of the Anthropocene: remote sensing for capturing landscape changes	822
De Caterini G. *, Argentieri A., Delfini C., Galetto G. & Monaco V. - “The Fountain of the Four Rivers” (Rome, Piazza Navona) as a representation of the sense of wonder in Baroque art and science	823
De Novellis V. *, Ascione V., Somma R. & Zoccola M. - Science and Art in the dissemination of volcanic risk	824
Eramo G., De Tullio M. *, Monno A. & Mesto E. - Ever played a phase diagram? Thermodynamic graphs as musical scores for educational live performance	825
Eramo G., Monno A., Tempesta G., Mesto E. & De Tullio M.* - Gem Session: aural logos of gemstones by sonification	826
Erba E. *, Mariani L. & Poli S. - Geoscience communication through videos	827
Facchino E., Mazzei S., Locchi L. & Giamborino A.* - The Italian Paleoart Award	828
Giamborino A. *, Petti F.M., Innamorati G. & Zuccari A. - The Time Machine Project - A travel into Deep Time	829
Giampaolo V. *, Calamita G., Corbo D., Fanti L. & Imbrenda V. - Land degradation: an unconventional tale	830
Lupi C. *, Marchini A., Brioschi S.A., Crenca E., Gazzola F. & Innocenti Malini G. - “Can You Sea?”: an aerial and acrobatic performance to involve people in marine bio-geoscience researches	831

Maganuco S.*, Ambrogi L., Capucella E., Figus C. & Gambini I. - Echoes of extinction: how an exhibition can unveil the lost world of dinosaurs through science and art	832
Mazzini I.* & CNR ECORD-IODP and ICDP Commission - How do comics help to learn about Marine Geology?	833
Monno A.*, Iurilli V. & Eramo G. - Earth Sciences in the Divine Comedy: a hidden story	834
Pioggia M.* & Sardella R. - SIGN ME IN - accessibility and usability of MUST (University Museum of Earth Sciences) explanatory panels for deaf visitors: an analysis	835
Troco E., Manucci F., Maganuco S.* & Ambasciano L. - Through the pages of the ages: conveying the unfathomable depth of time in an illustrated book	836
Zuccari C.*, Artegiani F., Fagioli G., Tancredi S. & Romano M. - From 'Gerusalemme Liberata' to Dante's Divina Commedia: the seismogenic hypothesis of earthquakes linked to underground winds	837
S32. Geosciences at school 2024	
Alvisi F.*, Cheimonopoulou M., Koulouri P., Mogias A. & Mokos M. - The dissemination of Marine Geosciences in schools as a contribution to the Ocean Literacy process: from teachers' training to hands-on activities	839
Barbarito L., Lillo A.*, Marzolla M., Menga H. & Ricco G. - The sea: life's source	840
Barletta M.L., Benedetto S., Genchi L., Ippolito M.P., Lillo A.*, Longano D., Ratti L. & Valletta S. - Science Nights at the High School Complex in Monopoli (BA)	841
Barone A.*, Madonia G. & Rotigliano E. - An experimental approach to improving the teaching-learning process in the geosciences	842
Benedetto S., Genchi L. & Valletta S.* - Caving and hiking activities for promoting knowledge and landscape preservation	843
Bianchini G.*, Brombin V., Tagliacollo L., Bonadiman C. & Tassinari R. - Outdoor science experiments, hands-on learning in nature: the Nirano Mud Volcano (NMV, Fiorano Modenese, Italy) open-field laboratory	844
Bini M.*, Zanchetta G., Lazzarotti M., Luppichini M., Gemignani G. & Tarantino I. - The didactical experience of the "Laboratory of climatology and environment" of the Master Course in Environmental Science of the University of Pisa	845
Braga R.*, Ballato P., Barani S., Bentivenga M., Bordoni M., Buosi C., Ciarcia S., Donato P., Fanti R., Forni F., Francese R., Giovanardi T., Invernizzi C., Lozar F., Morsilli M., Pondrelli M., Punturo R., Ragaini L., Renzulli A., Rigo M., Saldi G., Sciascia L., Sottili G., Tavarnelli E., Tropeano M., Vezzoli G., Vitale S. & Zini L. - A nationwide effort to engage secondary school students in geology - The new Progetto Nazionale Geologia of the Piano Lauree Scientifiche	846
Brustia E., Lucarini M., Pompili R.* & Primerano P. - A journey in the Caput Mundi geodiversity	847
Bussolesi M.*, Battiston T., Comboni D., Cavallo A. & Grieco G. - Georesources: finding the perfect mixture between science and dissemination in PCTO activities	848
Cattafi I., Sticchi A. & Braga R.* - Teaching geosciences with ChatGPT during the first year of an upper secondary school	849
Comino E.*, Balestra V., Bellopede R., Fazli M., Tamietto M., Treves A. & Zambrotta M. - Building bridges between academia and high school: the experience of "Open river Laboratory" project (in the framework of Percorsi per le Competenze Trasversali e l'Orientamento)	850
D'Addezio G.* & Besker N. - Geosciences through the eyes of primary school students: a visual journey	851
D'Amato M.* & Stornelli C. - STEAM project to raise young people's awareness of land protection	852
Della Seta M.* & Medeghini L. - REKHOVER-Science: REAlizing Kits for HOspitals to Visualize EaRth Sciences	853
Faedda G.L.* & Pascucci V. - Interdisciplinary approaches in geoscience education: exploring the application of entomology in ichnoentomology	854
Franza A.* & Pratesi G. - Geoscientific school heritage: from the past to the future	855
Furfori I.*, Albertarelli N., Bonaccorsi E., Colotti C. & Gioncada A. - Can the interdisciplinary approach be an asset for teaching Geosciences in Natural Sciences?	856

Furfori I.*, Bonaccorsi E., Chicco J.M., Gioncada A., Greco R., Occhipinti S., Piangiamore G.L. & Realdon G. - Didactics and dissemination in the field of georesources: the experience of the GeothermiX 2023 conference	857
Gallo Maresca M.* - Geological narratives, a new approach to assessing skills	858
Gravina T.* & Iannace A. - Fostering inquiry and engagement in Earth Science: designing and testing a specialized curriculum for Italian liceo students	859
Gravina T.*, Funicciello F., Realdon G. & Cifelli F. - Advancing geoscience education in Italy through teacher professional development: insights from the EGU-GEFO field officer initiative	860
Locritani M.*, Garvani S., Melini D., Merlino S., Grezio A., Cianetti S., Bianucci M., Danesi S., Muscari G., Lo Bue N., Alberti T., Rouwet D., Policicchio M., Magnaneschi M., Saragosa M., Maccarrone M., Martinicchio G., Saladino F., Sanfilippo S.R.D., Genitili A., Belloni V., Grandi D., Rossi L. & Guarnieri A. - MACMAP: a student-designed game to simulate multidisciplinary climate change project	861
Lupi C.*, Pelfini M. & Pettinari C. - Geology in down town: easy fieldtrips for learning Earth sciences out of school	862
Maramai A.*, Lombardo V. & Piangiamore G.L. - Two virtual reality tools to enhance earthquake and tsunami awareness	863
Occhioni M.* & Paris E. - A web virtual world activity on critical minerals in smartphones for 14-years old students	864
Occhipinti S.* - The learning process in Geosciences: analysis, evaluations, and proposals	865
Onida M.C.*, Fusi N. & Bonomi T. - Soil ecosystem: STEM approach for developing scientific thinking	866
Panza M.O., Parentini L., Pomarici R.L.* & Serinelli M.L. - #Io sono ambiente, a laboratory path on education for sustainable development in the “I.I.S. Duni-Levi”, a secondary school at Matera (Southern Italy)	867
Paterni M., Alvisi F., Bianucci M.*, Bini M., Casanova E., Caselli L., Castiglioni G., Castagnetti T., Ferdeghini F., Gigantesco P., Godani M., Locritani M., Luppichini M., Perfetti A., Rossi A. & Merlino S. - Adopt-a-Dune project: use of ‘virtual adoption’ and citizen science approach to increase knowledge and raise student awareness on coastal systems management	868
Pioggia M., Della Seta M. & Medeghini L.* - IN-MUST: for an inclusive Earth Sciences museum	869
Pioggia M.*, Sardella R., Della Seta M. & Medeghini L. - European Museums’ Night 2024: understanding radiometric dating through a scavenger hunt inside the MUST (Museo Universitario di Scienze della Terra, Sapienza)	870
Punturo R.*, Visalli R., Sturiale G., Maniscalco R. & Cirrincione R. - Raising environmental awareness in the students through geosciences: the educational importance of geotrails	871
Realdon G.*, Gallo M.T. & Occhioni M. - Ocean Literacy beyond knowledge: investigating ocean connections among a sample of children in Friuli Venezia Giulia (N-E Italy)	872
Roberto R., De Tullio M., Liso S., Rizzo A.* & Mastronuzzi G. - Education and training activities in the frame of the ecological transition: insights from the Earth and Geoenvironmental Sciences context	873
Ronca S., Berra F.*, Crippa G., Fumagalli P., Garavaglia A., Lustrino M., Mosconi A., Saracino G. & Sottili G. - Disaggregation of geological dissemination activities in focused initiatives: “hands-on” approach for stimulating geological curiosity and knowledge	874
Tosetti V.* & Giamborino A. - “Nella fucina di Efesto”: a new teaching project to promote meaningful geological learning. Peer tutoring from high school to primary school	875
Vitale S., Izzo F.*, Piegari E. & Riccardi U. - The GEOLAB experience at the DiSTAR (University of Naples Federico II, Italy)	876
S33. Fossil record, paleoenvironment and climate change throughout the Neogene and Quaternary Earth history	
Addante M.*, Herbert T., Caruso A., Girone A., Marino M., Scopelliti G. & Maiorano P. - Calcareous plankton and bio-geochemical climate signals during the Pliocene-Pleistocene transition in the Mediterranean area	878
Argenio C.*, Balestra B., Flores J.A. & Amore F.O. - Palaeoceanographic and paleoclimatic changes during the Marine Isotope Stage 5 at IODP Site 1385	879

Argiriadis E.*, Denniston R.F. & Columbu A. - Trace organic compounds in speleothems as a pioneering approach to high-resolution paleofire reconstruction	880
Baio M., Violanti D., Pezzotta A.*, Tantardini D., Zerboni A. & Crippa G. - Pliocene-Pleistocene evolution of the upper central Po Plain (Northern Italy)	881
Bini M.*, Caroti A., Cantini F., Fabiani F., Fornaciari A., Isola I., Lazzarotti M., Luppichini M., Mensing S., Palli J., Piovesan G. & Zanchetta G. - The last 2000 years of floods from Arno and Serchio rivers (Tuscany) from historical, geoarchaeological and stratigraphic data	882
Bronzo L., Cascella A.*, Bonomo S., Morigi C., Cacho I., Margaritelli G., Frigola J., Pena L.D. & Lirer F. - Calcareous nannofossil response to Holocene climatic events in the North Ionian Sea	883
Capotondi L.*, Correggiari A., Gennari R., Corino L., Maiorano P., Martinelli P., Remia A., Zonno E. & Riminucci R. - Benthic foraminiferal response to anthropogenic impact in the North Adriatic Sea during the last two centuries	884
Caruso A.* - Response of particular taxa to climatic and environmental variations during the evolution of the Mediterranean Sea: from the Messinian Salinity Crisis to Zanclean normal marine conditions	885
Cervellieri M.*, Scarponi D., Crippa G. & La Perna R. - Distribution pattern of macrobenthic assemblages along the Ideale Section of the Montalbano Jonico succession (southern Italy)	886
Cheli G.*, Zanchetta G., Isola I., Dong X., Pérez-Mejías C., Cheng H., Dallai L., De Waele J. & Columbu A. - Climate variability at around the 4.2 event based on novel $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ - $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ speleothem data from Sardinia (Italy, Western Mediterranean)	887
Cosentino C.*, Guastella R., Mancin N. & Caruso A. - Impact of the genus <i>Amphistegina</i> on the benthic foraminiferal association of the Pelagian Islands, an example of invasion in the Central Mediterranean Sea	888
De Santis N.*, Zanchetta G., Isola I., Columbu A., Vigna B., Regattieri E., Drysdale R., Hellstrom J. & Dallai L. - Paleohydrological changes during the early Holocene through the study of an isotope record from stalagmite of Bossea Cave (NW Italy)	889
Degl'Innocenti N.*, Niccolini G. & Bertini A. - Terrestrial and marine palynomorphs from Holocene deposits and mosses samples in the Mar Piccolo semi-enclosed marine basin (Taranto, Southern Italy)	890
Iannucci A.* & Sardella R. - Updates on the middle and late Villafranchian large mammal faunal turnovers	891
Isola I.*, Bini M., Columbu A., Di Vito M.A., Giaccio B., Hu H-M., Martini F., Pasquetti F., Sarti L., Mule F., Mazzoleni A., Shen C.C. & Zanchetta G. - New insights on MIS 9e and MIS 5e sea-level highstands from Infreschi Cave and Cilento Coast (Central Italy)	892
Isola I.*, De Santis N., Zanchetta G., Columbu A., Regattieri E., Drysdale R. & Hellstrom J. - Last glaciation Dansgaard-Oeschger events in speleothems from Central Italy	893
Logrieco A.*, De Santis V., Ortiz J.E., Palencia Y.S., Mastrototaro F., Chimineti G., Sozio A. & Caldara M. - Survey on <i>Pinna nobilis</i> associated benthic biocenosis with a paleoenvironmental approach in terraced marine deposits of the Last Interglacial period (Taranto, Italy)	894
Mancini A.M.*, Gennari R., Lozar F. & Negri A. - The climatic and oceanographic setting during the Messinian: what can be learned for present and future deoxygenation dynamics?	895
Marino M.*, Maiorano P., Girone A., Gallicchio S., Bassinot F., Nomade N., Simon Q., Bertini A., Herbert T., Petrosino P., Addante M., La Perna R., Trotta S. & Ciaranfi N. - Climatostratigraphy through a standard auxiliary boundary stratotype for the Middle Pleistocene subseries of the Quaternary System (Montalbano Jonico, southern Italy)	896
Mecozzi B.*, Bona F., Conti J., Lembo G., Mazzini I., Muttillio B., Pieruccini P. & Sardella R. - Palaeoenvironmental reconstruction of the lower levels of Grotta Romanelli (Apulia, southern Italy) based on the mammal record	897
Milaneschi L.*, Cornamusini G., Maffei J., Martini I., Cifelli F., Corti V., Mattei M., Zurli L. & Foresi L.M. - Portable X-ray fluorescence and Milankovitch cycles in coeval marine and continental Upper Pliocene deposits from the Valdelsa Neogene Basin (Southern Tuscany, Italy)	898
Parisi R.*, Aiello G., Barra D., Vitolo J.P. & Mazzini I. - Messinian, Pliocene and Pleistocene ostracod events in the Atlantic-Mediterranean area	899
Parisi R.*, Mazzini I. & Cronin T.M. - Ecosystem dynamics, climate change and glacial-interglacial cycles from Quaternary ostracod assemblages in the Corinth Gulf, Greece	900

Pepe F., Corradino M., Cirelli C.*, Casalbore D., Di Donato V., Incarbona A., Melini D., Molisso F. & Spada G. - The interplay between sedimentary supply, sea-level rise and tectonics from the last glacial maximum onwards: insights from the Sant'Eufemia continental shelf (Offshore Calabria, Italy)	901
Sarı S.*, Cipollari P., Cosentino D., Gliozzi E., Lirer F., Cornacchia I., Marchegiano M., Öğretmen N., Kanbur S., Mattei M. & Cifelli F. - The Mid-Pleistocene transition in the Eastern Mediterranean: a multi-proxy approach to reconstruct its impact at the southern margin of the Central Anatolian Plateau (CAP)	902
Scarponi D.*, Fitzgerald E., Nawrot R., Huntley J.W., Tomasovych A., Zuschin M. & Kowalewski M. - Late Holocene breakdown of antagonistic interspecific interactions in the western Adriatic Sea	903
Stefanelli D.*, Mecozzi B., Marino M. & Sardella R. - Paleoenvironmental remarks on the Early-Middle Pleistocene site of Contrada Monticelli (Apulia, Southern Italy)	904
Zanchetta G.*, Bini M., Chuan-Chou S., Columbu A., Drysdale R., Hsun-Ming Hu H., Isola I., Luppichini M., Milevski I., Natali S., Regattieri E., Hellstrom J., Pennos C. & Izdebski A. - Hydrological variability during the Roman and Medieval periods in the Balkan Peninsula using speleothems	905
Zanchi A.*, Ravazzi C., Chiesa S., Crosta G.B., Fascetta S. & Fusi N. - The deformational mega-structures of the Pianico-Sellere Basin (Iseo Lake, Lombardy) which evidence for their origin?	906
S34. A petrologic journey through the lithosphere	
Battifora C.*, Ferrando C., Crispini L. & Rampone E. - Reactive melt percolation in spinel mantle harzburgites from the Wadi Tayin Massif (Oman ophiolite)	908
Bonadiman C.*, Bianchini G., Braga R., Tagliacollo L. & Tassinari R. - Geochemical and petrological study of eastern limb of Rustenburg Layered Suit (Bushveld mafic complex)	909
Borghini G.*, Crotti C.F. & Fumagalli P. - Pyroxenite generation via high-pressure crystallization of a MORB-type basalt: an experimental study at 1-2.5 GPa	910
Brunelli D.*, Cipriani A., Verhoest L., Michailow M., Hemond C., Maia M. & Soltanmohammadi A. - Alkaline MORBs mark low-T domains along Mid Ocean Ridges	911
Bussolesi M.*, Grieco G., Cavallo A. & Sinojmeri A. - Variability in Platinum Group Elements enrichments in supra- and sub-Moho ophiolite chromitites: case studies from the Dinarides-Hellenides belt	912
Casetta F.*, Aulbach S., Faccincani L., Ashchepkov I., Abart R. & Ntaflou T. - Using olivine trace elements content as a tool to reconstruct the chemical log of the sub-cratonic lithospheric mantle and the evolution of kimberlite melts	913
Crotti C.F.*, Borghini G., Fumagalli P., Tiepolo M., Rampone E. & Stephan K. - MORB melt - harzburgite interaction at 1-2 GPa: experimental constraints on oceanic mantle refertilization	914
Del Rio M.*, Corradetti A., Černok A., Narduzzi F., Venier M. & Zibera L. - Petrographic and structural study of a lower crustal mafic-ultramafic sequence from the Sesia Valley (Ivrea-Verbano zone, Italy)	915
Dini A.*, Rielli A., Di Giuseppe P., Ruggieri G. & Boschi C. - The Se-Te-bearing VMS deposits of Tuscan ophiolites	916
Freitas V.A.*, Montanini A., Etiope G., Segadelli S., Artoni A. & Moretti I. - Exploration of natural hydrogen in the Northern Apennines, Italy	917
Grieco G.*, Bussolesi M., Comboni D. & Gjoca G. - Tests for implementing ophiolitic chromite concentrates from Albania mines to chromite foundry sands quality parameters	918
Grosso C.*, Ferrando S., Tursi F. & Rolfo F. - Serendipity-driven discovery of a new UHP slice in the southern Dora-Maira Massif	919
Guarino V.*, Bonazzi M., Nimis P., Guitarrari Azzone R., Cariddi B. & Zanetti A. - Subcontinental lithospheric mantle stratigraphy in the SW margin of São Francisco Craton: insights from xenocrysts and xenoliths trapped in the Três Ranchos kimberlite (APIP, Brazil)	920
Iaccarino S.*, Montomoli C., Pippo E., Carosi R., Cottle J. & Lanari P. - HT-LP extensional shear zones in the GHS (E Nepal): preliminary data on P-T-D conditions and timing	921
Innocenzi F., Martino L., Ronca S., Agostini S. & Lustrino M.* - Carbonatitic and related alkaline to ultralkaline melts in the Quaternary Eifel Volcanic Province, Germany	922
Malaspina N.*, Langenhorst F., Pollok K., Cerantola V., Murri M., Longa C., Bersani D. & Montanini A. - The redox state of heterogeneous mantle: clues from C-S-bearing clinopyroxenites	923

Maroni A.*, Miccoli A., Balestro G., Groppo C. & Castelli D. - The Monte Pagliano Unit in the southern Dora-Maira Massif (Western Alps): a preliminary petrologic study	924
Marras G.* & Stagno V. - Chemistry of sulfides in the Earth's mantle: insights from magmas, mantle xenoliths and inclusions in diamonds	925
Montanini A.*, Cluzel D., Secchiari A., Ferrari E., Heizler M., Jourdan F., Meffre S., Zhou R. & Teyssier C. - New geochemical and age constraints on forearc intrusive rocks from the New Caledonia ophiolite (SW Pacific): diversity of melts generated at hot subduction inception	926
Nerone S.*, Groppo C., Ágreda-López M., Petrelli M. & Rolfo F. - Kyanite trace element zoning as a method for unravelling migmatite petrological evolution	927
Nerone S.*, Lanari P., Forshaw J.B., Groppo C. & Rolfo F. - Quantitative isopleth thermobarometry for determination of optimal P-T conditions from Perple_X models	928
Petrocchia A.*, Caso F., Nerone S., Maffei A., Corno A. & Zucali M. - 2D vs. 3D rock investigation comparison and possible influences for thermodynamic modelling estimates	929
Poli S.* & Melluso L. - The origin of melilitites: an experimental study	930
Scarani S.*, Sanfilippo A., Basch V., Genske F. & Stracke A. - Compositional variability of the oceanic crust as a function of spreading rates: insights from the ultra-slow spreading Gakkel Ridge (Arctic Ocean)	931
Secchiari A.*, Toffolo L. & Tumiatì S. - Quantitative analysis of sulfur volatile species generated from HP-HT experiments: a novel approach	932
Soltanmohammadi A.*, Bedard J.H. & Hinchey A. - Sulfide mineralization in the Lower Crust of the Bay of Islands Ophiolite, Canada	933
Soltanmohammadi A.*, Rabinowicz M. & Fontaine JF. - From cold to hot mantle: exploring new concepts for migration of alkaline melts and perspective on critical minerals	934
Spieß R.*, Festa V. & Tursi F. - When modern petrology meets advanced microstructural analysis	935
Tagliacollo L.*, Bonadiman C., Saccani E., Bianchini G., Brombin V. & Tassinari R. - Potential mineral resources in historically dismissed volcanogenic massive sulfide (VMS) deposits of the Emilia Romagna region (Italy): petrological and geochemical study for Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) exploration and exploitation	936
Terranova K.G.*, Narduzzi F., Venier M., Del Rio M., Černok A. & Zibera L. - Exploring a garnet-bearing pegmatoid pyroxenite in the Ivrea Verbano Zone (northwestern Italy): petrography and phase equilibrium modelling	937
Tumiatì S.*, Faucher G., Monzillo A., Ferrari E., Toffolo L., Erba E. & Poli S. - Investigating isotopic signatures of CO ₂ produced by coccolithophore algae in subduction zones: experimental insights and modeling approach	938
Tursi F.*, Godard G., Braga R. & Piluso E. - It's getting hot, depleted, dense and dry: evolution of garnet-sillimanite restites from Catena Costiera (northern Calabria, Italy)	939
Wafik A., Visalli R.*, Punturo R., Conte A.M., Guglietta D., Ben Massoude M., El Ouad N., Mabika N.N. & Cirrincione R. - Neoproterozoic serpentinites from the Bou Azzer ophiolite (Central Anti-Atlas - Morocco): exploring the geodynamic changes and mantle processes beneath the boundaries of the West African Craton	940
Zibera L.*, Beltrame M., De Min A., McCammon C., Masotta M., Del Rio M., Narduzzi F., Černok A., Terranova K. & Venier M. - The continental Moho from a geobarometric perspective	941
S35. New frontiers of Planetary Geology	
Agrosi G.*, Manzari P., Mele D., Tempesta T., Rizzo F., Catelani T. & Bindi L. - A second AlCu-bearing micrometeorite from Monte Gariglione (Italy): insights on the origin and growth conditions	943
Agrosi G., Mele D.* & Manzari P. - Identification and characterization of Martian chips by non-destructive analyses	944
Agrosi G., Mele D. & Manzari P.* - A preliminary non-destructive characterization of Tarda meteorite	945
Baroni M.*, Baschetti B., Pisello A., Massironi M. & Petrelli M. - FRESCO, a Python open source tool to democratize CRISM spectral data management, analysis, and mapping	946
Bindi L.* - Are there more out there? The possible prevalence of quasicrystals in the Universe	947

Bokanda F., Cavalazzi B. & Franchi F.* - Geomicrobiology of the concretions of the Makgadikgadi pans (Botswana): an astrobiological perspective	948
Brunetti M.T.* & Peruccacci S. - Landslides on solid bodies in the Solar System	949
Caramanico A.*, Lanci L. & Francioni M. - Comparative studies on Martian landslides found in Craters of Noachian highlands: new perspectives for mass wasting phenomena	950
Cuppone T., Palomba E. & Pratesi G.* - Mineralogical analysis and preliminary physical property results on Didymos/Dimorphos meteorite analogues	951
D'Aniello M.*, Zampella M., Dosi A., Rownok A., Delli Veneri M., Ettari A., Cavuoti S., Sannino L., Brescia M., Donadio C. & Longo G. - Interplanetary river classification: a geomorphological approach utilizing subjective and objective analysis through advanced statistical methods	952
Ermini A.* & Salvini R. - Three-dimensional probabilistic slope stability analysis in lunar South Pole region	953
Fastelli M.*, Schmitt B., Beck P., Poch O., Zucchini A. & Comodi P. - Reflectance spectra of mascagnite and salammoniac minerals with varying viewing geometry	954
Landi A.I.*, Carli C., Capaccioni F. & Pratesi G. - Highly reduced meteorites: a comparison with Mercury's surface through mineralogical and spectroscopic investigation	955
Manzari P.*, Marzo C., Giunta A. & Petropoulou V. - Supporting the characterization of Atira surfaces with synthetic photometry of meteorites	956
Melchiori G.*, Pozzobon R., Massironi M. & Mazzarini F. - Structural analysis of wrinkle ridges in the region between Aristarchus plateau and Marius Hills in Oceanus Procellarum (Moon)	957
Pascucci V.*, Stelletti M., Sechi D., Cossu G. & Andreucci S. - Lanzarote as suitable Mars analogue to test if recent Mars deposits could be dated using luminescence	958
Permian G., Tagliacollo L.*, Bonadiman C., Nodari L., Brombin V. & Tassinari R. - Geochemical characteristics of a newly discovered Vigarano chondrite fragment (CV3) - Study of redox conditions with unconventional Mössbauer spectroscopy	959
Pisello A.*, Fastelli M., Baroni M., Schmitt B., Beck P., Zucchini A., Petrelli M., Comodi P. & Perugini D. - Reflectance spectra of synthetic Nakhilite rocks as lab-made analogues for Martian terrains: influence of mineralogy, glass content and acquisition geometry	960
Pondrelli M.*, Di Pietro I., Le Deit L., Marinangeli L., Pantaloni M. & Rossi A.P. - Geological map, depositional processes, environments, and evolution of the Eberswalde delta (Mars)	961
Pozzobon R.*, Rossi A.P., Massironi M., Marinangeli L., Pondrelli M., Carli C., Zambon F., van der Bogert C., Baschetti B., Penasa L., Frigeri A., Rossi C., Alemanno G., Chirico R., Heyer T., Lopez I., Stephan K. & Wagner R. - EUROPLANET GMAP: the geology and planetary mapping winter school	962
Pratesi G.* - Mankind cannot stay in the cradle forever. The Space It Up project	963
Shehaj X.*, Ammannito E. & Pratesi G. - "Chirfa" meteorite: the largest specimen from Mars	964
Tangari A.C.*, Marinangeli L., Scarciglia F., Pompilio L. & Piluso E. - Experimental alteration of volcanic bedrock: a terrestrial analogue for Mars	965
Verdecchia M.*, Pedone M., Tomasetti B., Manzari P., Lombardi A. & Colaiuda V. - Application of CHyM hydrological model on Mars surface: clues of drainage patterns on Jezero crater	966
S36. Challenges in the characterization of active faults: the contribution from seismology, geodesy, and structural analysis	
Bacchiani A.*, Ferranti L., Iezzi F. & Pavano F. - Structural setting and tectonic evolution of the Central Matese Fault System, Southern Apennines: preliminary observations	968
Bonini S.*, Asti R., Viola G., Tartaglia G., Rodani S., Benedetti G. & Vignaroli G. - Addressing fault structural complexity and geometric interference in seismic hazard assessment for railways design	969
Cardello G.L., Barreca G., Monaco C.*, De Michele M. & Antonioli F. - First comparison of instrumental European Ground Motion Service by Copernicus Data with short and long-term geological vertical movements for the Italian Coasts	970
Doglioni C.* - Fault activation energy	971

Esposito A., Pietrolungo F.*, Pezzo G., Govoni A., Soldati G., Inannarelli M., Terribili A., Chiarabba C. & Palano M. - The continuous GNSS network of Salina Island in the framework of CAVEAT project ...	972
Ferranti L.*, Bacchiani A., Brighenti F., Carnemolla F., De Guidi G., Giuffrida S., Iezzi F. & Palano M. - Geodetic velocity constraints on fault strain accumulation in southern Italy	973
Fonzetti R.*, Valoroso L., De Gori P., Govoni A. & Chiarabba C. - ML vs. semi-automatic seismic catalogs: a new catalog for the L'Aquila 2009 earthquake sequence	974
Giuffrida S.*, Anderlini L., Carnemolla F., Brighenti F., De Guidi G., Cannavò F., Graham S. & Monaco C. - Interseismic coupling degree along the Serre and Cittanova faults in Southern Calabria, (Italy): new constraints from geodetic data observations	975
Iezzi F.*, Bacchiani A., Ferranti L., Pavano F., Di Paola C., Pagliara F., Boni P. & Di Maio R. - Detailed geological and geophysical investigation of a segment of a major active normal fault: the Northern Matese Fault System	976
Madarieta-Txurruka A.*, Galindo-Zaldívar J., Pietrolungo F., Sparacino F., Ercilla G. & Palano M. - New geodetic 3D velocity field of Iberia and adjacent mountain ranges	977
Mele G.*, Battelli P., Castello B., Carluccio I., Ciaccio M.G., Della Bina E., Lauciani V., Di Stefano R., Nardi A., Maniscalco M., Marchetti A., Latorre D. & BSI Working Group - The new website of the Italian Seismic Bulletin (BSI): architecture and content	978
Mowbray V.*, Sue C., Beauval C., Lemoine A., Mathey M. & Baize S. - Integrating geophysical, structural and tectonic data in a probabilistic seismic hazard assessment (PSHA) for the South-East of France ..	979
Muluneh A.*, Brune S., Pagli C., La Rosa A., Keir D., Neuharth D. & Corti G. - Time-dependent rift connection between the Red Sea and Gulf of Aden rifts in central Afar	980
Occhipinti M.*, Lanari R., Carboni F. & Porreca M. - DInSAR coseismic surface deformation of the 2023 Mw 6.8 Al Haouz earthquake (High Atlas Mountains, Morocco)	981
Palano M.*, Billi A., Conti A., Cuffaro M., Orecchio B., Presti D., Scolaro S., Sparacino F. & Totaro C. - Geodetic and seismological constraints for the intra-orogenic normal Lakes Fault (Sila, Calabria, southern Italy)	982
Palano M.*, Parrino N., Madarieta-Txurruka A., Pietrolungo F., Sparacino F. & Sulli A. - Crustal deformation along the Dead Sea fault system	983
Perrucci F.* & de Lorenzo S. - A method for the determination of the orientation of fault plane from the analysis of seismograms in the time domain	984
Puliti I., Pizzi A.*, Gori S., Falcucci E., Galadini F., Moro M. & Saroli M. - Paleoseismological evidence of multiple, large magnitude earthquake surface ruptures on the active Mt. Morrone normal fault, central Apennines, Italy	985
Riva F.*, Marzorati S., Agostinetti N.P., Latorre D., Chiaraluce L. & Barchi M.R. - Integration of active and passive seismic data to investigate the relationships between seismicity and geological structures at the hanging-wall of the alto Tiberina fault (Northern Apennines of Italy)	986
Rossi F.*, Pucci S., Volpe G. & Collettini C. - The role of structural complexity in seismicity distribution: L'Aquila 2009 seismic sequence (Central Apennines, Italy)	987
Sparacino F.*, Galuzzi B.G., Palano M. & Azzaro R. - Analysis of the Seismic Coupling Coefficient for Italy: first results	988
Tavani S.*, Petracchini L., Billi A., Carminati E., Chiarabba C., Conti A., Devoti R., Palano M., Pezzo G., Scognamiglio L. & Tinti E. - Unraveling the dynamics of the active frontal sector of the Northern Apennine thrust belt: a multidisciplinary investigation following the 2022 Mw 5.5 Adriatic earthquake	989
S37. Carbonate platform systems: records of palaeoenvironmental change	991
Španiček J.* & Korbar T. - Open questions on the Likva locality K-Pg boundary bed on the Adriatic carbonate platform	992
Španiček J.*, Korbar T., Fuček L. & Steuber T. - Diversity of Early Cretaceous carbonate facies around the OAE1a on Adriatic carbonate platform	
Artegiani F.*, Cipollari P., Cosentino D., Rabiee A., Rossetti F., Cipriani A. & Fabbi S. - The record of the Early Cretaceous Oceanic Anoxic Events (OAE) in the Apennine carbonate platform: insight from the geological mapping of the Sheet 390 - Frosinone (CARG project)	993

Berra F.* - Soft-sediment deformation structures and Neptunian dykes across a carbonate system: Evidence for an earthquake-related origin (Norian, Dolomia Principale, Southern Alps, Italy)	994
Coccia N.*, Della Porta G., Berra F. & Marini M. - The drowning of the Trento Platform: facies characterization and depositional changes across the San Vigilio Oolite - Rosso Ammonitico Veronese transition (Lower-Middle Jurassic, Venetian Southern Alps, N Italy)	995
de Luca A.*, Lisco S., De Giosa F., Gimenez G.A., Pierri C., Acquafredda P., Corriero G. & Moretti M. - Unveiling the architecture and geological significance of mesophotic oyster reefs on the Apulian Continental Shelf: a multiscale approach	996
Della Porta G.*, Wright V.P., Samankassou E., Preto N. & Morsilli M. - Carbonate platforms: what can still be learned from outcrops?	997
Fracchiolla T.*, Lisco S., Ravisato M., Pierri C., de Luca A., D'Abbicco V., Lazic T., Acquafredda P. & Moretti M. - An unusual rhodolith bed as a record of human activities in Mar Piccolo (Taranto)	998
Gianolla P.*, Caggiati M., Alverà G., Dal Corso J., Riva A. & Aldrighetti E. - The Cassian Dolomite demise: basinal insights on the carbonate platforms' agony (Dolomites, Late Triassic)	999
Lippolis E.*, Spalluto L. & Tropeano M. - Facies analysis of a Cretaceous peritidal carbonate succession cropping out at Cava Porcili (Minervino Murge, southern Italy)	1000
Morabito C.* & Morsilli M. - The Eocene carbonate deposits of the Gargano Promontory and Tremiti Islands (southern Italy)	1001
Morsilli M.* - Unraveling the evolution of the Apulia Carbonate Platform and its sedimentary dynamics	1002
Passaseo C.* & Morsilli M. - Lower Messinian <i>Halimeda</i> bioherms from the Mediterranean area: new insights on the controlling factors	1003
Peng S.Y.*, Wu K., Shi Z.Q., Qiao D. & Wang M.L. - Marlstone pseudo-desiccation cracks: an enigmatic sedimentary structure in the Early Triassic Feixianguan Formation in South China	1004
Preto N.*, Caggiati M., Della Porta G., Franceschi M. & Morsilli M. - The record of paleoenvironmental change in Mesozoic carbonate platforms of Western Tethys: some half-baked ideas	1005
Randazzo V.*, Berra F., Todaro S. & Di Stefano P. - Diagenetic and tectonic history of the Upper Triassic, Dachstein-type margin of the Panormide Carbonate Platform (Sicily, Southern Italy)	1006
Santone S.*, Franceschi M., Franceschi P. & Rusciadelli G. - Exploring shallow-water carbonate precipitation rates through geological time	1007
Spalluto L.*, Petruzzelli M., Sabato L. & Tropeano M. - Cretaceous cyclic peritidal carbonates of the Apulia Carbonate Platform (Apulia, southern Italy) in a hierarchical sequence-stratigraphic perspective: a case study from the Murge area (the Giovinazzo sea-cliff section)	1008
Todaro S.*, Petrella F., Rigo M. & Sulli A. - The recovery of carbonate platforms after the End Triassic Mass Extinction: new data of a Lower Jurassic succession from south-western Sicily	1009
Vidi C.*, Roghi G., Preto N. & Breda A. - Response of a carbonate platform to the Cenomanian-Turonian Boundary Event: the Akrabou Formation of Southern Morocco	1010
S38. Frontiers in the regional geology of the Apennines: a multidisciplinary perspective	
Abbassi A.*, Cipollari P. & Cosentino D. - A new proposal for the stratigraphy of the "Tolfa unit" (CARG project, 364-Bracciano)	1012
Ambrosino M.*, Palarea-Albaladejo J., Albanese S. & Cicchella D. - The geochemical domains map of the Volturno river basin (South Italy): usefulness and comparison with the geological map	1013
Amore F.O.*, Argenio C., Di Vito M.A., Fistola R., La Rocca R.A., Messina M. Y., Panarello A., Rastelli A. & Zingariello I. - The paleontological heritage and innovative communication modalities for the territorial development	1014
Amore F.O., Argenio C., Faranda C., Ferraro L., Gliozzi E., Magri D., Michelangeli F., Russo B., Siciliano J., Vallefucio M., Mauro A., Meo A.* & Senatore M.R. - Multi-proxy analyses to reconstruct the environmental evolution through the composite section cropping out at San Giuliano Lake area (Matera, Southern Italy)	1015
Artoni A., Chizzini N.*, Basso J., Torelli L., Polonia A., Gasperini L. & Qadir A. - Oblique plate collision remnants of the Southern Apennines-Calabrian Arc boundary revealed in the offshore Bradano Basin (Ionian Sea - Central Mediterranean)	1016

Barbero E.*, Festa A., Saccani E. & Catanzariti R. - The redefinition of the Ligurian Units at the Alps-Apennines junction (NW Italy) and their role in the evolution of the Ligurian accretionary wedge	1017
Bellotti P.*, Barrera Acosta D., Stendardi F., Pezzoli S., Toscani G. & Di Giulio A. - Linking the exposed belt to the buried one: preliminary data and results in the framework of the project CARG 160 Pavia	1018
Bonfardeci A.*, Agate M., Gasparo Morticelli M., Incarbona A., Avellone G., Gennuso M., Rizzo G.F., Moscariello A., Muraro C., Bonomo R., Parrino N., Pucci S. & Sulli A. - Late Pliocene-Pleistocene stratigraphic evolution of the Menfi wedge-top basin (South-western Sicily - Italy)	1019
Brandano M.*, Raffi I., Mancini A. & Marianelli D. - The Oligo-Miocene Carbonate ramp succession of Maiella Mountain, the record of changing oceanographic conditions in the Central Mediterranean	1020
Brandano M.*, Cornacchia I., Catanzariti R., Mancini A. & Marianelli D. - Bioclastic intercalations in the Tortonian hemipelagic marls of the Latium-Abruzzi carbonate platform domain (Central Apennines): the link between oceanography and climate	1021
Brogi A.*, Liotta D. & Zucchi M. - Neogene evolution of the inner northern Apennines and the related geothermal systems: insights from the Elba Island	1022
Capezzuoli E.*, Spina A., Molli G., Brogi A., Liotta D., Zucchi M. & Degl'Innocenti N. - Chronostratigraphy of Palaeozoic formations by means of palynological studies: the case of the Filladi e Quarziti di Buti Formation (Northwestern Tuscany)	1023
Chizzini N.*, Artoni A., Torelli L., Quadir A., Polonia A. & Gasperini L. - Tectono-stratigraphic evolution of the Apulia plate and the role of the advancing Southern Apennine/Calabrian Arc wedge on its present-day structural and stratigraphic architecture	1024
Ciarcia S.* & Vitale S. - Orogenic evolution of the northern Calabria-southern Apennines System: stratigraphy	1025
Ciarcia S.*, Vitale S., Aiello G., Barra D., Di Donato V. & Morabito S. - Sedimentary evolution of the Pliocene wedge-top basins in the southern Apennines: a review	1026
Commis L.*, Barbagallo V., Brandano M., Cornacchia I., Distefano S., Mancini A., Marianelli D., Salerno A., Tortorici G., Di Stefano A. & Catalano S. - The impact of an integrated stratigraphic and structural analysis on the updating of the regional tectonic scheme: an example from the Hyblean Plateau (SE Sicily)	1027
Consorti L.*, Cardello G.L., D'Onofrio R. & Garzarella A. - New biostratigraphic data on the hemipelagic succession at the western escarpment of the Apennine Carbonate Platform: insights from the Volsci Range	1028
Corrado G.*, Gioia D., Minervino Amodio A. & Schiattarella M. - New morphotectonic and stratigraphic data on the Quaternary evolution of the Vallo di Diano basin, southern Italy	1029
Cosentino D.*, Mondati G., Giaccio B., Deino A., Arcangeli P., Bertini A., Huang H., Nocentini M., Iorio M., Angelino A., Cifelli F., Mattei M., Sagnotti L., Gliozzi E., Marchegiano M., Petrelli M., Peral M., Claeys P., Regattieri E., Zanchetta G., Spadi M., Tallini M., Conte A.M., Conticelli S. & Casalini M. - Constraining the early stage of the post-orogenic extensional tectonics in central Italy: new evidence from a long sediment core from the tectonically active L'Aquila basin (Central Italy)	1030
Degl'Innocenti N.*, Spina A., Capezzuoli E., Brogi A., Liotta D. & Zucchi M. - Microfloristic evidence in metamorphosed rocks of Elba Island: new constraints and correlation of the early Palaeozoic	1031
Fabozzi C.* - pH soil measurements of the Sant'Antuono CO ₂ gas vent in the Sannio area (southern Apennines, Italy): insights on the active Southern Matese Fault system	1032
Fabozzi C.*, Albanese S., Ambrosino M., Cicchella D., De Paola C., Di Giuseppe M.G., Isaia R., Natale J., Pagliara F., Prinzi E.P., Troiano A., Ciarcia S. & Vitale S. - New data about Irpinian mud volcanoes: a multidisciplinary approach to understanding the relationship between fluid leakage and faults	1033
Gambino S.*, Conigliello E., Monaco C. & Barreca G. - 3D Structural architecture of the front of the Sicilian Apennine (Southern Italy) as derived from well-calibrated seismic reflection profiles interpretation ..	1034
Gori F., Barberio M.D., Barbieri M., Boschetti T., Cardello G.L.*, Damato A. & Petitta M. - Groundwater-rock interaction and mixing in fault-controlled karstic aquifers: a structural, hydrogeochemical and multi-isotopic review of the Pontina Plain (Central Italy)	1035
Iorio M., Meo A.*, Aiello G. & Senatore M.R. - Seismo-stratigraphy architecture of the transgressive and highstand systems tracts during the Last Glacial-Holocene and the NYT reflector in the Gulf of Gaeta (Eastern Tyrrhenian margin, Italy)	1036

Mainini A. *, Conti S. & Serventi P. - Alternative origin for the Middle Miocene mass transport deposits of the Marnoso Arenacea Formation	1037
Massa B., Famiglietti N.A. *, Memmolo A. & Miele P. - Use of low-frequency GPR to refine stratigraphy and tectonics in the Ofanto River Valley (Southern Apennines)	1038
Pasqualone L. *, Brozzetti F., Luchetti L., Tangari A.C., Barchi M.R. & Mirabella F. - Development of a foredeep basin in the Northern Apennines through a multidisciplinary approach: the example of the Miocene Marnoso-arenacea fm. (Umbria, Italy)	1039
Pedini M. *, Cella F., Mazzoli S., Pierantoni P.P. & Di Celma C. - 3D Structural model of the Messinian Umbria-Marche Foredeep basin: insights from the Ascoli Piceno sector, southern Marche (Italy)	1040
Pizzati V. * & Tinterri R. - Turbidite lobe deposits in a tectonically confined foredeep basin (Firenzuola turbidite system, Marnoso-arenacea Formation, Northern Apennines, Italy)	1041
Qadir A. *, Maiorana M., Chizzini N., Artoni A., Torelli L., Le Breton E. & Sulli A. - New insights into the structural setting of North-Western offshore Sicily, Central Mediterranean	1042
Remitti F. *, Festa A., Nirta G., Barbero E. & Mitterpergher S. - The External Ligurian Units of the Northern Apennines: a glimpse in the deformation of shallow accretionary prisms and implications for seismicity	1043
Santoro V.P. *, Brozzetti F. & Cirillo D. - Tectono-Stratigraphic setting of the Abruzzo Sub-Apennines along the Colledara-Montefino transect (Abruzzo-Italy)	1044
Spina A., Brogi A. *, Capezzuoli E., Caggianelli A., Zucchi M., Langone A., Tursi F., Chinedu I. & Liotta D. - The Palaeozoic succession of the Giglio Island (Tuscan Archipelago)	1045
Vitale S. * & Ciarcia S. - Orogenic evolution of the northern Calabria-southern Apennines System: Tectonics	1046
Vitale S. *, Di Giuseppe M.G., Ciarcia S., Albanese S., Isaia R., Cicchella D., Troiano A., Iezzi F., Natale J., Fabozzi C., Ambrosino M. & De Paola C. - Multidisciplinary study of non-volcanic CO ₂ degassing vents in Oliveto Citra area (southern Apennines)	1047
S39. Open session on Stratigraphy and Sedimentology	
Abbassi A. *, Cipollari P., Zaghoul M.N. & Cosentino D. - The mesorif unconformity in the external rif (Morocco): new insights from stratigraphical and biostratigraphical constraints	1049
Addante M. *, Maiorano P., Girone A., Herbert T., Marino M., Scopelliti G. & Caruso A. - Improving climatostratigraphic signals at the Gelasian GSSP type-section	1050
Agate M. *, Todaro S., Maiorana M.G., Caldareri F., Lombardo C., Severini A. & Sulli A. - Seismo-stratigraphic analysis of middle-late Quaternary shelf margin prograding deposits in the Western Sicily offshore (central Mediterranean Sea)	1051
Caggiati M. *, Gianolla P., Riva A., Alverà G. & Aldrighetti E. - The stratigraphic signature of the Carnian Pluvial Episode in the northern Greater Adria	1052
Cipriani A., Consorti L. *, Fabbi S., Barattolo F. & Pampaloni M.L. - Ratifying the upper Campanian to Paleogene shallow-water carbonate unit to fill a lithostratigraphic “gap” within the Apennine Carbonate Platform succession	1053
Di Stefano A. *, Foresi L.M., Lirer F., Barbagallo V., Catania G., Cacho Lascor I., D’Andrea N.M., Cornacchia I., Sagnotti L., Raffi I., Turco E. & Hilgen F.J. - A potential Mediterranean reference section for the GSSP of the Burdigalian Stage: St. Thomas section (Delimara Peninsula, Malta Island)	1054
Distefano S. *, Di Stefano A. & Gamberi F. - Deltaic processes and depositional canyon-heads in a narrow continental shelf: examples from the north-eastern Sicilian margin	1055
Ezeh S.C. *, Bhattacharya J.P., Dellapenna T.M. & Carlin J.A. - Sediment distribution in the Brazos Delta: Estimation and numerical modelling of sedimentation rates and the effect of bioturbation in event beds preservation	1056
Gaspari R. *, Rusciadelli G., Ricci C. & Cestari R. - The Orfento formation of the Maiella Mountain (Central Apennines, Italy): depositional facies model of an Upper Cretaceous bioclastic wedge	1057
Lauria A. *, Longhitano S.G., Sabato L. & Tropeano M. - Stratigraphic patterns of shelf-type deltas in the Lower Pleistocene of the Sant’Arcangelo Basin, Basilicata, southern Italy	1058
Longhitano S.G. * - Deflected deltas: what are they?	1059

Mancini A.*, Brandano M. & Ferràndez-Cañadell C. - Coralgial buildup in a mixed carbonate-siliciclastic succession of the Upper Eocene San Martí Xic Formation (Oris, Vic, SE Ebro basin, Spain)	1060
Mancini A., Brandano M., Cardello G.L. & Ronca S.* - Vertebrate pits recorded in carbonate sedimentary succession: the case study of the Pliocene Macco formation (Tarquinia - Central Italy)	1061
Martella A.*, Sarti G. & Baneschi I. - Environmental and human control factors on the Holocene evolution of Venice lagoon: sedimentological and geochemical approach	1062
Pellegrini C.*, Sammartino I., Schieber J., Tesi T., Paladini de Mendoza F., Rossi V., Chiggiato J., Schroeder K., Gallerani A., Langone L., Trincardi F. & Amorosi A. - On depositional processes governing along-strike facies variations of fine-grained subaqueous deltas in the Adriatic Sea	1063
Putrino N.*, Cardillo G., Brindisi A., Carfagna N. & Albarello D. - Advanced seismic microzonation in correspondence of deep sedimentary basins: the case of Foggia (Southern Italy)	1064
Salvador C.*, Fanti F. & Catuneanu O. - Depositional architecture and provenance analysis of the non-marine deposits of the Oldman Formation (Campanian, Belly River Group) at the U.S.-Canada border	1065
Sarti G.*, Capitani M., Cascella A., Collareta A., Da Prato S., Nocentini M., Pappalardo M., Ragaini L., Baneschi I., Casati S., Bertoni D., Bosio G., Martella A., Merella M. & Sacchelli T. - Multi-proxy investigation of Pliocene transgressive-regressive high-frequency cycles in Geological Sheet 274 Empoli (Tuscany, Italy): insights from the CARG Project	1066
Spina A.*, Rettori G., Cirilli S., Mansour G. & Rettori R. - How did the plant ecosystem adapt to climatic variations (shifts) during the middle to the late Permian? A case study from Northern Gondwana	1067
Spina A.*, Yilmaz I.O., Capezzuoli E., Cirilli S. & Bengul N. - The end-Guadalupian anoxic event in Northern Anatolia: new constrains and correlation through palynological data	1068
Spina A., Capezzuoli E., Gretter N., Marchetti L., Corradini C., Degl'Innocenti N., Scarani R.* & Ronchi A. - Onset of the Permian 2 nd tectono-sedimentary cycle from the Southern Alps: new constraints from palynological assemblages and regional-global inferences	1069
Zanola E.*, Bonomo S., Ferretti P., Fornaciari E., Incarbona A., Rodrigues T. & Capraro L. - High-resolution multi proxy records across the Plio-Pleistocene boundary: a central Mediterranean perspective	1070
S40. Source-to-sink processes and genesis of resources in sedimentary deposits: advances in understanding of geologic and environmental dynamics through a multidisciplinary perspective	
Alvisi F.* - The disappearance of sand: just a false alarm or a global emergency?	1072
Amato V., Ebrahimi P., Matano F.*, Mattera R. & Scepi G. - Using a large dataset of field-based measurements to statistically estimate thickness of fallout pyroclastic deposits in the peri-volcanic areas of Campania region, southern Italy	1073
Andò S.*, Barbarano M., Caruso P., Gambarotta O., Garzanti E., Limonta M., Malusà M., Paglia S., Pastore G., Resentini A. & Vezzoli G. - From the micro to the macro-scale: the contribution of the "Provenance Centre" (Unimib) in the study of sedimentary archives	1074
Civitelli M.*, Critelli S. & Ingersoll R.V. - Diagenetic and hydrothermal changes in submarine quartzofeldspathic turbidite sandstones of the Butano Sandstone, central California, USA	1075
Criniti S.* & Costamagna L.G. - Detrital modes of the Pennsylvanian-Permian sandstones in Central-Eastern Sardinia (Italy)	1076
Criniti S.* & Martín-Martín M. - Detrital modes of the Culm facies in the Betic-Rifean chain	1077
De Cesare P.* & Scarciglia F. - Integrated study of erosion rates using cosmogenic and fallout radionuclides (¹⁰ Be and ²³⁹⁺²⁴⁰ Pu) in a pilot stream catchment of Calabria, southern Italy	1078
de Luca A.*, Lisco S., Fracchiolla T., D'Abbicco V., Trani R., Ravisato M., Lazic T. & Moretti M. - Sedimentological features of sandy sediments trapped in Sabellarian Bioconstructions along the Apulian Coastline (Southern Italy)	1079
Dimuccio L.A.*, Pratas J., Ribeiro J., Rodrigues N., Cunha L., Micheletti F. & Acquafredda P. - Integrated paleoenvironmental multi-proxy analysis of Late Quaternary fluvial sediments in the Cõa Valley (northeast Portugal)	1080
Fornelli A.*, Micheletti F., Acquafredda P. & Mangone A. - Crystallization of Mn-hydroxides for interaction between limestones and clay minerals in the Apulian karst (southern Italy)	1081

Gallicchio S.*, Fornelli A., Maiorano P., Fanelli G. & Micheletti F. - Late Paleogene syn-sedimentary volcanoclastic deep-sea succession of the Candela Gorges (Southern Italy). New constrains for the evolution of the Southern Apennines	1082
Kairouani H., Abbassi A., Zaghoul M.N., El Mourabet M., Fornelli A., Mongelli G., Critelli S. & Micheletti F.* - The Jurassic climate change in the northwest Gondwana (External Rif, Morocco): A probable control of successive mega-monsoons through the African Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone	1083
Kairouani H., Micheletti F.*, Borrelli M., Perri E., Zaghoul M.N. & Fornelli A. - Early Jurassic phosphatic sandstones (External Rif, Northern Morocco): evidence of mineralogical and biogeochemical processes related to the Early Toarcian Oceanic Anoxic Event	1084
Le Pera E.*, Dutta A. & Riber L. - (Paleo)weathering or diagenesis as the principal control factor of sand(stone) framework grains dissolution?	1085
Pavano F.*, Pazzaglia F.J., Barnes L., Rittenour T.M., Catalano S., Corbett L.B. & Bierman P. - Tectonic forcing encoding in the geomorphic and stratigraphic records of a tight source-to-sink system (Northeastern Sicily, Italy)	1086
Pugliese E.*, Tangari A.C. & Le Pera E. - Heavy Minerals analysis of fluvial sand in the Crati River (Northern Calabria)	1087
Scarciglia F.* - Weathering and erosion rates at different timescales in a granitic area of the Mediterranean (Sila Massif, Calabria, southern Italy): an overview on recent advances	1088
Tangari A.C.*, Le Pera E., Andò S., Garzanti E., Piluso E., Marinangeli L. & Scarciglia F. - Weathering processes and soil formation in Sila Massif and Catena Costiera (Calabria, southern Italy): Insight from heavy minerals	1089
S41. The evolution of sedimentary basins: from source to complex basin architecture	
Abbassi A., Cipollari P.*, Rabiee A., Rossetti F. & Cosentino D. - The Upper Cretaceous Pietraforte formation (Monti della Tolfa, Northern Latium, Italy) in a source-to-sink perspective	1091
Ballato P.*, Brune S. & Strecker M.R. - Linking sedimentary loading-unloading cycles and faulting in intermontane basins of the broken foreland of NW Argentine Andes: new prospective from numerical modeling and field observations	1092
Barbagallo V. *, Brandano M., Borzi L., Catania G., Cornacchia I., Distefano S., Pellegrino A., Macri P., Mancini A., Marianelli D., Maniscalco R. & Di Stefano A. - Integrated stratigraphy reveals Oligo-Miocene paleoclimatic phases: a Central Mediterranean insight from the western Hyblean sedimentary succession	1093
Bellinvia L., Gasparrini M., Montano D.*, Mangenot X., Berra F., Decarlis A. & Ceriani A. - Diagenesis and paleo-fluid characterization of the Bathonian-Callovian platform carbonates from the southern Paris Basin sub-surface	1094
Catto B.*, Muzzi Magalhães P. & Tinterri R. - Control of the synsedimentary tectonics on turbidite channels dynamics: an integrated study between field and subsurface data	1095
Cerone D.*, Notaro A. & Prosser G. - Detailed field mapping and revised litho-biostratigraphy of the Castelvete Formation cropping out at the NW Campania-Basilicata border (Southern Apennines, Southern Italy)	1096
Cerone D., Gallicchio S.*, Patacci M. & Tinterri R. - Turbidite systems in tectonically-confined foredeep and trench-slope basins: a comparison between Serra Palazzo Fm. and tufti delle Gole Candela succession (Lucanian Apennines, Italy)	1097
Critelli S.* - Assembling and dismantling the supercontinent Pangaea recorded from provenance relations of Phanerozoic sandstones of the circum-Mediterranean Region	1098
Fabbi S.* & Cipriani A. - Tectonic activity recorded by deep basin deposits: a sedimentological approach to unravel synsedimentary tectonics	1099
Kim D.*, Relvini A., Forzese M., Parente M., Iannace A., Punturo R., Maniscalco R. & Ogata K. - Introducing TOOLS: climatic-tectonic modulation in the Langhian-Tortonian “megaturbidites” of the S. Mauro Formation (Cilento Group, Southern Apennines)	1100
Mangenot X., Gasparrini M.*, Bonifacie M., Rouchon V., Deschamps P. & Ceriani A. - Low-temperature $\Delta 47/(U-Pb)$ carbonate thermochronology reveals the exhumation history of the Paris Basin southern margin	1101

Maniscalco R.*, Nadudvari A., Forzese M., Barbagallo V., Distefano S., Giustolisi C., Pellegrino A.G. & Di Stefano A. - Correlation of biomarker, foraminiferal and nannofossil records to unravel past environments: new insight from pre-evaporitic Torrente Vaccarizzo section (Sicily)	1102
Marini M., Patacci M.*, Cifelli F., Cipollari P., Mattei M. & Muttoni G. - Magnetostratigraphy and calcareous nannofossil biostratigraphy of upper Eocene turbidites (Ventimiglia Flysch Fm) from the western Alps foreland basin	1103
Micheletti F.*, Fornelli A., Gallicchio S., Tursi F., Criniti S. & Critelli S. - Petrographic and geochronological records from turbidite successions of the Lucanian external chain: new insights for the tectono-sedimentary evolution of the Southern Apennines, Italy	1104
Montano D.*, Gasparini M., Vergara Sassarini N.A., Michel P., Teles V., Corrado S., Lasseur E., Berra F., Decarlis A. & Ceriani A. - Paleo-fluid characterization of the Upper Triassic siliciclastic reservoirs from the Paris Basin depocenter (France)	1105
Moretto V.*, Del Sole L., Curzi M., Dallai L., Vignaroli G., Viola G. & Aldega L. - Paleothermal indicators and H, O stable isotopes for constraining temperature and fluid evolutionary models of complex fault zones: a new approach	1106
Patacci M.* & Marini M. - The stratigraphic record of the Ventimiglia Flysch Fm, north-west Italy (western Alps foreland basin, Grès d'Annot turbidite system)	1107
Stendardi F.*, Viola G., Carrapa B. & Vignaroli G. - Oligocene-Miocene exhumation history of the Epiligurian wedge-top basins (Northern Apennines) constrained by low-temperature thermochronology	1108
Tinterri R.*, Lima D.F. & Civa A. - Low efficiency turbidite systems controlled by the geometry of structurally-confined mini-basins (Valla and Fraschetto Systems, Oligocene, Tertiary Piedmont Basin, NW Italy)	1109
Weert A., Vinci F., Ogata K. & Tavani S.* - Unlocking geothermal potential: syn-rift fluvial deposits in the West Netherlands Basin	1110
Zuffetti C.*, Felletti F. & Marini M. - Architecture of migrating channel belts in a foreland basin: insights from the Tortonian Tachrift turbidite system, Taza-Guercif basin, NE Morocco	1111

S42. Geophysics for Tectonics and Energy Resources

Amoroso O., Giampaolo V.*, Baccaro A., Balasco M., Blasone M., Bubbico D., Capuano P., De Martino G., Gargiulo M.V., Napolitano F., Perrone A., Panebianco S., Russo R., Serlenga V. & Stabile T.A. - A multi-messenger geophysical approach for geothermal resource evaluation and sustainable energy exploitation: two case studies in Southern Italy	1113
Biondini E.*, D'Orazio F., Lolli B. & Gasperini P. - Comparative analysis of alarm-based earthquake forecasting models in Italy	1114
De Luca M.*, Mancinelli P., Patruno S. & Scisciani V. - Exploring the Greater East Shetland Platform (Northern North Sea, UK): integration and modelling of wellbore, seismic, gravity and magnetic data to evaluate its storage potential	1115
Ferreri A.*, Romeo A., Giannuzzi R., Cecere G., Falco L., Filippucci M., Michele M., Serlenga V., Panebianco S., Stabile T., Selvaggi G. & Tallarico A. - OTRIONS seismic network during ten years of analyses: the new microseismicity catalog of the Gargano area (Southern Italy)	1116
Gasperini P.* & Lolli B. - A comparison between moment magnitude scales	1117
Kashi R.*, Balasco M., De Girolamo M., Graziano M., Improta L., Patella D., Pigniatello G., Siniscalchi A., Tripaldi S., Ventola I., Villani F. & Romano G. - New insights on the deep electrical structure of the Molise-Sannio region: preliminary outcomes of a Magnetotelluric survey	1118
Lavecchia A.*, Serlenga V., Filippucci M., Stabile T.A., Prosser G. & Tallarico A. - Fault (re)activation and fluid-induced seismicity: an example from the Val d'Agri intermontane basin (Southern Italy)	1119
Lolli B.*, Vannucci G. & Gasperini P. - What is in the INGV ISIDe online database before 16 April 2005? ..	1120
Maffucci R.*, Pascazio A., Vico G., Bonamico A., Corrado S., Giordano G. & Bigi S. - Elaboration of new regional temperature-at-depth maps, aiding in the assessment of the geothermal potential in the Southern Latium	1121
Napolitano F.*, Amoroso O., De Siena L., Convertito V., De Matteis R., La Rocca M., De Novellis V. & Capuano P. - Multidisciplinary study to characterize seismic gap crustal properties	1122

Pedini M.*, Cella F., Invernizzi C., Mazzoli S., Viramonte J.G. & Filipovich R. - New insights in Andean geothermal exploration: preliminary results from the Tocomar geothermal system case study (Puna, Argentina)	1123
Pignatiello G.*, Coco I., De Girolamo M., Di Persio M., Giannattasio F., Gizzi C., Materni V., Miconi L., Miconi M., Piangiamore G.M., Romano G., Romano V., Santarelli L., Sapia V., Spadoni S., Tozzi R., Tripaldi S., Siniscalchi A., De Michelis P. & Balasco M. - Geoelectromagnetic map for central Italy: preliminary results of the MARGE project	1124
Romeo A.*, Cecere G., Filippucci M., Selvaggi G. & Tallarico A. - GNSS CORS network of the University of Bari: an open infrastructure for research and educational	1125
Tesauro M.*, Cortassa V., Gola G., Galgaro A. & Manzella A. - New insights from analyses of geophysical data in the Northern Apennine buried structures for evaluation of their geothermal potential	1126
Tinivella U.*, Giustiniani M., Castellani B., Giovannetti R., Zannotti M., Nicolini A. & Rossi F. - Reliable long-term CO ₂ storage as clathrate hydrates in seawater and marine sediments: the CO ₂ -RESTO project	1127
Ventola I.* - Seismic-electromagnetic effect in the Pollino area: measurements, analysis and numerical modelling	1128
 S43. Groundwater resources innovation and sustainability: from characterisation to management of saturated and unsaturated zone	
Agius B. & Mamo J.* - Characterising rainfall-runoff processes and recharge rates in Mediterranean ephemeral streams with small impoundment dams	1130
Arras C., Calia M.*, Biddau R., Murgia A. & Da Pelo S. - Evaluation of recharge sources and nitrates origin in a karst spring: a case study from the F.na Nurighe spring (NW Sardinia, Italy)	1131
Brigida S.*, De Giglio O., Bagordo F., Grassi T., De Carlo L., Savino A.F., Turturro A.C., Montagna M.T. & Caputo M.C. - Review of laboratory-scale studies to assess factors affecting the fate of microorganisms in porous media	1132
Caputo M.C., De Carlo L., Doveri M., Giamberini M.S., Giordano R., Masciale R., Menichini M., Portoghese I.*, Turturro A.C. & Passarella G. - Integrated assessment of climate impacts on ecosystem functions and productivity of critical-zone eco-hydrology: the Italian case study of the INTERACTION project	1133
De Giglio O., Savino A.F.*, Bagordo F., Grassi T., Brigida S., Triggiano F., Apollonio F., Colella D., Turturro A.C., De Carlo L., Caputo M.C. & Montagna M.T. - Column test to study the influence of lithological characteristics of rocks on the hygienic-sanitary quality of groundwater	1134
Di Giovanni A.*, Di Curzio D. & Rusi S. - High-altitude minor springs in Central Italy tapped for drinking supply: hydrogeological characterization and aquifer potentialities evaluation	1135
Franceschi L.*, Menichini M., Parisi A., Gianecchini R. & Doveri M. - The effect of rainfall extreme events in the unsaturated and saturated zone: the case study of Pianosa Island (Tuscan Archipelago, Italy) ...	1136
Fuoco I.*, Criscuoli A., Vespasiano G., Bloise A., De Rosa R., Apollaro C. & Figoli A. - From geochemistry to treatment: a multidisciplinary study for reuse of safe natural waters	1137
Lapadula S., Balestra V.*, Barzagli B., Falaschi M., Ficotola G.F. & Manenti R. - Rhythmic response of cave animals to external cycles	1138
Lobina F.*, Da Pelo S., Biddau R., Coppola A., Vacca A., Hassan M.B.S., Arras C. & Porru C. - Evaluation of nitrate leaching processes during infiltration and transport in the unsaturated zone	1139
Mainini A.*, Sabattini M., Critelli V., Arosio D., Brozzo G., Panzani A., Droghieri E., Righetti S. & Ronchetti F. - River Magra aquifer system groundwater flow model, for correct water management in the perspective of climate change (Liguria Region, Italy)	1140
Parisi A.*, Di Gregorio S. & Gentini A. - BIOflushing technology for in situ applications of the Soil-Omic protocol. Operational scale prototype of a plant for the decontamination of soil in the saturated and unsaturated zone	1141
Parisi A.*, Doveri M., Franceschi L., Baneschi I., Provenzale P., Raco B. & Menichini M. - Hydrological processes in the aquifer system unsaturated zone: insights from the small Mediterranean island of Pianosa (Tuscan Archipelago)	1142

Peruzzo L.* , De Carlo L., Caputo M.C. & Cassiani G. - ERT characterization of treated water pathways from large infiltration trenches in unsaturated fractured/karstified calcarenite	1143
Peruzzo L.* , Werban U., Pohle M., Cassiani G., Consoli S. & Vanella D. - EMI and ERT characterization of plant-scale irrigation and ET: an orange orchard-case study and methodological challenges	1144
Piscedda F.A.* , Wanty R., Arras C., Porru M.C., Biddau R., Musu F., Podda F. & Da Pelo S. - Assessing surface water-groundwater exchange dynamics for managed aquifer recharge design: a case study in Muravera, Southeastern Sardinia, Italy	1145
Porru M.C.* , Davids T., Arras C., Oude Essink G.H.P., Piscedda F.A. & Da Pelo S. - Methodological approach to simulate the evolution seawater intrusion with climate change	1146
Surian B.* , Forte E. & Zini L. - Monitoring saltwater intrusion in the area surrounding the Grado lagoon (NE Italy)	1147
Taddia G.* , Gizzi M., Berta A. & Lo Russo S. - Renewable energy application: sustainability techniques in Torino Urban City	1148
Tiwari S., Saviano S. & Polemio M.* - An integrated numerical modelling approach to the management of a coastal plain aquifer (Southern Italy)	1149
Torres D., Zambrano M.* & Baena J.G. - Use of GPR imaging for early detection of water leaks in pipelines	1150
Turturro A.C.* , De Carlo L. & Caputo M.C. - Integrated experimental approach for supporting the planning of a Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) plantIntegrated experimental approach for supporting the planning of a Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) plant	1151
Verani M.* , Caputo M.C., Cassiani G., De Giglio O., Milani M., Carducci A., Federigi I., Pagani A., Angori A., De Carlo L., Turturro A.C., Prigiobbe V., Triggiano F., Savino A.F., Bagordo F., De Donno M.A., Grassi T., Brigida S., Consoli S., D'Emilio A., Barresi S., Bivona F. & Montagna M.T. - Predictive dynamics of microbiological contamination of groundwater in the earth critical zone and impact on human health: the DY.MI.CR.ON Project	1152
Volpe A.* , De Carlo L., Masciale R. & Caputo M.C. - Groundwater - lake interaction in a mediterranean coastal aquifer: the Alimini lake case study (Southern Italy)	1153
S44. New concepts and applications in exploration, sustainable exploitation, storage and modelling of georesources	
Anderlini L.* , Anselmi M., Braun T., Errico M., Garcia A., Morelli A., Pezzo G., Saccorotti G., Serpelloni E. & Zaccarelli L. - What we learned from geodetic monitoring of subsurface industrial activities	1155
Chiozzi P., Bonorino L. & Verdoya M.* - Lithosphere heat flow and subsidence of the Tyrrhenian back-arc basin	1156
De Luca M.* , Mackay E.J., Good T.R., Scisciani V., MacBeth C. & Patruno S. - Geological modelling and CO ₂ flow simulation: an integrated approach for basin scale storage in a saline aquifer	1157
Dinani P.* , Bigi S., Conti A. & Moallemi A. - Carbon sequestration potential of abandoned fractured reservoirs in Northwest Zagros, Iran	1158
Fagiani A., Antoncicchi I.* , Corneli D., Sofia R. & Sterpa S. - National energy policy: a focus on georesources targets at 2050	1159
Galione M.R.* , Criscuolo L., Manzella A. & Trumpy E. - Enhancing the Italian geothermal data infrastructure: integrating geothermal data and potential assessment tools	1160
Giorgetti C.* , Scuderi M.M., Bourgeois F., Wibberley C. & Collettini C. - Evolution of hydromechanical coupling from quartz to shale rich faults and implications for fault parallel vs. fault perpendicular permeability	1161
Lorenzet R., Corradetti A., Del Ben A., Franceschi M. & Bonini L.* - A potential site to store Hydrogen in the subsurface in Northeast Italy	1162
Loreto M.F.* & Exp. Science Party - Sealing potential of the messiniaN SALT from IODP Expedition 402 .	1163
Maiorana M.* , Rizzo G.F., Todaro S., Gasparo Morticelli M., Agate M. & Sulli A. - Linking an outcrop analogue to a deep potential CO ₂ storage site with 3D geological model: an example from southwestern Sicily	1164

Marchesini B.*, Pozzi G., Collettini C., Carminati E. & Tesei T. - Caprock genesis in hydrothermal systems via alteration-controlled fault weakening and impermeabilization	1165
Marchesini B.*, Rossetti F., Ruggieri G., Cavallo A., Moretto V., Castorina F., Trippetta F., Aldega L., Novella D., Caracausi A., Billi A. & Carminati E. - Alteration-controlled repeated breakage of hydrothermally altered marly-limestones seals, Fenice-Capanne mining area (Tuscany, Italy)	1166
Mattioni L.*, Armitage J., Christ A.-B., Granjeon D., Lemgruber-Traby A., Pujol A. & Bourgeois F. - Why it is important to perform a fully integrated basin-scale modeling of CO ₂ storage in saline aquifers? Insights from the Paris Basin (France)	1167
Morelli A.*, Saccorotti G., Anderlini L., Anselmi M., Braun T., Caciagli M., Carannante S., Errico M., Famiani D., Garcia A., Molinari I., Salimbeni S., Vassallo M., Zaccarelli L. & Zerbinato P. - CMS@INGV: An operational monitoring center for risk mitigation related to anthropic underground operations in Italy	1168
Nanni T.*, Chiozzi P., Miola M., Verdoya M. & Vetuschi Zuccolini M. - Stochastic and thermophysical modelling for geothermal resource assessment: the case of the Po Basin	1169
Pierozzi A.*, Rateau R., Orlando A., Borrini D., Tassi F. & Rodriguez Blanco J.D. - A mineralogical and geochemical approach to evaluate the redox capacity of basaltic glass and crystals via experiments ...	1170
Ridolfi R.M.*, Azzaro S., Beaubien S.E., Da Pra A., Pontiggia M. & Bigi S. - Development of a site-screening method for hydrogen storage purposes and its application to an industrial dataset of Italian reservoirs	1171
Romano M.A.*, Bernardi P., Diez E., Franceschinell F., Garbin M., Guidarelli M., Klin P., Laurenzano G., Magrin A., Moratto L., Peruzza L., Pettenati F., Plasencia M., Priolo E., Rebez A., Romanelli M., Sandron D., Santulin M., Saraò A., Tamaro A., Tunini L., Zuliani D., Bonano M., De Luca C., Lanari R. & Zinno I. - Seismic and geodetic monitoring of two underground gas storages in Northern Italy .	1172
Ruospo D.*, Brogi A., Liotta D., Lucci F. & Zucchi M. - Syn-tectonic emplacement of late-magmatic granitic dyke swarms in the Capo Focardo area (Exhumed geothermal system of eastern Elba island, Italy) ...	1173
Salvadori M.*, Pennisi M., D'Orazio M. & Dini A. - Potential sources of Li-rich fluids in Northern Apennines (Italy): first results on lithium distribution in pelitic rocks	1174
Semprebello A.*, Lazzaro G., Caruso C., Scirè Scappuzzo S., Morici S., Gattuso A. & Longo M. - Inverse modelling for estimating gas flow emission rate on stationary vents	1175
Summino L.*, Giorno M., Barale L., Bertok C., Frenzel M., Gasparri M. & Martire L. - Gorno and Piani Resinelli: genesis and correlations of two Alpine-type Pb-Zn districts	1176
Tommasone M.A.*, Di Domenico G., Bortolotti V., Cruciani G., Chiarella D., Nagmutdinova A. & Frijia G. - Characterization of dual porosity in bioturbated carbonates: A case study of Cenomanian-Turonian platform carbonates from the Southern Apennines (Italy)	1177
Urso S.* & Viccaro M. - New paradigms for an energetic independence and sustainable development of minor volcanic islands in Sicily: opportunities from the geothermal resources	1178
Vespasiano G.*, Floridia G., De Rosa R., Viccaro M., Cacace M., Bloise A., Fuoco I., Muto F., Guido A., Cipriani M., Maruca G. & Apollaro C. - 3D lithospheric thermal model of the Calabria region (Southern Italy): a supporting tool for new exploration campaigns for geothermal resources	1179
Vidal-Reyes M.*, Tesauro M., Amadori C., Nader F., Marini M., Reguzzi S. & Maino M. - Geothermal potential of the Tertiary Piedmont Basin: structural and lithological controls	1180
Yakisik O.*, Geloni C., Tamburelli S., Ruggieri G., Orlando A., Borrini D., Gherardi F. & Toscani G. - Laboratory experiments and geochemical models for CO ₂ mineralization in basalts	1181
Zucchi M., Brogi A., Liotta D., Fregola R.A., Caggianelli A., Ventruti G., Avanzinelli R. & Ruggieri G.* - Tracing the palaeo-circulation of geothermal fluids in the shallow crust exposed in the eastern Elba Island (Tuscany, Italy)	1182
S45. Recent advances in karst research, with particular focus on underground waters	
D'Ettoire U.S.*, Liso I.S. & Parise M. - Desertification risk assessment using the modified MEDALUS model in the Alta Murgia karst plateau (Apulia, Southern Italy)	1184
D'Ettoire U.S.*, Liso I.S. & Parise M. - A global overview of desertification in karstlands	1185

Fregola R.A.*, Liso I.S., Parise M., Lacalamita M., Cardellini C., Tieri M., Caliro S., Palmisano G., Gambini R. & Chiodini G. - Mineralization of the Kozan-8 thermal well (Kruja Province, central Albania): a mineralogical and water geochemical study	1186
Leone G.*, Esposito L., Ginolfi M. & Fiorillo F. - Terzaghi's effective stress principle and hydrological deformation of karst aquifers detected by GNSS and InSAR measurements	1187
Leone G., Jourde H., Ginolfi M.*, Esposito L., Ventafridda G. & Fiorillo F. - Short- and long-term changes in the discharge of the Caposele karst spring (Southern Apennines, Italy): statistics and modeling to understand their causes	1188
Leone G., Liso I.S., Michele G.*, Esposito L., Parise M. & Fiorillo F. - Karst hydrology and geomorphology of the Matese and Alburni Massifs, (Southern Italy), focusing on dolines and endorheic areas	1189
Liso I.S.*, D'Ettorre U., Benedetto L., Ladisa V., Lorusso F. & Parise M. - Open window on water table: examples from Apulia Region	1190
Lorusso F., Liso I.S., Mastronuzzi G. & Parise M.* - A flank margin cave along the Adriatic side of Apulia, Southern Italy	1191
Mammoliti E.*, Fronzi D., Rapazzetti M., Domizi J. & Tazioli A. - Integrating fracture analysis and X-ray tomography with permeability tests for rock fracture hydraulic conductivity assessment at laboratory-scale	1192
Manucci A.*, Cambi C., Fronzi D., Liso I.S., Mazzocca M., Mirabella F., Parise M., Casadei S., Tazioli A. & Valigi D. - Estimation of recharge to the karst Scirca spring (Central Italy) by using conventional and modified APLIS methods: a comparison	1193
Mostafa M.F.*, D'Ettorre U.S., Liso I.S. & Parise M. - On the hydraulic role of dolines	1194
Mostafa M.F.*, Liso I.S. & Parise M. - Seawater intrusion and coastal karst aquifers in Apulia: status, challenges and future scenarios	1195
Onorato M.*, Di Capua I., Liso I.S., Onorato R., Congedo M., Poto M., Palmisano G., Puglia G., Zini L. & Parise M. - Palude del Capitano (Apulia, Italy): a natural coastal laboratory to monitor biological diversity and dynamics of karst hydrogeology	1196
Rinaldi N., Marenghi L., Mittempergher S., Brozzo G., Longoni L., Papini M., Sabattini M., Mainini A. & Ronchetti F.* - New groundwater chemistry and isotope evidence on the La Spezia karst aquifer (western promontory, Gulf of La Spezia)	1197
Riva A.*, Longanesi G. & Ghirotti M. - Preliminary insights on hydrogeology of Mount Toc from 3D modeling	1198
Tieri M.*, Liso I.S., Parise M., Cardellini C., Chiodini G., Palmisano G., Gambini R., Caliro S. & Santi A. - Springs water geochemistry in central-southern Albania	1199
Vigna B.* & Fiorucci A. - The Bossea Karst Hydrogeology Laboratory	1200
Zini L.*, Calligaris C., Finocchiaro F., Ponton M. & Potleca M. - A karst area shared between carbonate megabeds and siliciclastic units: the example of Mt. Bernadia (NE Italy)	1201
S46. Sustainable raw material supply to boost the green and digital transition: the role of mineral waste recovery and recycling	
Aquilano A.*, Marrocchino E. & Vaccaro C. - Giving new life to granite quarrying waste: a case study from Buddusò (Sardinia, Italy)	1203
Baldassarre G.*, Fiorucci A. & Marini P. - Exploring critical and strategical raw materials recovery potential from mining waste: findings from some Italian historical mining districts	1204
Baldassarre G.*, Mori De Oliveira C. & Marini P. - Laboratory-scale reprocessing trials of historical mine waste from the Traversella mining district (Piedmont, Italy)	1205
Dino G.A.*, Mancini S., Casale M., Tazzini A., Faraudello A. & Rossi P. - Towards a Green transition: tools and protocols to help decision makers and companies to decide if and when applying extractive waste exploitation as an alternative to remediation	1206
Dolenec S.*, Pavlin M. & Ducman V. - Standardization of innovative construction products as a tool for market up-take	1207
Fantini R.*, Bernini M., Conte S., Zanelli C., Dondi M., Gualtieri A.F. & Arletti R. - Transforming extractive waste into ceramic innovation: a comprehensive characterization and recycling study	1208

Graziano S.F.*, Marone P., Trinchillo A., Di Benedetto C., Montesano G., Rispoli C. & Cappelletti P. - Processing waste of quartzite from Jaipur District (India) as secondary raw materials for cementitious adhesives	1209
Jackson L., Parbhakar-Fox A., Colombi F. & Baldassarre G.* - The role of secondary prospectivity of mine waste for enhancing critical metals recovery in South Australia	1210
Khelifi F., Dino G.A., Zhao X., Tazzini A.*, Passarella I. & Padoan E. - Geochemical and environmental evaluation of trace metals within newly constructed technosols: risks and potentials for large scale applications	1211
Mancini S.*, Pereira M.D., Lasagna M., Gambino F., Prego G., Gonçalves D., Jacinto A., Daud J., Loite J., Nganhane H., Rodrigues N., Dinis P. & Dino G.A. - Sustainability in geo-resource management through shared competence-building projects. The example of GEODES Erasmus Project	1212
Nakhaeiashtari M., Rabee A., Reitano R., Funicello F., Capitelli F. & Della Ventura G.* - Toward novel strategies for consolidating earther cultural heritage manufacts	1213
Radica F.*, Iezzi G., Capasso I., Galderisi A., Bianchini G., Paris E. & de Brito J. - Physical and petrographic features of CDW rubbles of 2016/2017 earthquakes from Central Italy	1214
Scervini S.*, Baldassarre G. & Bellopede R. - Sonic drilling: evaluation of the best techniques for tailings and mining waste exploration and valorization	1215
Sedda L.*, Attardi A., De Giudici G. & Naitza S. - Sardinia's mining heritage revaluig: a path to sustainable critical raw materials extraction	1216
Spizzichino D.*, Fumanti F., Mariano S., De Corso S., Andrisani M.G., Dacquino C., Guerra M., Lanz A., Lucarini M., Muto L., Serra M. & Amanti M. - URBES (URBan mining and Extractive waste information Sistem) Project	1217
Vitale E.* - Alkaline-activation of natural and artificial pozzolans as binders for soil treatment	1218
Zhao X., Khelifi F., Casale M., Tazzini A., Cavallo A., Padoan E., Yang K. & Dino G.A.* - Critical raw materials supply: challenges and potentialities to exploit REEs from siliceous stones and extractive waste	1219
S47. Evolution of the Variscan crust	
Attardi A.*, Cocco F., Deidda M.L., Sedda L., Funedda A. & Naitza S. - CRMs prospecting through comparative ore deposit modelling in SW Sardinia	1221
Caçador I., Dias da Silva Í.* & Pereira MF. - Syn-tectonic plutonism and extensional tectonics in the Variscan orogen: evidence from the Mississippian Reguengos de Monsaraz pluton (Ossa-Morena Zone, SW Iberian Massif)	1222
Cardello G.L.*, Amadori C., Rossignol C., Ferrero S., Cogné N., Poujol M., Persano C., Wildman M., Di Nicola L. & Casini L. - New geochronologic and thermochronologic constraints on the Variscan crustal evolution of the Einstein Telescope candidate site of Sardinia (Italy)	1223
Carosi R.*, Montomoli C., Iacopini D., Petroccia A., Simonetti M. & Oggiano G. - Geology of the Asinara Island (Sardinia, Italy)	1224
Cruciani G.*, Dulcetta L., Franceschelli M., Frassi C. & Musumeci G. - Late Variscan age of a metamorphic core complex in the foreland of the Variscan belt: insights from the Mt. Filau Orthogneiss (SW Sardinia, Italy)	1225
Deidda M.L.*, Naitza S., Casini L., Cocco F., Funedda A., Loi A., Oggiano G., Secchi F., Marchesini B. & Beranoaguirre A. - Distinct gold mineralisation events in the Variscan mineral system from southern Sardinia (Italy): implications for crustal sources	1226
Dias da Silva Í.*, Pereira M.F., González Clavijo E., Gama C. & Steel Hart L. - Mississippian gneiss domes and synorogenic basins: keys to understand the Variscan collisional orogen	1227
Dore E.*, Cocco F., Ferrero S., Melis M.T., Rossignol C., Biddau R., Buttau C., Dessì F., Calia F., Pani M., Da Pelo S. & Funedda A. - Geological investigations at Einstein Telescope site of Sardinia (Italy): preliminary results	1228
Funedda A.* - The Variscan basement of Sardinia: state of the art and open questions	1229
Funedda A.*, Cocco F., Forci A., Baraille J., Salaun M., Caria I. & Piredda R. - Preliminary data from fieldwork in the framework of the CARG Project 546-Guspini (SW Sardinia)	1230

Petroccia A., Carosi R., Montomoli C., Iaccarino S.*, Forshaw J.B. & Petrelli M. - Constraining the deformation in transpressive shear zones: insights from the Monte Grighini Shear Zone in Sardinia and implications for the Southern European Variscan belt	1231
Pieruccioni D.* & Simonetti M. - Preliminary results from microstructural investigations of post-collisional granitoid from the Asinara Island (NW Sardinia)	1232
Russo D. *, Fiannacca P., Fazio E., Cirrincione R. & Mamtani M.A. - An integrated field, microstructural, AMS and EBSD approach to unveil the architecture and construction mechanisms of post-collisional granitoid complexes: evidence from the late Variscan Serre Batholith (Southern Calabria)	1233
Spahić D., Cocco F.* & Tančić P. - Far-field interplay between the intra-Ordovician compressional tectonics along the northeastern Gondwana active margin and Gondwana interior: insights from the central Lybia Ordovician succession	1234
Spahić D., Radović M., Blagojević D., Tanasković L., Jovanović D., Vuković S. & Cocco F.* - Polyphase deformations and transposition cycles in the “Median Dacides” tectonic units	1235
Zanchi A. *, Angiolini L., Beauchamp B., Henderson C. & Snyder W. - Carlin Canyon, a key area for the study of the latest Carboniferous deformation in Nevada (USA)	1236
S48. Multidisciplinary Approaches to 3D Geological Modelling: Uncertainty mitigation for basin analysis and geological applications	
Abdallah I.B.*, Hollis C., Healy D., Prosser G. & Agosta F. - Multidimensional structural analysis of reservoir-scale fault damage zones flanking the eastern side of the High Agri Valley Basin, Southern Italy	1238
Anzelmo G. *, Forzese M., Iacopini D., Carbone S., Catalano S., Montalbano S. & Maniscalco R. - Building a 3D model of CARG Ragusa Sheet 648 (Hyblean Plateau, SE Sicily, Italy): evaluating/mitigating uncertainty through the integration of structural data at different scales	1239
Artoni A. *, Cioce S., Campana D., Martini A., Calabrese L., Lambertini L. & Tinterri R. - Unexpected results from 3D geological modelling in already extensively investigated area: the SE termination of the Salsomaggiore Terme tectonic window (Northern Apennines foothills, Parma province, Italy)	1240
Barbero E. *, Marcelli I., Irace A., Festa A., Catanzariti R., Da Prato S., Livio F. & Fioraso G. - From geological map to 3D model: integrating surface and subsurface datasets from Sheet 177 Tortona of the Geological Map of Italy at 1:50.000 scale (CARG Project)	1241
Barrera Acosta D. *, Toscani G., Amadori C., Colombera L. & Di Giulio A. - 3D reconstruction of regional-scale unconformities in the Po Basin: integrating well data and seismic profiles to improve the understanding of Plio-Pleistocene evolution	1242
Bigi S.* - Examples of multidisciplinary approach as a strategy to reduce uncertainties in geological models	1243
Canzoneri A. *, Martorana R., Agate M., Capizzi P., Gasparo Morticelli M., Carollo A. & Sulli A. - A subsoils model reconstructed integrating geological and geophysical data in the area of the town of Palermo ..	1244
Canzoneri A. *, Martorana R., Capizzi P., Bonfardeci A. & Favara R. - Characterization of the sedimentary basins in coastal plain sectors through the integration of geological and geophysical data: the case study of the North-Eastern Sicily	1245
Cortassa V. *, Tesauro M., Gola G., Galgaro A. & Manzella A. - Geological reconstruction of the Romagna and Ferrara folds area to evaluate its geothermal potential	1246
D’Ambrogi C.* - Geological 3D modeling is the new geological mapping	1247
Demurtas M. *, Sharp I., Pasqualetto L., Krüger Y., Drost K., Meckler A.N. & Rotevatn A. - Fluid flow history and paragenesis along a syn-rift basin bounding fault: the Helmsdale Fault (NE Scotland)	1248
Fonzetti R. *, Buttinelli M., Valoroso L., De Gori P. & Chiarabba C. - How high-resolution tomographic imaging can provide new information on fault interaction: the case of the 2009 L’Aquila seismic sequence	1249
Forzese M. *, Lipparini L., Chiacchieri D., Cavallaro D., Firetto Carlino M., Scarfi L., Faenza L. & Molinari I. - Regional subsurface 3D model of southern Sicily for potential seismogenic fault characterization and seismic scenarios: the INGV SPIN project	1250
Iandelli I. *, Marchetti E., Benvenuti M., Coli M. & Maestrelli D. - A first step toward a 3D geological model of Florence area (CARG Programme, Sheet 275): first approach for the reconstruction of the top substrate surface	1251

Invernizzi C.*, Costa M., Penza G., Teloni S. & Pierantoni P.P. - Seismotectonic characteristics of the 2022/24 Fano seismic sequence (Central Italy)	1252
Labry C.*, Duque C., Blanco-Coronas A., Da Pelo S., Funedda A. & Marcia L. - Groundwater modelling in faulted siliciclastic-carbonate sequences	1253
Livani M.*, Scrocca D., Gaudiosi I., Mancini M., Cavinato G.P., de Franco R., Caielli G., Vignaroli G., Romi A. & Moscatelli M. - A geology-based 3D velocity model of the Amatrice Basin (Central Italy)	1254
Manna L.*, Menegoni N., Maino M. & Perotti C. - Early deformations of carbonate platforms driven by differential compaction of the basinal unit: Finite Element Method-based numerical analysis	1255
Marcelli I.*, Irace A. & Fioraso G. - The subsurface geological map of the Torino metropolitan area (Western Po plain): from 3D model to 2D map export	1256
Meneghini F.*, Rielli A., Boschi C., Baneschi I., Amabile F., Perondi F., Marroni M. & Pandolfi L. - In search of a geological signature of slow earthquakes: structural and geochemical characterization of crack-seal veins in metasediments from the Alpine accretionary prism	1257
Morabito C.* & Morsilli M. - The importance of lithofacies mapping: a case study of Eocene base-of-slope deposits of the Apulia Carbonate Platform (Gargano Promontory, Southern Italy)	1258
Norini G.*, Caielli G., De Franco R., Rusconi D., Aghib F., Schirolli P., Zerboni A., Piccin A., D'Ambrogi C. & the CARG sheet Brescia research group - Approach and methodologies for the 3D geological modelling of the CARG 121 Brescia 1:50.000 sheet	1259
Olita F.*, Giampaolo V., Rizzo E., Giano S.I., Capozzoli L., De Martino G. & Prosser G. - Interpretation of subsurface data for the 3D static model of the High Agri intermontane basin: inferences for Quaternary tectonic evolution of the Southern Apennines	1260
Pace P.*, Scisciani V. & Mancinelli P. - 3D Subsurface structural-geological modelling at the Central-Southern Apennines boundary: The 379-Capracotta geological sheet	1261
Petricca P.*, Castorina G., Congi M.P. & D'Ambrogi C. - A proposal for simple accuracy evaluation of geological surfaces based on spatial autocorrelation	1262
Pizzati M.*, Torabi A., Cavozi C., Iacumin P. & Balsamo F. - Fluid flow patterns inferred from selective cementation in fluvio-deltaic, sandstone-conglomerate bodies, Crotona forearc Basin	1263
Rizzo G.F.*, Maiorana M. & Gasparo Morticelli M. - Multidisciplinary approach for 3D geological model reconstruction: the example of Mt. San Calogero (Sciacca, Southwestern Sicily)	1264
Tentori D.*, Mancini M., Livani M., Stigliano F., Milli S. & Moscatelli M. - Stratigraphic constraints for the 3D modeling of the Tevere Alluvial Valley beneath Rome (Italy)	1265
Zambrano M.* - Preliminary findings from deep 3D electrical resistivity tomography in active faults	1266
S49. Multidisciplinary approaches to the geometric and kinematic definition of seismogenic faults	
Adinolfi G.M.*, Carducci A., De Matteis R., de Nardis R. & Romano M.A. - Advanced tool for fault plane solution reliability assessment	1268
Alessandrini M. & Menichetti M.* - The geology of Mt. Vettore area in the Sibillini Mountains, Northern Apennines of Italy	1269
Andrenacci C.*, Lavecchia G., Bello S., Pietrolungo F. & de Nardis R. - Quaternary stress and strain patterns in the Italian peninsula from QUIN's data	1270
Andrenacci C., Bello S.* & Lavecchia G. - Get to know the QUIN database: applications and potential insights from fault traces and over 8000 structural-geological data points in the Quaternary extensional belt of Italy	1271
Barrera Acosta D.*, De Matteo A., Maesano F., Toscani G., Seno S. & Basili R. - Probabilistic analysis of slip rates over time of offshore buried thrusts in the Central Adriatic Sea (Italy)	1272
Battistelli M.*, Ferrarini F., Carafa M.M.C., Cardinali M., Bucci F., Merryman Boncori J.P. & Brozzetti F. - Do faults play hide-and-seek? New hints on the relationship between active deformation and surface faulting in a seismic gap zone of central-southern Apennines - A multidisciplinary approach	1273
Bonini L.*, Basili R., Burrato P., Abbate A., Areggi G., Bertone N., Del Ben A., Maesano F.E. & Ponton M. - Geometric and kinematic assessment of the seismogenic sources of Northeast Italy	1274
Buttinelli M.*, Anselmi M. & Maesano F.E. - A fresh view of the 1997 Umbria-Marche seismic sequence in light of a fusion of updated seismological and subsurface data	1275

Cicala M.*, De Giosa F., Piscitelli A. & Festa V. - Reprocessed SEG-Y seismic profiles across the continuation in the Apulia offshore of the onshore seismogenic Mattinata Fault (Adriatic Sea, Southern Italy)	1276
Cipressi G.M., Romano M.A.*, Bernardi P., Diez E., Franceschinell F., Garbin M., Guidarelli M., Klin P., Laurenzano G., Moratto L., Peruzza L., Pettenati F., Plasencia M., Priolo E., Rebez A., Romanelli M., Sandron D., Santulin M., Saraò A., Tamaro A., Lavecchia G. & de Nardis R. - Building a comprehensive seismic catalog of the Montello-Collalto area (Eastern Southern Alps, Italy) for seismotectonic and induced seismicity purposes	1277
Francescone M.*, Ciaglia S., Giallini S., Pagliaroli A. & Pizzi A. - New insights on the Mt. Morrone (Central Apennines) active normal fault and related basin through passive seismic methods	1278
Lavecchia G.* & de Nardis R. - Exploring the significance of fault-earthquake data pairs in unveiling structural and seismotectonic complexities - Case studies across different tectonic regimes in Central Italy	1279
Lavecchia G.*, Cirillo D., Andrenacci C., Pietrolungo F., Bello S., Brozzetti F., de Nardis R., Valoroso L., Diaferia G., De Landro G., Presti D., Totaro C., Scolaro S. & Orecchio B. - First detailed 3D geometric and kinematic curvilinear fault models of the Southern Italy extensional belt: integrated analysis of surface and deep data	1280
Lenci S.*, Keir D., Molli G., Vannucchi P., Del Ventisette C. & Pagli C. - Seismological study of transverse faults in a highly segmented extensional front in the Northern Apennines: the case of Sant'Anna Pelago	1281
Lipparini L., Forzese M.*, Chiacchieri D., Cavallaro D., Firetto Carlino M., Scarfi L., Molinari I., Maniscalco R. & Catalano S. - 3D imaging and modelling of a complex regional fault system: the Scicli Line (Sicily, Italy)	1282
Loreto M.F.*, Ferrante V., Argnani A., Conti A., Cuffaro M., Ganas A., Lampidou D., Ligi M., Merino I., Muccini F., Elisavet N., Palmiotto C., Petracchini L., Poulos S., Ranero R.C., Romano S. & Nomikou P. - Anatomy of strike-slip Kefalonia fault to Hellenic frontal thrust transitional zone, western Hellenic Arc	1283
Morelli D., Crispini L.*, Locatelli M., Cianfarra P., Federico L., Maino M., Perozzo M. & Seno S. - Past to recent tectonic activity in the western Ligurian Margin: new insights from geophysical marine data ..	1284
Palmucci A.*, Brozzetti F., Akimbekova A., Bello S., Ercoli M., Pauselli C., Carboni F., Barchi M.R., Lavecchia G. & Cirillo D. - Field and seismic reflection constraints for the geometric and kinematic characterization of the Quaternary extensional fault system in the Campania-Lucania arc (Southern Apennines, Italy)	1285
Parnas M.*, Pagli C., Keir D., La Rosa A. & McNeill L. - New analysis of InSAR and seismology for kinematic reconstruction of the 1995 offshore Aigion M6.5 earthquake (Greece)	1286
Pietrolungo F.*, Palano M., Madarieta-Txurruka A., Srivastava E., Sparacino F., Sulli A., Parrino N., Andrenacci C., Cirillo D., Bello S. & Lavecchia G. - Strain-rate estimation and focal mechanism stress inversion in Himalaya-Tibet region	1287
Safarzadeh E., Barchi M.R.*, Ercoli M., Carboni F., Akimbekova A., Mirabella F. & Porreca M. - Structural style and seismicity: a geological focus on the 2022 Mw5.5 Northern Adriatic off-shore earthquake ..	1288
Scolaro S.*, Batlló J., Orecchio B., Presti D., Stich D. & Totaro C. - Exploring historical seismograms: moment tensor inversion of the 1947 Squillace Basin Earthquake (Calabria, South Italy)	1289
Talone D.*, de Nardis R., De Siena L. & Lavecchia G. - Geometric constraints for thrust-related deformation in eastern Central-Southern Italy: new insights from travel-time and attenuation tomography	1290
Tiberti M.M.*, Maesano F.E., Buttinelli M., De Gori P., Ferri F., Minelli L. & Di Nezza M. - A multidisciplinary geophysical approach as help to validate 3D models and investigate the seismotectonics of the Central Apennines (Italy)	1291
Valensise G.* - From active faults to seismogenic sources: understanding their geometry, hierarchy, and earthquake potential through a fully multidisciplinary approach	1292
S50. Unveiling earthquake mechanics, from field to laboratory based approach	
Abdallah IB.*, Dastoli S., Corradetti A., Taddeo C., Mercuri M., Curzi M. & Agosta F. - Fault roughness associated to fault growth mechanisms along high-angle normal faults, first results from the field-based structural analysis of the Monte Capo di Serre Fault, Abruzzo, Italy	1294

Aldrighetti S.* , Di Toro G. & Pennacchioni G. - Asymmetric microfracture pattern associated to seismic rupture (Gole Larghe Fault, Italy)	1295
Bigaroni N., Trippetta F.*, Noel C., Giorgetti C., Pozzi G. & Collettini C. - Evolution of the Vp/Vs ratio during deformation tests at high fluid pressure: implications for earthquake mechanics	1296
Chinello M.* , Schito A., Bowden S.A., Tesei T., Spagnuolo E., Aretusini S. & Di Toro G. - Origin of mirror-like fault surfaces in bituminous dolostones (Central Apennines, Italy)	1297
Di Toro G.* , Gomila R., Feng W., Salvadori L., Wu W.-H., Guglielmi G., Tesei T., Yao L., Sciarra A., Cantucci B., Grassa F., Piochi M. & Ma S. - Frictional fault healing under hydrothermal conditions	1298
Guglielmi G.* , De Paola N., Giorgetti C., Collettini C. & Trippetta F. - Rheology of Triassic evaporites and implications for seismicity of the Apennines: insights from triaxial laboratory experiments	1299
Manna L., Maino M.* , Dabrowski M. & Casini L. - A study on how the damage geometry governs the stress distribution within a fault zone	1300
Masoch S.* , Fondriest M., Preto N., Prando F., Di Toro G., Pennacchioni G. & Molli G. - Deformation processes and origin of fluids during Miocene exhumation of Alpine Corsica	1301
Mauro M.* , Volpe G., De Solda M., Magnani M.B., Collettini C. & Scuderi M.M. - Probing the micromechanics of laboratory faults using ultrasonic waves: insights from borehole samples from Delaware Basin, Texas	1302
Novellino R.* , Prosser G., Lettino A., Costa S. & Agosta F. - From fault weakening to re-strengthening, new insights on fluidization in carbonate-hosted normal fault	1303
Pizzati M.* , Aretusini S., Spagnuolo E., Aldega L., Torabi A., Storti F. & Balsamo F. - Shallow earthquakes affecting high-porosity rocks in forearc basin settings: a combined meso-microstructural, mineralogical, and experimental approach	1304
Pozzi G.* , Volpe G., Ruggieri R., Scuderi M., Tesei T., Marone C., Collettini C. & Cocco M. - Friction, mineralogy, and microstructures: how complex is the brittle deformation of faults?	1305
Salvadori L.* , Tesei T. & Di Toro G. - Frictional strength, healing behaviour and deformation mechanism of low-grade serpentinites at hydrothermal conditions	1306
Sciarra A.* , Di Toro G., Cantucci B., Gomila R., Grassa F., Piochi M., Brusca L., Bellomo S. & Ricci T. - The study of the seismic cycle in hydrothermal conditions through experiments, analysis and modeling in the SCHOTTA project	1307
Tesei T.* , Molli G., Remitti F., Mitterpergher S. & Pozzi G. - The structural geology of fault healing: a preliminary view	1308
Toffol G.* , Pennacchioni G., Scambelluri M. & Morales L.F.G. - Microstructural record of seismic brittle failure at intermediate-depth conditions	1309
S51. Unveiling the long-lasting evolution of active margins from field to micro-scale	
Ballato P.* , Balestrieri M.L., Dunkl I., Balling P., Paknia M., Biralvand M., Heidarzadeh G., Zeilinger G., Ghasemi M., Faccenna C. & Strecker M.R. - Tectonic evolution of the northern sectors of the Iranian Plateau: insights from thermo-kinematic modelling into Neogene plateau building processes	1311
Carosi R.* , Simonetti M., Montomoli C., Iaccarino S. & Petrocchia A. - The importance of regional-scale shear zones in paleogeographic reconstructions: the case study of the Variscan belt in the Mediterranean area	1312
Caso F., Filippi M., Piloni C.B., Farina F., Roda M., Piazzolo S. & Zucali M.* - A journey into the Permian lower continental crust: a multidisciplinary approach to reconstruct migmatization in the Valpelline Series (Dent-Blanche Nappe, Western Alps)	1313
Casoli L.* & Giuntoli F. - Evidence of strain partitioning and localization in carpholite-bearing hybrid veins: a case study from the Piedmont Zone, Western Italian Alps	1314
Cattò S., Ballato P., Bagheri S., Zattin M. & Cavazza W.* - Limited Neogene dip-slip tectonics in the northwestern Iranian Plateau: evidence from low-temperature thermochronology	1315
Cicala M.* , De Giosa F., Lisco S., Moretti M. & Festa V. - Evolution of active margins? A link with the tectonic reactivation in foreland area	1316
Corvò S., Montemagni C., Zanchetta S.* & Langone A. - Reconciling the onset of Tethyan rifting in the Ivrea Verbano Zone (European Southern Alps)	1317

Cruciani G.*, Fancello D., Ferrari M., Bragagni A., Tommasini S. & Franceschelli M. - Petrological constraints and geodynamic significance of a Triassic lamprophyre dyke crosscutting the Palaeozoic basement of NE Sardinia, Italy	1318
Dana D.*, De Cesari F., Montomoli C., Iaccarino S., Lenci S., Corno A. & Carosi R. - Geology and petrology of the Northern Dora-Maira Massif in the Tredici Laghi - Conca Cialancia area (Germanasca - Pellice Valleys, Western Alps)	1319
De Cesari F.*, Dana D., Montomoli C., Iaccarino S., Corno A. & Carosi R. - Unveiling the tectono-metamorphic framework of northern Dora-Maira Massif (Western Alps): insights from Pellice and Chisone valley	1320
Del Sole L.*, Vignaroli G., Moretto V., Curzi M., Aldega L., van der Lelij R. & Viola G. - Unveiling complex fault architecture evolution through (micro)structural, geochronological and petrophysical investigations: the case of the Carboneras Fault (SE Spain)	1321
Feriozzi F.*, Siravo G. & Speranza F. - The heritage of Tethyan oceanic transform faults within Alpine orogens: The Shkoder-Peja transverse zone (SPTZ) of Northern Albania	1322
Gómez-Barreiro J.* - Textural footprint of orogenic processes: convergence, collision and reequilibration ...	1323
Montemagni C.*, Rocca M., Zanchi A., Favaro S., Viola G., Aldega L. & Zanchetta S. - Long-lived activity of a regional thrust-system in a pre-collisional setting: the Orobic Thrust (Southern Alps, N Italy)	1324
Montemagni C., Monti R., Malaspina N. & Zanchetta S.* - Shearing at the top of the Adula nappe: syn-collisional exhumation of the San Bernardino eclogites	1325
Montomoli C.*, Iaccarino S., Montemagni C., Nania L. & Carosi R. - Multistage evolution of a regional shear zone: constraints from the South Tibetan Detachment System	1326
Petrocchia A.*, Giuntoli F., Viola G. & Callegari I. - Heterogeneous rock response to deformation in subduction-related continental shear zones: a possible record of episodic tremors and slow slip events from the Saih Hatat window, Oman	1327
Piloni C.B.*, Orellana H.E., Gusmeo T., Assanelli M., Filippi M., Rebay G., Zanoni D., Roda M., Zucali M. & Spalla M.I. - Tectono-metamorphic evolution of continental and oceanic crustal slices in the Alpine Subduction Complex (Piemonte - Sesia-Lanzo Zone boundary, Western Italian Alps)	1328
Rocca M.*, Zanchetta S., Montemagni C., Aldega L., Fiorini A., Carminati E., Kylander-Clark A. & Zanchi A. - New insights on the Late Cretaceous S-verging thrusting in the central Southern Alps: clues from structural, geochemical, and geochronological analyses	1329
Simonetti M.*, Langone A., Bonazzi M., Corvò S. & Maino M. - Evolution of a rift-related mid-crustal shear zone: the case study of the Forno-Rosarolo shear zone (Ivrea-Verbanò Zone, Southern Alps)	1330
Viola G.*, Zuccari C., Giuntoli F., Degl'Innocenti S., Sanguettoli T., Callegari I. & Vignaroli G. - Orogenic wedge formation during obduction: insights, implications and new perspectives from the Oman Mountains	1331
Zucali M.*, Spalla M.I., Roda M., Zanoni D. & Piloni C.B. - The Sesia-Lanzo Zone in the Western Alps Subduction Complex: Alpine evolution and pre-Alpine remnants	1332
Zuccari C.*, Tavarnelli E., Mazzarini F., Viola G., Aldega L., Moretto V., van der Lelij R. & Musumeci G. - Fault architecture, age and deformation localisation history of the Mykonos Detachment, Cyclades, Greece	1333
S52. Open session on volcanic processes	
Brum da Silveira D.*, Thordarson T., Höskuldsson Á., Moreland W. & Jónsdóttir I. - The 3ka Búrfellshraun lava flow field, Northeastern Iceland: lava dynamics and surface morphology	1335
Carrazana A. & Gimeno D.* - Volcano- and chemostratigraphy of the calc-alkaline and peralkaline succession of Sulcis region, SW Sardinia, Italy: new pyroclastic units, redefinition of others, and improvement of the mapping of volcanic units	1336
Caruso E.*, Sulpizio R., Costa A., Petrelli M., Massaro S. & Fisauli G. - A novel approach to assess magma ascent times through crystal zonation analysis	1337
Colle F.*, Masotta M., Costa S., Giacomoni P.P., Marani M., Trua T. & Pichavant M. - Petrological evolution of the trans-crustal plumbing system of Marsili volcano (Tyrrhenian Sea, Italy): insights into crystal mush heterogeneity from glomerocrysts variability	1338

De Natale G.*, Rolandi G., Troise C., Di Lascio M. & Sacchi M. - The 1538 eruption at Campi Flegrei resurgent caldera: implications for unrest evolution and eruption hazard	1339
Knuever M.*, Mele D. & Sulpizio R. - Skarn formation associated with alkaline magma chambers: comparison of Somma-Vesuvius, Colli Albani and Merapi volcanic systems	1340
Masotta M.*, Colle F., Costa S. & Landi P. - Plagioclase dissolution and reaction in a hydrous basaltic melt: a proxy for deciphering time scales of mixing events at Stromboli volcano (Italy)	1341
Mele D.*, Knuever M., Dellino P., Costa A., Fornelli A., Massaro S. & Sulpizio R. - New evidence of syn-eruptive magma-carbonate interaction: the case study of the Pomici di Avellino eruption at Somma-Vesuvius (Italy)	1342
Moretti R.* - H ₂ O-CO ₂ fluid infiltration and the Campi Flegrei unrest: from hydrothermal drying to shallow magma rejuvenation	1343
Musu A.*, Caricchi L., Vetere F., Griffiths T., Petrelli M., Corsaro R.A., Peres S., Perugini D. & Pisello A. - Linking crystal textural and chemical features to pre-eruptive magmatic processes: insights from dynamic experiments on natural Mt. Etna trachybasalts	1344
Novembre D.*, Carrazana A. & Gimeno D. - Solid-state synthesis of calcosilicates mimics pyroclastic rheomorphic rhyolitic- xenolith interaction in the Monte Ulmus peralkaline unit (SW Sardinia, Italy)	1345
Sieber J.*, Arzilli F., Lo Monaco S. & Carroll M.R. - Alkali feldspar dissolution kinetics in trachytic melts .	1346
Sortino F.*, Calderone L., Giammanco S. & Ferlito C. - Monitoring fumarole emissions on the flanks of mount Etna and correlation with volcanic activity	1347
Tranquilino C.*, Dioguardi F., Gentile L., Caballero L. & Sarocchi D. - Finding the best protocol to characterize the rheological behavior of fine volcanic sediment suspensions	1348

S53. Open Poster Session

Accettella D.*, Savini A., Cuffaro M., Diviacco P., Muccini F., Zgur F., Buca M., Cova A., Facchin L., Santulin M., Romeo R. & Viola A. - ISOBatA's contribution and strategy to Antarctic Seabed Exploration	1350
Alisi C., Biddau R., Calandrelli T., De Giudici G., Dore E., Fancello D., Marras P.A., Medas D.*, Musu E., Paganin P., Pili S., Podda F., Siclari G. & Vacca S. - Investigation on bioaugmentation as a sustainable alternative to chemical fertilizers: preliminary results	1351
Bindellini G.*, Benton M.J., Petti F.M., Bernardi M., Rubidge B., Hancox J. & Romano M. - Middle Triassic tetrapods: a triumphant faunal return after the Permo-Triassic mass extinction	1352
Bonetto S., Caselle C., Frasca G. & Mosca P.* - A geological and geotechnical modelling of Alpine sulphates: the SALT project	1353
Borzi A.M.*, Cannata A., Panzera F., D'Amico S. & Aster R.C. - Exploring the relationship between the microseism long-term energy trend and wave power in the Mediterranean Sea during the period 1996-2023	1354
Corradino M.*, Lo Presti V., Cassataro R., Agate M. & Sulli A. - Mapping of <i>Posidonia oceanica</i> meadows in the Capo San Marco offshore (Sciaccia, Sicily): evaluation of the lower limit using geophysical methods	1355
Corradino M.*, Faraci C., Monaco C. & Pepe F. - Coastal boulder production controlled by columnar joints of ignimbrite and extreme waves along the high-energy rocky coast of Pantelleria Island (Sicily Channel, Mediterranean Sea)	1356
De Carlo C.*, Ferrante V., Longhitano S.G. & Gamberi F. - The evolution of the Mortorio submarine canyon (Eastern Sardinia Margin): preliminary ideas from a process-oriented morphologic interpretation of a shelf-indenting canyon	1357
De Lucia V.*, Donati Sarti G., Protano G., Nannoni F. & Salvini R. - Drone remote sensing and geopedological analyses for precision farming viticulture in the area of Montalcino (Siena, Italy)	1358
Fiore A.*, Sabato L., Simone O. & Tropeano M. - Natural sections of incised valleys partly filled by late Quaternary alluvial deposits perched on rocky sea-cliff of Gargano (Apulia, Southern Italy)	1359
Galamini G.*, Malferrari D., Altimari F., Orlandi S. & Barbieri L. - From waste to resource: recovery of quarry by-products for zinc foliar fertilization	1360
Guerriero V.*, Scorzini A.R., Di Lena B., Iulianella S., Di Bacco M. & Tallini M. - Climate variations and crop yields: a sustainability issue illustrated by a case study from the Abruzzo region, Italy	1361

Ibe C.U.*, Perrini M., Caggianelli A., Brogi A., Langone A., Liotta D., Stuart F., Tursi F. & Zucchi M. - From emplacement to exhumation of a granitic intrusion in a highly extended continental crust: insights from the Pliocene Gavorrano granite (Northern Apennines, Italy)	1362
Lustrino M.* - Miracles needed. Climate changes and the physical limits of the Earth	1363
Petrella F.* & Todaro S. - Sedimentological analysis of the Jurassic pelagic “oolites” (Buccheri Formation, Western Sicily): paleoenvironmental and paleogeographic implications	1364
Servetto G.P.*, Root C.M., Di Felice S., Passarella A., Ruiz-Zepeda F., Gieré R. & Vigliaturo R. - Magnetite nanoparticles dissolution in simulated biological fluids	1365
Smiljanić D., Daković A.*, Marković M., Ožegović M. & Obradović M. - Organobentonites as perspective adsorbents for nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug - diclofenac sodium	1366

PhD Day

Some of the abstracts submitted for the PhD day are available in the sessions indicated in parentheses

Chrappan Soldavini B.* & Merlini M. - Synthesis and structural characterization of a new high-pressure and high-temperature CaSiO ₃ polymorph	1368
Baldassarri L.*, Fanti F., Dinelli E. & Bais G. - Geochemical analysis and palaeoenvironmental reconstruction of the laminated limestones from the Villaggio del Pescatore fossil site (Trieste, Italy) (S4)	164
Monnanni A.*, Rimondi V., Morelli G., Nannoni A., Sforzi L., Martellini T., Cincinelli A., Chelazzi D., Laurati M., Lattanzi P. & Costagliola P. - Microplastics characterisation in shallow waters of the Arno River (Central Italy) and its discharge into the Mediterranean Sea: the main impacting role of the smallest size particles (S2)	129
Mowbray V.*, Sue C., Beauval C., Lemoine A., Mathey M. & Baize S. - Integrating geophysical, structural and tectonic data in a probabilistic seismic hazard assessment (PSHA) for the South- East of France (S36)	979
Onorato M.*, Di Capua I., Liso I.S., Onorato R., Congedo M., Poto M., Palmisano G., Puglia G., Zini L. & Parise M. - Palude del Capitano (Apulia, Italy): a natural coastal laboratory to monitor biological diversity and dynamics of karst hydrogeology (S45)	1196
Sobbe A.*, Bianchini G., Rizzo E. & Brombin V. - Geophysical and geochemical data integration for agricultural soil monitoring and prevention of the effects of salinity, organic matter, and climate change in the Province of Ferrara (Northern Italy) (S29)	788
Indelicato V.*, Punturo R., Visalli R., Pistorio A., Cirrincione R., Cantaro C. & Pinizzotto M.R. - Approaching knowledge of naturally occurring asbestos in volcanic geological contexts of southern Italy (S19)	569
Ouladmansour A.*, Mesto E., Lacalamita M., Mongelli G., Mamei P., Cerri G., Capitani G., Conconi R., Agrosi G. & Schingaro E. - Mineralogical and geochemical characterization of red muds from Portovesme (SW Sardinia, Italy) (S19)	574
Pirulli G., Mancino S.*, Sabato G., Parise M., Scardino G. & Scicchitano G. - Landslide body segmentation from satellite imagery using artificial intelligence model: case studies Ischia island and Forli - Cesena area (S14)	450
Criniti S.* & Martín-Martín M. - Detrital modes of the Culm facies in the Betic-Rifean chain (S40)	1077
Luconi I.*, Ercoli R. & Paris E. - Artificial weathering and surficial consolidation techniques applied to the ‘Peperino’ from the Alban Hills volcano (Latium, Italy) (S5)	209
Casarin A.*, Radica F., Iezzi G., Galderisi A., Bravo M., de Brito J., Brando G., Nazzari M. & Scarlato P. - 2D image analysis of mortars: amount of cement paste and texture of the aggregates (S20)	582
Dallara E.*, Chelle-Michou C., Fulignati P., Gioncada A., Tavazzani L., Tattitch B. & Lelli M. - Fluid evolution in the deep reservoir of the Larderello geothermal system: insights from microthermometry and LA-ICP-MS analyses of quartz-hosted fluid inclusions (S10)	343
Fasciglione G.*, Benassai G., Mattei G., Mucerino L., Pappone G. & Aucelli P.P.C. - Erosive effects of sea-storms, human pressure, and sea level rise on Volturno coastal plain (mid-Tyrrhenian area): present to future coastal hazard (S15)	468
Hu L., Donati D.*, Landi G., Zama F. & Borgatti L. - Development and application of an enhanced inversion algorithm for the reconstruction of the basal surface of landslides (S25)	700
Martiniello S.*, Capitanio A., Legnaioli S. & Raneri S. - Gemstone, treatments and imitations in medieval goldworking: a gemmological and spectroscopic combined approach (S7)	274

Fonzetti R. *, Valoroso L., De Gori P., Govoni A. & Chiarabba C. - ML vs semi-automatic seismic catalogs: a new catalog for the L'Aquila 2009 earthquake sequence (S36)	974
Imam C. *, Chaibi M., Ayt Ougougdal M. & Charif A. - Analyzing coastal cliff stability and recession rates along the Safi Atlantic Coast, Morocco (S15)	470
Javed S. *, Dondi M., Molinari C., Conte S., Arletti R., Fantini R., Gualtieri A., Siligardi C., Miselli P., Bignozzi M.C., Ridolfi G., Spalanzani G. & Zanelli C. - Characterization and valorization of dam sediments: potential use in building materials (S22)	634
Negri A. *, Storta E., Guerini M., Khoso R.B., Mantovani A. & Giardino M. - Geoheritage and cultural heritage in the Sesia Val Grande UNESCO Global Geopark (North-West Italy): new approach for monitoring and assessing geosites and cultural sites (S8)	305
Pignatiello G. *, Coco I., De Girolamo M., Di Persio M., Giannattasio F., Gizzi C., Materni V., Miconi L., Miconi M., Piangiamore G.M., Romano G., Romano V., Santarelli L., Sapia V., Spadoni S., Tozzi R., Tripaldi S., Siniscalchi A., De Michelis P. & Balasco M. - Geoelectromagnetic map for central Italy: preliminary results of the MARGE project (S42)	1124
Vance G. *, Clementucci R., Picotti V. & Willett S.D. - Catchment-averaged denudation rates in the Northern Apennines and Ligurian Alps and implications for landscape dynamics (S14)	456
Vitrano A. *, Viti C., Della Ventura G., Lucci F. & Vetere F. - A preliminary petrological study of refractory inclusions in NWA12800 meteorite (S20)	594
Ariano M. *, Fantozzi P.L. & Albarello D. - A systematic analysis on Italian national territory to test the role of local topographic effects (S24)	665
Castronuovo R. *, Borghetti M., Ferrara A.M.S., Spatola M.F. & Nolè A. - Vegetation cover dynamics in the Mediterranean region: a spectral-based assessment of the riparian vegetation patterns (S29)	772
Fracchiolla R. *, Bonamassa G., Liso I.S., Lollino P., Lorusso G. & Parise M. - Building a database for the analysis of sinkholes related to artificial cavities: the case study of Altamura (Apulia, Southern Italy) (S26)	717
Nava L. *, Mondini A., Bhuyan K., Fang C., Monserrat O., Novellino A. & Catani F. - Sentinel-1 SAR-based globally distributed landslide detection by deep neural networks (S25)	703
Anzelmo G. *, Forzese M., Iacopini D., Carbone S., Catalano S., Montalbano S. & Maniscalco R. - Building a 3D model of CARG Ragusa Sheet 648 (Hyblean Plateau, SE Sicily, Italy): evaluating/mitigating uncertainty through the integration of structural data at different scales (S48)	1239
Di Chiara G. *, Farina I., Fraternali F. & Petrillo A. - New materials for civil engineering through solidification and stabilization processes (S16)	494
Cacioli M.G., Mancini M. *, Cosentino G., Carfagna N., Coltella M., Francescone M., Pacitti P., Albarello D., Motti A., Natali N., Simone G., Onga M., Stigliano F. & Moscatelli M. - Update of the Level 2 Seismic Microzonation in Umbria Region: methodology and perspectives (S24)	669
Ghani J. *, Dinelli E., Funari V., Giuliani S. & Bellucci L.G. - Radionuclides assessment in municipal solid waste incineration plants wastes: a comparative case study of pre- and post-pandemic periods (S17) .	520
Indelicato V. *, Punturo R., Mineo S., Pappalardo G., Lanzafame G., Visalli R. & Cirrincione R. - Multi-analytical characterization of main lithotypes employed in the Val di Noto UNESCO sites (south-eastern Sicily) (S5)	203
Maiorana M. *, Rizzo G.F., Todaro S., Gasparo Morticelli M., Agate M. - Linking an outcrop analogue to a deep potential CO2 storage site with 3D geological model: an example from southwestern Sicily (S44)	1164
Salerno A. *, Commis L. & Catalano S. - Rock outcrops classification by Sentinel-2 images: a new gis-based toolbox proposal (S14)	453
Storta E. *, Senesi M. & Borghi A. - Mèmora: a showcase for the cultural heritage of Piemonte Region (S6)	254
Venezia V. *, Bellini F., Festa V., Sabato L. & Tropeano M. - The Water and the Rock: a geotouristic route through the geology of springs and fountains in Matera (Basilicata, Southern Italy) (S8)	313
Dinani P. *, Bigi S., Conti A. & Moallemi A. - Carbon sequestration potential of abandoned fractured reservoirs in Northwest Zagros, Iran (S44)	1158

D'Aniello M.*, Zampella M., Dosi A., Rownok A., Delli Veneri M., Ettari A., Cavuoti S., Sannino L., Brescia M., Donadio C. & Longo G. - Interplanetary river classification: a geomorphological approach utilizing subjective and objective analysis through advanced statistical methods (S35)	952
Dumon Steenssens L.*, d'Elia M., Quarta G. & Mastronuzzi G. - 14C age determination of beaches ridges from Terra Nova Bay, Antarctica (S3)	147
Parnas M.*, Pagli C., Keir D., La Rosa A. & McNeill L. - New analysis of InSAR and seismology for kinematic reconstruction of the 1995 offshore Aigion M6.5 earthquake (Greece) (S49)	1286
Barrera Acosta D.*, Toscani G., Amadori C., Colombera L. & Di Giulio A. - 3D reconstruction of regional-scale unconformities in the Po Basin: integrating well data and seismic profiles to improve the understanding of Plio-Pleistocene evolution (S48)	1242
Pezzotta A.*, Marinoni A., Al Kindi M., Zucali M. & Zerboni A. - How long does the signature of tectonic events last in the landscape? Topographical analysis of Jebel Akhdar dome and surrounding Semail Ophiolite in the Al-Hajar Mountains (northern Sultanate of Oman) (S14)	448
Commis L.*, Barbagallo V., Brandano M., Cornacchia I., Distefano S., Mancini A., Marianelli D., Salerno A., Tortorici G., Di Stefano A. & Catalano S. - The impact of an integrated stratigraphic and structural analysis on the updating of the regional tectonic scheme: an example from the Hyblean Plateau (SE Sicily) (S38)	1027
D'Abbicco V.*, De Giosa F., de Luca A., Fracchiolla T., Lisco S., Mastronuzzi G. & Moretti M. - Sedimentary dynamics and biological-anthropic processes on the seafloor: the natural laboratory of Taranto seas (northern Ionian Sea, southern Italy) (S12)	393
Ridolfi R.M.*, Azzaro S., Beaubien S.E., Da Pra A., Pontiggia M. & Bigi S. - Development of a site-screening method for hydrogen storage purposes and its application to an industrial dataset of Italian reservoirs (S44)	1171
Saltarelli C.* - Seismic maps between historical approach and scientific research. A contribution from the history of science to risk reduction (S11)	379
Sorrentino A.*, Fasciglione G., Mattei G., Pappone G. & Aucelli P.P.C. - On the resilience to climate change of sites of community importance (SCI): the case of Cala del Cefalo (Southern Italy) (S15)	479
Balzan S.*, Botezatu C., Faccini B., Ferretti G., Galamini G., Mattioli L., Tassoni G. & Coltorti M.A - A comprehensive study of ammonium removal from livestock effluents using zeolites in various operational scenarios (S22)	618
Furlan A.*, Contessi M. & Fanti F. - Taxonomic diversity of fossil vertebrates from the quaternary deposits of the Karst Pit of Cà Negra (Croatia) (S6)	245
Tagliacollo L.*, Bonadiman C., Sacconi E., Bianchini G., Brombin V. & Tassinari R. - Potential mineral resources in historically dismissed volcanogenic massive sulfide (VMS) deposits of the Emilia Romagna region (Italy): petrological and geochemical study for Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) exploration and exploitation (S34)	936
Mascaro M.E.*, Auriemma R., Mazzoli C. & Maritan L. - Investigating post-depositional alterations in underwater ceramics. The case of the archaeological site of Torre Santa Sabina (south-eastern Italy) (S5)	213
Scarani S.*, Sanfilippo A., Basch V., Genske F. & Stracke A. - Compositional variability of the oceanic crust as a function of spreading rates: insights from the ultra-slow spreading Gakkel Ridge (Arctic Ocean) (S34)	931
Scanu M.*, Capaldi C., Ciotola A., D'Uva F., Morra V., Verde M. & De Bonis A. - African amphorae from Cumae: archaeometric study for provenance and technological features (S5)	228
De Gregorio E., Ferone C., Izzo F., Langella A., Mercurio M., Migliaccio C.*, Occhicone A., Roviello G. & Tarallo O. - Alkaline and acid red mud-metakaolin based geopolymers: mineralogical and morphological characterization (S22)	631
De Luca M.*, Mackay E.J., Good T.R., Scisciani V., MacBeth C. & Patruno S. - Geological modelling and CO2 flow simulation: an integrated approach for basin scale storage in a saline aquifer (S44)	1157
Dumon Steenssens L.*, Lisco S., Micheletti F. & Mastronuzzi G. - Sedimentologic and petrographic characteristics of beach ridges in Terra Nova Bay (Antarctica) (S3)	146

Fonzetti R.*, Buttinelli M., Valoroso L., De Gori P. & Chiarabba C. - How high-resolution tomographic imaging can provide new information on fault interaction: the case of the 2009 L'Aquila seismic sequence (S48)	1249
Gravina T.* & Iannace A. - Fostering inquiry and engagement in Earth Science: designing and testing a specialized curriculum for Italian liceo students (S32)	859
Lämmle L., Moreira V.B., D'Aniello M.*, Ilacqua S., Brandolini P., Perez Filho A. & Donadio C. - Coastal erosion in urban areas and socio-environmental challenges: the case of São João da Barra, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil (S13)	430
Lapadula S., Balestra V.*, Barzaghi B., Falaschi M., Ficetola G.F. & Manenti R. - Rhythmic response of cave animals to external cycles (S43)	1138
Massa M.*, Calce S., Pachaiappan P. & Bontempi E. - Sewage sludge ashes characterization and microwave thermochemical treatment for fertilizer production (S17)	522
Palmucci A.*, Brozzetti F., Akimbekova A., Bello S., Ercoli M., Pauselli C., Carboni F., Barchi M.R., Lavecchia G. & Cirillo D. - Field and seismic reflection constraints for the geometric and kinematic characterization of the Quaternary extensional fault system in the Campania-Lucania arc (Southern Apennines, Italy) (S49)	1285
Peng S.Y.*, Wu K., Shi Z.Q., Qiao D. & Wang M.L. - Marlstone pseudo-desiccation cracks: an enigmatic sedimentary structure in the Early Triassic Feixianguan Formation in South China (S37)	1004
Ruospo D.*, Brogi A., Liotta D., Lucci F. & Zucchi M. - Syn-tectonic emplacement of late-magmatic granitic dyke swarms in the Capo Focardo area (Exhumed geothermal system of eastern Elba island, Italy) (S44)	1173
Semprebello A.*, Lazzaro G., Caruso C., Scirè Scappuzzo S., Morici S., Gattuso A. & Longo M. - Inverse modelling for estimating gas flow emission rate on stationary vents (S44)	1175
Vidal-Reyes M.*, Tesauro M., Amadori C., Nader F., Marini M., Reguzzi S. & Maino M. - Geothermal potential of the Tertiary Piedmont Basin: structural and lithological controls (S44)	1180
Vitrano A.*, Viti C., Della Ventura G., Lucci F. & Vetere F. - A preliminary petrological study of chondrules in NWA12800 meteorite (S20)	595
Yakisik O.*, Geloni C., Tamburelli S., Ruggieri G., Orlando A., Borrini D., Gherardi F. & Toscani G. - Laboratory experiments and geochemical models for CO ₂ mineralization in basalts (S44)	1181
Buffardi C.* - A geological-geotechnical approach to analyze the causes of subsidence in the Volturno River plain (northern Campania, Italy) (S26)	709
De Luca M.*, Mancinelli P., Patruno S. & Scisciani V. - Exploring the Greater East Shetland Platform (Northern North Sea, UK): integration and modelling of wellbore, seismic, gravity and magnetic data to evaluate its storage potential (S42)	1115
Hameed A.*, Confuorto P., Parise M., Lollino P., Ishfaq M. & Alias Aamir Soomro M.H. - Landslide susceptibility, vulnerability, and risk assessment based on remote sensing and GIS data models: a case study at the eastern Hindukush Mountain ranges, Pakistan (S25)	699
Niaz J.*, Lollino P. & Niaz A. - Integrated geophysical and geotechnical investigations of Upper Sarbala Landslide: a case study of Himalayas Mountain ranges, Pakistan (S25)	704
Balzano S., Ghani J., Bettinelli A., Zhao Y., Guo L. & Funari V.* - Mine tailings characterization and potential pychoremediation (S1)	103
Criniti S.* & Costamagna L.G. - Detrital modes of the Pennsylvanian-Permian sandstones in Central-Eastern Sardinia (Italy) (S40)	1076
Barbagallo V. *, Brandano M., Borzi L., Catania G., Cornacchia I., Distefano S., Pellegrino A., Macri P., Mancini A., Marianelli D., Maniscalco R. & Di Stefano A. - Integrated stratigraphy reveals Oligo-Miocene paleoclimatic phases: a Central Mediterranean insight from the western Hyblean sedimentary succession (S41)	1093
Baroni M.*, Baschetti B., Pisello A., Massironi M. & Petrelli M. - FRESCO, a Python open source tool to democratize CRISM spectral data management, analysis, and mapping (S35)	946
Binetti M.S.*, Massarelli C. & Uricchio V.F. - Monitoring and identification of environmental crimes: a satellite imagery and machine learning approach (S9)	317

Catania G.*, Barbagallo V., Brandano M., Borzi L., Cornacchia I., Distefano S., Pellegrino A., Mancini A., Marianelli D., Maniscalco R., Salerno A. & Di Stefano A. - Middle Miocene paleoclimatic phases: a Central Mediterranean perspective from the SE Sicily sedimentary succession (S4)	167
Sist E.*, Parisi F. & Princivalle F. - Crystal chemistry of clinopyroxenes and spinels enclosed in mantle xenoliths (Mandakh-Mandal-Gobi area, Mongolia) (S21)	614
Martella A.*, Sarti G. & Baneschi I. - Environmental and human control factors on the Holocene evolution of Venice lagoon: sedimentological and geochemical approach (S39)	1062
Clementucci R.*, Uchusov E., Willett S. & Wang Y. - External forcing on drainage divide evolution in rifted margins: case of Madagascar (S14)	442
Melchiori G.*, Pozzobon R., Massironi M. & Mazzarini F. - Structural analysis of wrinkle ridges in the region between Aristarchus plateau and Marius Hills in Oceanus Procellarum (Moon) (S35)	957
Sarı S.*, Cipollari P., Cosentino D., Gliozzi E., Lirer F., Cornacchia I., Marchegiano M., Öğretmen N., Kanbur S., Mattei M. & Cifelli F. - The Mid-Pleistocene transition in the Eastern Mediterranean: a multi-proxy approach to reconstruct its impact at the southern margin of the Central Anatolian Plateau (CAP) (S33)	902
Qadir A.*, Maiorana M., Chizzini N., Artoni A., Torelli L., Le Breton E. & Sulli A. - New insights into the structural setting of North-Western offshore Sicily, Central Mediterranean (S38)	1042
Srivastava E.*, Parrino N., Caldareri F., Morticelli M.G., Burrato P., Pucci S., Agate M. & Sulli A. - Late Pleistocene eustatic variations and fluvial terrace development in the Carboj River catchment, Southern Sicily (S12)	416

Phoenician seeds are rich in minerals: a multi-analytical study of mineralised archaeobotanical remains from the archaeological site of Motya

Moricca C.¹, Ciccola A.*¹, Matassa R.², Favero G.¹, Nottola S.³, Nigro L.⁴, Spagnoli F.⁴, Nucara A.⁵ & Sadori L.¹

¹ Dipartimento di Biologia Ambientale, Sapienza Università di Roma. ² Sezione di Fisica, Scuola di Scienze e Tecnologie, Università di Camerino. ³ Dipartimento di Scienze Anatomiche, Istologiche, Medico Legali e dell'Apparato Locomotore, Sapienza Università di Roma. ⁴ Dipartimento "Istituto Italiano di Studi Orientali - ISO", Sapienza Università di Roma. ⁵ Dipartimento di Fisica, Sapienza Università di Roma.

Corresponding author email: alessandro.ciccola@uniroma1.it

Keywords: archaeobotanical remains, mineralisation, FTIR.

Although most of the botanic remains recovered from archaeological sites in the Mediterranean area are constituted by charred samples, mineralized macro-remains obtained from excavations represent interesting case studies, because their actual chemical composition could be related to the archaeological context, while the chemotaxonomic data deriving from the identification of mineral phases could be used for the identification of fossil plant taxa, enriching the interpretations deriving from the morphological analysis (Vajda et al., 2017). In this study, a multi-disciplinary protocol combining Optical microscopy, Variable Pressure Scanning Electron Microscopy supported by dual-Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (VP-SEM-dEDS) and Fourier Transformed InfraRed spectroscopy (FTIR) was applied to investigate the fossilization of selected fruits and seeds retrieved in the Phoenician-Punic site of Motya (Sicily, Italy; Moricca et al., 2023). In the first steps, the archaeological remains were identified through a stereomicroscope using atlases (Neef et al., 2012; Sabato & Pena-Chocarro, 2021), while their mineralization conservation state was assessed. After this procedure, the carpological remains have been compared to those of their modern counterparts: both the archeological and modern samples were subjected to imaging, elemental and molecular analysis, in order to highlight processes attributable to biomineralization and to replacement mineralization. VP-SEM-dEDS was applied to observe the seed structure at higher magnification and to obtain elemental maps -both on the outer surface and on the cross section of archaeological and modern samples- to highlight the main differences in their elemental composition. In order to individuate the molecular compounds deriving from mineralization, FTIR spectroscopy was applied by means of two different approaches. Specular FTIR reflectance provided the fingerprints modern seeds and fruits and the chemical modifications on archaeobotanical remains. Besides, diffuse FTIR spectra on powdered samples revealed their bulk composition and the presence of organic residues in archaeological samples. The combination of the results obtained from microscopic and spectroscopic techniques resulted generally coherent in providing information about the chemical and mineral composition of the analyzed fossils, while the comparison with the imaging data provided preliminary hypotheses on the mineralization process, extending also the actual knowledge on the preservation condition of archaeobotanical materials from Motya.

Moricca C. et al. (2023) - Plant assemblage of the Phoenician sacrificial pit by the Temple of Melqart/Herakles (Motya, Sicily, Italy). *Environ. Archaeol.*, 28(5), 383-395, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14614103.2020.1852757>

Neef R. et al. (2012) - Digital Atlas of Economic Plants in Archaeology. Barkuis Pub, 724 pp., <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt20p56d7>.

Sabato D. & Pena-Chocarro L. (2021) - *Maris Nostri Novus Atlas. Seeds and fruits from the Mediterranean Basin.* Ediciones Doce Calles, 452 pp., <http://hdl.handle.net/10261/266042>

Vajda V. et al. (2017) - Molecular signatures of fossil leaves provide unexpected new evidence for extinct plant relationships. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.*, 1, 1093-1099, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0224-5>

SPONSOR

PLATINUM

GOLD

SILVER

BRONZE

CHARITY PARTNER

PATROCINI

